

European-wide city level air quality mapping

Evaluation of the current mapping methodology with respect to the level of cities and NUTS3 units and suggestions for future

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Summary

The report evaluates current air quality mapping methodology with respect to city- and NUTS3-levels mapping. For the cities of the City Audit and for the NUTS3 units, a comparison between the measurements and the mapping data has been carried out. Based on the results of the analysis, it can be stated that the current mapping can be used at the city and NUTS3 levels across Europe, for all examined pollutants (i.e., PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and ozone), despite a mild smoothing effect at locations of the measurement stations. If the agreement of the predicted and observed values should be improved, a potential methodological adaption might be applied, i.e., a post-processing correction based on the kriging residuals, namely by interpolating them by some exact interpolator, which respects the measurement values.

For all cities of the City Audit, the population-weighted concentration based on the mapping results have been calculated as a potential new approach for the city ranking. The results have been compared with the average of the stations located in the relevant city as used in the current city ranking. Based on the analysis, it seems that while the averaged measurement data from the background stations provides a superior information for the whole city in general (when the measurement error is neglected), the population-weighted concentration also fairly well represents the whole city (albeit a certain smoothing effect of the interpolation) and gives a consistent information for all cities, including those without station measurements. Thus, this indicator is recommended for further evaluation for the city ranking index.

Apart from this, few potential improvements of the mapping methodology have been examined. At first, the alternative mapping variant using the joint rural-urban background map layer created based on all background stations has been compared with the current variant using the merge of the rural and the urban background map layers for three pollutants (for PM₁₀, NO₂ and ozone). It has been found that this alternative mapping variant does not improve the mapping methodology. Next to this, alternative treatments of the background and traffic stations in the urban areas have been examined for PM₁₀ and NO₂. It has been found that an alternative adjustment of the urban traffic map layer slightly improves PM₁₀ (not NO₂) mapping. Potential application of this slight improvement should be evaluated in relation to increased demandingness of this improved mapping procedure. During the analysis, it was confirmed that urban traffic areas are underestimated in the final 1x1 km² maps. For future, if the urban traffic areas should be better represented in the final maps, an increased map resolution (e.g. 100x100 m² instead of the current 1x1 km²) is recommended.

Several possibilities of future development towards the European-wide city level mapping in a fine resolution have been suggested. This includes applying the existing methodology but exploiting a high-resolution model output (e.g. from the uEMEP model), downscaling of the existing spatial maps using a geostatistical downscaling technique in combination with fine-resolution proxy datasets, and the exploitation of existing low-cost sensor networks for providing additional information within a city in areas that is not adequately covered by traditional air quality stations.

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1 Introduction

The routinely used data fusion air quality mapping (Horálek et al., 2022 and references therein) was developed for estimating European-wide and country-wide exposure. Currently, a need for consistent information at NUTS3 and city levels across Europe has emerged, because the air quality monitoring and modelling background information has evolved substantially since the mapping methodology was developed. Apart from this, a city ranking index has been recently suggested, based on the measurements within the cities. Nevertheless, an improved city ranking indices based on the spatial maps might be developed, if the maps are consistent at the city level.

For these reasons, the current mapping methodology has been checked with respect to the city- and NUTS3-levels mapping. For the cities of the Urban Audit and for the NUTS3 units, a comparison between the measurements and the mapping data has been carried out. Due to the short-term aim to improve the city ranking, more detailed analysis for the cities of the Urban Audit have been executed compared to the NUTS3 units. The analysis has been performed for PM₁₀ annual average, PM_{2.5} annual average, NO₂ annual average and the ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of daily maximum 8-hourly means, based on 2019 data.

Potential improvements of the mapping methodology (for both the NUTS3 and the city levels) have been examined. Specifically, alternative treatments of rural and urban stations has been evaluated. The analysis has been performed for PM₁₀ annual average, NO₂ annual average and the ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of daily maximum 8-hourly means, based on 2019 data.

In addition, the report suggests potential future developments concerning the European-wide city level mapping. A need of a more fine spatial resolution compared to the current 1x1 km² grid has emerged. Specifically, for the purposes of the integrated assessment of noise and air quality in Europe, consistent air quality maps for European cities on a 100x100 metres grid (i.e., in the same resolution as the noise maps) are required. Several possibilities of future development towards European-wide city level mapping at a fine spatial resolution have been suggested.

Chapter 2 describes the methodology and Chapter 3 shows the input data applied. Chapter 4 examines the comparison between the mapping and the measurement data for the cities and the NUTS3 units. Chapter 5 presents an alternative way of dealing with rural, urban background and urban traffic stations. Chapter 6 introduces potential approaches for city-level mapping at the European scale. Chapter 7 gives conclusions and recommendations. The Annex presents numerical results for the cities of the Urban Audit dataset.

2 Methodology and input data

2.1 Mapping methodology

The basic mapping methodology applied is the Regression – Interpolation – Merging Mapping (RIMM) as routinely used in the spatial mapping under the ETC/ATNI (Horálek et. al., 2022). It consists of a linear regression model followed by kriging of the residuals from that regression model:

$$\hat{Z}(s_0) = c + a_1X_1(s_0) + a_2X_2(s_0) + \dots + a_nX_n(s_0) + \hat{\eta}(s_0) \quad (2.1)$$

where $\hat{Z}(s_0)$ is the estimated concentration at a point s_0 ,
 $\hat{Z}(s_0)X_1(s_0)$ is the chemical transport model (CTM) data at point s_0 ,
 $X_2(s_0), \dots, X_n(s_0)$ are $n-1$ other supplementary variables at point s_0 ,
 c, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are the $n+1$ parameters of the linear regression model calculated based on the data at the points of measurement,
 $\hat{\eta}(s_0)$ is the spatial interpolation of the residuals of the linear regression model at point s_0 , based on the residuals at the points of measurement.

For different pollutants and area types (rural, urban background, and for PM and NO₂ also urban traffic), different supplementary data are used.

The spatial interpolation of the regression residuals is carried out using ordinary kriging, according to

$$\hat{\eta}(s_0) = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i \eta(s_i) \quad \text{with } \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i = 1, \quad (2.2)$$

where $\hat{\eta}(s_0)$ is the interpolated value at a point s_0 ,
 N is the number of the measurement points used in the interpolation, which is fixed based on the variogram; in any case, $20 \leq N \leq 50$,
 $\eta(s_i)$ is the residual of the linear regression model at the measurement point s_i ,
 $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_N$ are the estimated weights based on the variogram, see Cressie (1993).

The variogram (as a measure of a spatial correlation) is estimated using a spherical function (with parameters nugget, sill, range). For details, see Horálek et al. (2022 and references therein).

For PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, prior to linear regression and interpolation, a logarithmic transformation to measurements and CTM output is executed. After interpolation, a back-transformation is applied. (For motivation, see Horálek et al., 2010.)

In the case of PM_{2.5}, in the mapping procedure we also use data from so-called pseudo PM_{2.5} stations. These data are the estimates of PM_{2.5} concentrations at the locations of PM₁₀ stations with no PM_{2.5} measurement, based on the linear regression model calculated based on the data at the points of stations with both PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ measurements. For details, see Horálek et al. (2022).

Separate map layers are created for rural background, urban background and urban traffic areas on a grid at resolution of 1x1 km² (for PM and NO₂) and for rural and urban background areas on a grid at resolution of 10x10 km² (for ozone). The rural background map layer is based on rural background stations, the urban background map layer on urban and suburban background stations and the urban traffic map layer is based on urban and suburban traffic stations.

The separate handling of the rural and urban background map layers is based on the assumption that the estimated rural map layer value is lower (PM and NO₂) or higher (ozone) than the estimated urban background map layer value. In areas (i.e., grid cells) where this criterion does not hold, both the rural and the urban background map layers are substituted by a joint urban/rural background map layer (created using all background stations regardless their type) and such adjusted rural and urban background map layers are further applied. Specifically, these layers are adjusted according to

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{Z}_{R_adj}(s_0) &= \hat{Z}_R(s_0) && \text{for } \hat{Z}_R(s_0) \leq \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0) \text{ or } \hat{Z}_J(s_0) > \hat{Z}_R(s_0) > \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0) \\
&= \hat{Z}_J(s_0) && \text{for } \hat{Z}_R(s_0) > \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0) \text{ and } \hat{Z}_J(s_0) \leq \hat{Z}_R(s_0) \\
\hat{Z}_{UB_adj}(s_0) &= \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0) && \text{for } \hat{Z}_R(s_0) \leq \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0) \text{ or } \hat{Z}_R(s_0) > \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0) > \hat{Z}_J(s_0) \\
&= \hat{Z}_J(s_0) && \text{for } \hat{Z}_R(s_0) > \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0) \text{ and } \hat{Z}_J(s_0) \geq \hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0)
\end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

where $\hat{Z}_{R_adj}(s_0)$ is the estimated concentration in a grid cell s_0 for the adjusted rural map layer,
 $\hat{Z}_{UB_adj}(s_0)$ is the estimated concentration in a grid cell s_0 for the adjusted urban background map layer,

$\hat{Z}_R(s_0)$ is the estimated concentration in a grid cell s_0 for the rural map layer,
 $\hat{Z}_{UB}(s_0)$ is the estimated concentration in a grid cell s_0 for the urban background map layer,
 $\hat{Z}_J(s_0)$ is the estimated concentration in a grid cell s_0 for the joint urban/rural background map layer.

The separate handling of the urban background and urban traffic map layers (for PM and NO₂) is based on the assumption that the estimated urban background map layer value is lower than the estimated urban traffic map layer value. In areas where this criterion does not hold, the urban traffic map layer is substituted by the urban background map layer and such adjusted urban traffic map layer is further applied. Thus, the urban traffic map layer is adjusted according to

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{Z}_{UT_adj}(s_0) &= \hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0) && \text{for } \hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0) > \hat{Z}_{UB_adj}(s_0) \\
&= \hat{Z}_{UB_adj}(s_0) && \text{for } \hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0) \leq \hat{Z}_{UB_adj}(s_0)
\end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

where $\hat{Z}_{UT_adj}(s_0)$ is the estimated concentration in a grid cell s_0 for adjusted urban traffic map layer,
 $\hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0)$ is the estimated concentration in a grid cell s_0 for urban traffic map layer.

Alternative adjustment of the traffic map layer is examined in this report (Section 5.2), according to

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{Z}_{UT_adj}(s_0) &= \hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0) && \text{for } \hat{Z}_{UB_adj}(s_0) \leq \hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0) \text{ or } \hat{Z}_{UB_adj}(s_0) > \hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0) > \hat{Z}_{JU}(s_0) \\
&= \hat{Z}_{JU}(s_0) && \text{for } \hat{Z}_{UB_adj}(s_0) > \hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0) \text{ and } \hat{Z}_{UT}(s_0) \leq \hat{Z}_{JU}(s_0)
\end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

where $\hat{Z}_{JU}(s_0)$ is the estimated concentration in a grid cell s_0 for the joint urban background-traffic map layer (created based on both background and traffic urban/suburban stations).

Subsequently, the separate map layers (as created at 1x1 km² resolution or 1x1 km² resolution, in dependence on a pollutant) are merged into one combined final map at 1x1 km² resolution (for all pollutants), according to

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{Z}_F(s_0) &= (1 - w_U(s_0)) \cdot \hat{Z}_{R_adj}(s_0) + w_U(s_0)(1 - w_T(s_0)) \cdot \hat{Z}_{UB_adj}(s_0) + w_T(s_0) \cdot \hat{Z}_{UT_adj}(s_0) \\
&&& \text{for PM and NO}_2 \\
\hat{Z}_F(s_0) &= (1 - w_U(s_0)) \cdot \hat{Z}_{R_adj}(s_0) + w_U(s_0) \cdot \hat{Z}_{UB_adj}(s_0) && \text{for ozone}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.6}$$

where $\hat{Z}_F(s_0)$ is the resulting estimated concentration in a grid cell s_0 for the final map,
 $\hat{Z}_{R_adj}(s_0)$, $\hat{Z}_{UB_adj}(s_0)$ and $\hat{Z}_{UT_adj}(s_0)$ are the estimated concentration in a grid cell s_0 for the adjusted rural, urban background and urban traffic map layer, respectively,
 $w_U(s_0)$ is the weight representing the ratio of the urban character of the grid cell s_0 ,
 $w_T(s_0)$ is the weight representing the ratio of areas exposed to traffic in a grid cell s_0 .

The weight $w_U(s_0)$ is based on the population density (in 1x1 km² resolution), while the weight $w_T(s_0)$ is based on the buffers around the roads. For details, see Horálek et al. (2022 and references therein).

2.2 Uncertainty estimation and comparison of different approaches

The uncertainty estimation and the comparison of different approaches of the European map is based on cross-validation and a simple comparison between the measurement data in the station points and

the estimated values of the 1x1 km² grid cells. The comparison is performed either based on the individual stations or based on the average of the station values in a given city or NUTS3 unit.

The predicted and measurement values are compared using statistical indicators and scatter plots. The main indicators used are root mean square error (RMSE), relative root mean square error (RRMSE) and bias (mean prediction error, MPE):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{Z}(s_i) - Z(s_i))^2} \quad (2.7)$$

$$RRMSE = \frac{RMSE}{\bar{Z}} \cdot 100 \quad (2.8)$$

$$bias(MPE) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{Z}(s_i) - Z(s_i)) \quad (2.9)$$

where $Z(s_i)$ is the air quality measured indicator value at the i^{th} point, $i = 1, \dots, N$,
 $\hat{Z}(s_i)$ is the air quality estimated indicator value at the i^{th} point using other information, without the indicator value derived from the measured concentration at the i^{th} point,
 \bar{Z} is the mean of the indicator values $Z(s_1), \dots, Z(s_N)$, as measured at points $i = 1, \dots, N$,
 N is the number of the measuring points.

Other indicators are R^2 and the regression equation parameters *slope* and *intercept*, following from the scatter plot between the predicted (using cross-validation) and the observed concentrations.

RMSE and RRMSE should be as small as possible, bias (MPE) should be as close to zero as possible, R^2 should be as close to 1 as possible, slope a should be as close to 1 as possible, and intercept c should be as close to zero as possible (in the regression equation $y = a \cdot x + c$).

Additionally, indicators *FAC50%* (for PM and ozone) and *FAC30%* (for NO₂) are used, which show the fraction of the predicted gridded values in the points of measurement stations outside $\pm 50\%$ or $\pm 30\%$ of the measured values. This indicator is motivated by the uncertainty data quality objective for modelling which is 50 % for PM annual averages and ozone 8-hour averages and 30 % for annual NO₂ averages, see Directive 2008/50/EC (EC, 2008). *FAC50%* and *FAC30%* should be as small as possible.

2.3 Population exposure

Based on the concentration maps and the population data, the population-weighted average concentrations for individual cities and NUTS3 units have been calculated, according to

$$c_{popw_avg} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N c(i) \cdot p(i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N p(i)} \quad (2.10)$$

where c_{popw_avg} is the population-weighted average concentration in a given year,
 $p(i)$ is the population in the i -th grid cell,
 $c(i)$ is the mean concentration in the i -th grid cell (based on the air quality map),
 N is the number of grid cells in the individual city or NUTS3 unit.

2.4 Current and proposed approaches for city ranking

Currently, the EEA's European city air quality viewer (EEA, 2021) ranks cities of the Urban Audit based on the average of the annual aggregated measurement data from all urban and suburban background stations located in the relevant city. Only stations with annual data coverage of at least 75 percent are used. The current city ranking is based on the PM_{2.5} annual average. In principle, the similar ranking might be calculated for other pollutants as well (especially for NO₂ and potentially also for ozone). The current city ranking is based on the average results of the last two years for the relevant city. For the last year, the non-validated "up-to-date" air quality data are used, while for the year before last, the validated air quality data.

The proposed approach for city ranking is based on the population-weighted concentration of the relevant city based on the mapping results (see Section 2.3). Again, it might be calculated for different pollutants. The motivation for the proposed approach is this: It might better represent the whole city (while the measurements are quite randomly located in the city area). It takes into account both background and traffic areas (in the case of PM and NO₂). And it can be calculated also for the cities with no measurement. A potential weakness of this approach is that the spatial maps smooth the measurement values. (Thus, the smoothing effect of the kriging interpolation is examined in this report, see the main analysis of Section 4.1.)

In this report, the concentration values calculated for the current and the proposed approaches for different pollutants are briefly compared, based on the 2019 data (see the additional parts of Section 4.1).

3 Input data

All input data used for mapping are the same as in Horálek et al. (2022). Apart from this, geographical data of cities and NUTS3 units have been used.

In all calculations and map presentations, the EEA standard projection ETRS89-LAEA5210 (also known as ETRS89 / LAEA Europe, see www.epsg.io) is used. The mapping domain consists of the areas of all EEA member and cooperating countries, and other microstates, as far as they fall into the EEA map extent Map_2c (EEA, 2018). The mapping area covers the whole Europe apart from Belarus, Moldova, Ukraine and the European parts of Russia and Kazakhstan.

3.1 Air quality monitoring data

In terms of air quality measurements, the validated data from the Air Quality e-Reporting database (EEA, 2021a) supplemented with several EMEP rural stations from the database EBAS (NILU, 2021) have been used. The annual aggregation for 2019 has been applied, namely PM_{10} annual mean [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$], $PM_{2.5}$ annual mean [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$], NO_2 annual mean [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$] and ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$]. Only data from stations classified as *background* (for all types of area, i.e. *rural*, *suburban*, *urban*) are used for ozone, while for PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$ and NO_2 , in addition to the background stations, also stations classified as *traffic* for the types of area *suburban* and *urban* are used. The stations classified as *industrial* are not considered. We did not use the stations from areas outside the EEA map extent Map_2c (EEA, 2018), i.e., from French overseas areas (departments), Svalbard, Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands. Only stations with annual data coverage of at least 75 percent are used.

Table 3.1 presents the number of the measurement stations used for the individual pollutants, both for the entire mapping and for the analysis within the cities of the Urban Audit.

Table 3.1 Number of stations used for each pollutant indicator and area type, 2019

Station type	PM ₁₀		PM _{2.5}		NO ₂		Ozone	
	All	Cities	All	Cities	All	Cities	All	Cities
Rural background	381	-	220	-	480	-	550	-
Urban/suburb. background	1452	647	768	452	1381	719	1201	599
Urban/suburban traffic	775	527	379	262	1060	789	-	-

For the $PM_{2.5}$ mapping, in addition to the $PM_{2.5}$ stations, 184 rural background, 722 urban/suburban background and 412 urban/suburban traffic PM_{10} stations (at locations without $PM_{2.5}$ measurement) have been also used for the purpose of calculating the pseudo $PM_{2.5}$ station data.

3.2 Modelling and other proxy data

The chemical transport model (CTM) used here is EMEP MSC-W (version rv4.35) at $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ spatial resolution, see Simpson et al. (2012) and NMI (2021). EMEP (2020) provides details on the EMEP modelling for 2019 using 2018 emission and 2019 meteorology. The same set of parameters like for the air quality observations have been used. The annual aggregated (for PM and NO_2) and hourly (for ozone) data have been downloaded from NMI (2020), the hourly data have been aggregated. The annual data have been spatially transformed into the $1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$ (for PM and NO_2) and $10 \times 10 \text{ km}^2$ (for ozone) grids: the concentration value in each $1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$ (or $10 \times 10 \text{ km}^2$) grid cell is calculated as a weighted average of the parts of the original $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ grid cells covering the relevant $1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$ (or $10 \times 10 \text{ km}^2$) grid cell.

The meteorological data used are the ECWMF data extracted from the Climate Data Store (CDS), ECMWF (2021). Hourly data for 2019 coming from the reanalysed data set ERA5-Land in $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$

resolution have been used, which was complemented by the data set ERA-5 in 0.25°x0.25° resolution in the coastal areas. The hourly data have been derived into the parameters needed, aggregated into the annual statistics and converted into the reference EEA 1x1 km² and 10x10 km² grids. Meteorological parameters used are *wind speed* (annual mean, in m.s⁻¹), *relative humidity* (annual mean, in percent) and *surface net solar radiation* (annual mean of daily sums, in MWs.m⁻²).

The satellite data used comes from the TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI) onboard of the Sentinel-5 satellite (Veefkind et al., 2012), namely the S5P_OFFL_L2__NO2 product (van Geffen et al., 2019, 2020) in the spatial resolution of cc. 7 km by 3.5 km (until August 2019) and cc. 5.5 km by 3.5 km (after August 2019), which was re-gridded to a 1x1 km² resolution to match the other input datasets. The daily gridded files have been averaged to an annual mean. The parameter used is *NO₂ annual average tropospheric vertical column density (VCD)* for 2019 [number of NO₂ molecules per cm² of earth surface].

Altitude data (in m) of Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data 2010 (GMTED2010) have been used, see Danielson et al. (2011). The data in an original grid resolution of 15x15 arcseconds was spatially transformed into the 1x1 km² and 10x10 km² grids.

The land cover data used is the CORINE Land Cover 2018 (CLC2018) – grid 100 x 100 m², Version 2020_20 (EU, 2020). For regions not included in the CLC2018 dataset we have used as alternative sources MDA (2015) and ESA (2019) data. Like in Horálek et al. (2022), the 44 CLC classes have been re-grouped into 8 more general classes. In this report, we use five of these general classes, namely high density residential areas (HDR), low density residential areas (LDR), agricultural areas (AGR), natural areas (NAT), and traffic areas (TRAF). Two aggregations have been used, i.e., into 1x1 km² grid and into the circle with radius of 5 km. For details, see Horálek et al. (2022).

Population data (in inhabitants.km⁻², census 2011) in the 1x1 km² resolution are based on Geostat 2011 grid dataset (Eurostat, 2014). For regions not included in the Geostat 2011 dataset we have used as alternative sources JRC (2009) and ORNL (EEA, 2010) data. For details, see Horálek et al. (2022).

GRIP vector road type data is used (Meijer et al., 2018). Based on these data (i.e., buffers around the roads), traffic map layers (Section 2.1) are merged into the final maps (Horálek et al., 2022).

3.3 Regular air quality mapping data

Throughout the report, the regular mapping results for 2019 created based on the current version of the RIMM methodology (Section 2.1) and using the input data as described in Sections 3.1 and 3.2 are used as the basic gridded mapping data. For details of these air quality maps, see Horálek et al. (2022).

3.4 Geographical data of cities and NUTS3 units

In this report, the cities of Urban Audit 2020 (Eurostat, 2020) have been used. This geospatial dataset includes cities with a population over 50 000 inhabitants. In total, 945 cities of 31 countries (i.e., EU-27 plus Iceland, Norway, Switzerland and the United Kingdom) are included in this data set. Note that 14 of them (located in French overseas departments, Azores, Madeira and Canary Islands) fall outside the EEA map extent Map_2c (EEA, 2018) and thus have not been used in the analysis. For boundaries of the cities, polygon features of shapefiles included in the zipped file “ref-urau-2020-100k.shp” of the Urban Audit 2020 data set (Eurostat, 2021) has been used. This data set contains boundaries of cities, greater cities and functional urban areas as defined according to the EC-OECD city definition (EC, 2012). Two Urban Audit categories have been used. The Urban Audit category “C” (City), i.e. the core city (using an administrative definition) has been applied for 936 cities. Specifically, all records (936) from shapefile “CITIES” have been used. For 9 cities, namely Brussels, Charleroi, Liege, Mons, La Louviere, Verviers (all BE), Larnaca (CY), Athens, Thessaloniki (both GR) with no record in shapefile “CITIES”, the category “K” (Greater City) has been used, i.e., their records from shapefile “GREATER_CITIES” have been added.

For the NUTS3 units, the EuroBoundaryMap Version 2020 geodatabase has been used (Eurogeographics, 2020), which contains the boundaries of Local Administrative Units (LAU) including the NUTS3 units (in NUTS 2016 version, see EU, 2016). In total, 1497 NUTS3 units have been used.

For the purposes of the population exposure calculation (Section 2.3), the geographical data have been merged with the 1x1 km² grid population data. The individual grid cells have been attached to the above-mentioned cities and NUTS3 units. In doing this, a certain level of simplification has been applied. For a grid cell to be attached to a city and a NUTS3 unit, it was enough if there was some overlap of the polygon of the city / the NUTS3 unit and the grid cell. However, each pixel could be attached to no more than one city and one NUTS3 unit. If a grid cell was overlapped by more than one polygon of the city / the NUTS3 unit, it was attached to the city / NUTS3 region that overlapped the largest part of it.

4 Comparison between measurement and mapping data for cities and NUTS3 units

4.1 Cities of the Urban Audit

For all cities of the Urban Audit, we have performed the comparison between the average of all measurements from urban and suburban stations within the limits of the city (see Section 3.4) with the average of the relevant gridded mapped values in the locations of these measurements. For PM and NO₂, the analysis has been done separately for the background and the traffic stations: the comparison of the station values has been done against the urban background and the urban traffic map layers, respectively. For ozone, no distinction of stations has been performed, as only background stations are used in the ozone mapping; the comparison has been done against the urban background map layer.

The reason of this comparison is to evaluate the impact of the smoothing effect of the mapping methodology in the individual cities. The difference between a measurement value in a point of a station and an estimated value in the underlying grid cell is caused partly by the smoothing effect of the kriging interpolation (if the value of the nugget parameter of variogram is higher than zero) and partly by the spatial averaging of the values in the 1x1 km² grid cells. (Note that in the interpolation smoothing effect, the measurement uncertainty also plays a role.) While the kriging interpolation is optimized across the whole European-wide mapping domain, this comparison enables us to see the smoothing effect at the city level.

Apart from this, for all cities of the Urban Audit, we have also calculated the population-weighted concentration (using the air quality maps, see Section 3.3) and have compared it with the average of the concentrations measured at the stations located in the relevant city in two variants, namely for the urban/suburban background stations and for all urban/suburban stations independently of their type. This exercise has been done in the context of the current and the proposed approaches for city ranking (see Section 2.4). The reason is to compare three approaches of the city ranking: the current (i.e., based on the average of the background measurements) and an alternative one (based on the average of all measurements) with the proposed one (i.e., based on the population-weighted concentration). Our aim is to see whether the results of the proposed approach show results that are reasonable. If so (and if the smoothing effect is not too large), the proposed approach can be further considered to be a basis for an updated city ranking.

While the overall results of the comparison are provided in this Section 4.1, the numerical results for individual cities of the Urban Audit are given in the Annex.

4.1.1 PM₁₀

For PM₁₀ annual average 2019, the comparison has been done for 454 cities with at least one urban or suburban background station and for 382 cities with at least one urban or suburban traffic station (and additionally also for 585 cities with at least one urban or suburban station without regard of its type). Altogether, 646 urban/suburban background stations and 527 urban/suburban traffic stations have been used in this analysis.

Table 4.1 shows the comparison between the city averages of the predicted gridded mapped values and the relevant averages of the measurements in locations within individual cities, separately for urban background and urban traffic locations (and the relevant map layers).

Table 4.1: Comparison of predicted grid values from separate urban background (top) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers against relevant measurements from urban/suburban background or traffic stations in average per city of the Urban Audit, using RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from scatter plots and FAC50% for PM₁₀ annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE, R² and FAC50 %.

PM ₁₀ Annual Average	Urban background areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban background	2.21	11.1%	0.29	0.872	y = 0.875x + 2.80	0.004
PM ₁₀ Annual Average	Urban traffic areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban traffic	2.09	9.6%	0.03	0.883	y = 0.834x + 3.66	0.005

Figure 4.1 shows the scatterplots for these comparisons.

Figure 4.1: Correlation between predicted grid values from urban background (left) and urban traffic (right) map layer (y-axis) versus measurements from urban/suburban background (left) and urban/suburban traffic stations (right) (x-axis) in average per city of the Urban Audit for PM₁₀ annual average 2019

The comparison presented in Table 4.1 and Figure 4.1 shows quite good agreement of the averaged measurement and mapped values: the relative uncertainty (in terms of RRMSE) is 11 % in the urban background areas and 10 % in the urban traffic areas and R² from the scatter plots is at the level of about 87 % for the urban background areas and about 88 % at the urban traffic areas. In the urban background areas, a slight bias of 0.3 µg.m⁻³ is observed, while a zero bias can be seen in the urban traffic areas. The fraction of the predicted gridded values outside ±50 % of the measured concentration levels is 0.004 (i.e., 2 of 454 cities) for the urban background areas and 0.005 (i.e., 2 of 382 cities) for the urban traffic areas. This seems to be an acceptable result.

In addition to the FAC50% indicator, a more detailed view on the differences between the predicted gridded and the measurement concentration values is presented in Table 4.2, in both absolute and relative numbers. The aim of this table is to provide data for evaluating whether the differences between the estimated and the measured values are allowable. One can see that for cc. 95 % of the cities, the differences are smaller than both one fifth (i.e., 20 %) and 5 µg.m⁻³.

Table 4.2: Ratio of absolute differences between predicted grid values from urban background (top) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers and relevant measurements from urban/suburban background or traffic stations in average per city of the Urban Audit for PM₁₀ annual mean 2019, which exceed certain absolute (left) and relative (right) difference levels

PM ₁₀ Annual Average	Urban background areas							
	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	> 7.5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>30%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.269	0.141	0.042	0.006	0.286	0.143	0.055	0.020
PM ₁₀ Annual Average	Urban traffic areas							
	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	> 7.5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>30%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.249	0.123	0.058	0.021	0.283	0.141	0.031	0.003

As mentioned above, the differences are caused partially by the smoothing effect of the kriging interpolation and partially by the spatial averaging of the values within the 1x1 km² grid cells. The effect of smoothing leads to underestimation of high values (cf. the slope of the regression equation consistently below 1) and overestimation of low values (cf. the intersect consistently above 0).

Based on the results of the city level analysis, we suppose that **the current mapping can be used at the city level across Europe**. If the agreement of the predicted and observed values should be improved in terms of the bias and the agreement of the predicted gridded and the measurement values, **a potential methodological adaptation might be a post-processing correction based on the kriging residuals**, specifically, by interpolating them by any exact interpolator (e.g. kriging with the zero nugget and a small range), which respects the measurement values, without regard to the worsening of the cross-validation uncertainty of the whole interpolation.

Next to the comparison of the measurement and underlying gridded values, we have additionally calculated the population-weighted concentration for each individual city (i.e., potential new approach for the city ranking, if applied for PM₁₀) and compared it with the average of the concentration values measured at stations located in the relevant city in two variants, i.e., for all urban/suburban stations without regard on their type and for the urban/suburban background stations only, which is a similar approach to the current city ranking for PM_{2.5}. See Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Correlation between the population-weighted concentration (y-axis) versus average of measurements from urban/suburban background (left) and all (right) stations (x-axis) located in relevant city of the Urban Audit for PM₁₀ annual average 2019

The reason of this comparison is to see the differences of the three approaches. Next to the scatterplot, the bias has been calculated, being $0.3 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for the comparison based on the urban/suburban background stations and $-1.2 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for the comparison based on all urban/suburban (i.e., both background and traffic) stations. As expected, the population-weighted concentrations show better agreement with the averages of the measurements from the background stations compared to the averages of the measurements from both background and traffic stations, due to higher representativeness (in terms of radius) of the background stations. Next to this, the population-weighted concentrations give in general somewhat higher results compared to the averages of the background stations and somewhat lower results compared to the averages of both background and traffic stations, as expected. In order to examine which part of the variability shown in the scatterplots of Figure 4.2 is attributable to the interpolation and the resolution smoothing effect (and the measurement uncertainty) and which part to the spatial variability within the city, we have compared for each city the population-weighted concentration with the average of the gridded mapped values in the locations of the measurement stations, again in two variants (i.e., for urban/suburban background stations and for urban/suburban stations without regard of their type). See Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Correlation between the population-weighted concentration (y-axis) versus average of predicted gridded values at locations of urban/suburban background (left) and all (right) stations (x-axis) located in relevant city of the Urban Audit for PM₁₀ annual average 2019

The relevant bias is $0.0 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ and $-1.3 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for the comparison based on the predicted gridded values at locations of urban/suburban background stations and all urban/suburban stations, respectively. One can see a good agreement between the population-weighted concentrations and the averages of the predicted gridded values at locations of urban/suburban background stations.

Comparing Figures 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3, one can state that the influence of the traffic areas in the population-weighted concentrations is marginal only. Next to this, one can state that the most of the variability between the population-weighted concentrations (i.e., the potential new approach for the city ranking) and the average of the urban/suburban background measurements (i.e., the current approach for the city ranking) is caused by the smoothing effect of the interpolation, while the variability within the city plays minor role only, in general.

Based on these results, one can state that (i) the averaged measurement data from the background stations provides a superior information for the whole city in general (when the measurement error is neglected); (ii) the population-weighted concentration also fairly well represents the whole city (albeit a certain smoothing effect of the interpolation) and gives a consistent information for all cities, including those without station measurements. Thus, when thinking about a potential update of the

city ranking (if applied for PM₁₀), **the approach based on the population-weighted concentration can be further considered as a basis for an updated city ranking, preferably in a combination with the current approach** based on the averaged measurement data from the background stations in cities with at least one background measurement station.

4.1.2 PM_{2.5}

For PM_{2.5} annual average 2019, the comparison has been performed for 357 cities with at least one urban or suburban background station and for 208 cities with at least one urban or suburban traffic station (and additionally also for 434 cities with at least one urban or suburban station without regard of its type). Altogether, 439 urban/suburban background stations and 262 urban/suburban traffic stations have been used in this analysis.

Table 4.3 shows the comparison between the city means of the predicted gridded mapped values and the relevant averages of the measurements in locations within individual cities, separately for urban background and urban traffic locations (and map layers).

Table 4.3: Comparison of predicted grid values from separate urban background (top) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers against relevant measurements from urban/suburban background or traffic stations in average per city of the Urban Audit, using RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from scatter plots and FAC50% for PM_{2.5} annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE, R² and FAC50%.

PM _{2.5} Annual Average	Urban background areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban background	1.49	12.0%	0.29	0.896	y = 0.903x + 1.50	0.008
PM _{2.5} Annual Average	Urban traffic areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban traffic	1.49	11.8%	0.08	0.814	y = 0.825x + 1.40	0.005

Figure 4.4 shows the scatterplots for these comparisons.

Figure 4.4: Correlation between predicted grid values from background (left) and urban traffic (right) map layer (y-axis) versus measurements from urban/suburban background (left) and urban/suburban traffic stations (right) (x-axis) in average per city of the Urban Audit for PM_{2.5} annual average 2019

The results are quite similar to those for PM₁₀. The comparison shows a fair agreement, see the relative uncertainty (in terms of RRMSE) of 12 % in both urban background and urban traffic areas and R² from the scatter plots at the level of about 90 % for the urban background areas and about 81 % at the urban traffic areas. A bias of 0.3 µg.m⁻³ is observed in the urban background areas, while a slight bias of 0.1 µg.m⁻³ can be seen in the urban traffic areas. The fraction of the predicted gridded values outside ±50 % of the measured concentration levels is 0.008 (i.e., 3 of 355 cities) for the urban background areas and 0.005 (i.e., 1 of 208 cities) for the urban traffic areas. Again, this is quite an acceptable result. Thus, the same conclusion as for PM₁₀ can be stated, i.e., that the current mapping can be used at the city level across Europe.

In addition to the FAC50 % indicator, a more detailed view on the differences between the predicted gridded and the measured concentrations is presented in Table 4.4, in both absolute and relative numbers. E.g., one can see that for 93 % of the cities, the differences are smaller than 3 µg.m⁻³.

Table 4.4: Ratio of absolute differences between predicted grid values from urban background (top) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers and relevant measurements from urban/suburban background or traffic stations in average per city of the Urban Audit for PM_{2.5} annual mean 2019, which exceed certain absolute (left) and relative (right) difference levels

PM _{2.5} Annual Average	Urban background areas							
	> 1 µg.m ⁻³	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>30%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.396	0.138	0.070	0.011	0.317	0.163	0.081	0.028
PM _{2.5} Annual Average	Urban traffic areas							
	> 1 µg.m ⁻³	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>30%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.370	0.135	0.067	0.014	0.279	0.178	0.101	0.034

Next to the comparison of the measurement and underlying gridded values, we have additionally calculated the population-weighted concentration for each individual city (i.e., suggested new approach for the city ranking) and compared it with the average of the concentration values measured at the stations located in the relevant city (i.e., for all urban/suburban background stations, the similar approach as the current city ranking; and for all urban/suburban stations without regard of their type). See Figure 4.5.

Figure 4.5: Correlation between the population-weighted concentration (y-axis) versus average of measurements from urban/suburban background (left) and all (right) stations (x-axis) located in relevant city of the Urban Audit for PM_{2.5} annual average 2019

Next to the scatterplot, the bias has been calculated, being 0.3 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for the comparison based on the urban/suburban background stations and -0.2 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for the comparison based on all urban/suburban (i.e., both background and traffic) stations. The difference compared to PM₁₀ (namely, the minor bias for comparison based on all stations) is caused by a smaller number of PM_{2.5} traffic stations and by a smaller traffic vs. background ratio of concentration levels for PM_{2.5} compared to PM₁₀. Apart from this, similar results to those for PM₁₀ can be seen.

Again, we have also compared the population-weighted concentrations with the average of the gridded mapped values in the locations of the measurement stations within the relevant cities (in two variants), in order to examine which part of the variability shown in the scatterplots of Figure 4.5 is attributable to the interpolation the resolution smoothing effect and which part to the spatial variability within the city. See Figure 4.6. The relevant bias is 0.1 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ and -0.3 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for the comparison based on the predicted gridded values at locations of urban/suburban background stations and all urban/suburban stations, respectively.

Figure 4.6: Correlation between the population-weighted concentration (y-axis) versus average of predicted gridded values at locations of urban/suburban background (left) and all (right) stations (x-axis) located in relevant city of the Urban Audit for PM_{2.5} annual average 2019

Similarly as in the case of PM₁₀, one can state that the most of the variability between the population-weighted concentrations (i.e., the potential new approach for the city ranking) and the average of the urban/suburban background measurements (i.e., the current approach for the city ranking) is caused by the smoothing effect of the interpolation, while the variability within the city plays a minor role, in general.

Again, we can suppose that while the averaged measurement data from the background stations provides a superior information for the whole city in general (when the measurement error is neglected), the population-weighted concentrations also fairly well represents the whole city (albeit a certain smoothing effect of the interpolation) and gives a consistent information for all cities, including those without station measurements. Thus, when thinking about a potential update of the city ranking, **the approach based on the population-weighted concentration can be further considered as a basis for an updated city ranking, preferably in a combination with the current approach** based on the averaged measurement data from the background stations in cities with at least one background measurement station.

4.1.3 NO₂

For the NO₂ annual average 2019, the comparison has been performed for 495 cities with at least one urban or suburban background station and for 444 cities with at least one urban or suburban traffic station (and additionally also for 642 cities with at least one urban or suburban station without regard of its type). Altogether, 719 urban/suburban background stations and 789 urban/suburban traffic stations have been used in this analysis.

Table 4.5 shows the comparison between the city means of the predicted gridded mapped values and the relevant averages of the measurements in locations within individual cities, separately for urban background and urban traffic locations (and map layers).

Table 4.5: Comparison of predicted grid values from separate urban background (top) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers against relevant measurements from urban/suburban background or traffic stations in average per city of the Urban Audit, using RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from scatter plots and FAC30% for NO₂ annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE, R² and FAC30%.

NO ₂ Annual Average	Urban background areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC30%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban background	2.55	13.4%	-0.06	0.849	y = 0.789x + 3.95	0.045
NO ₂ Annual Average	Urban traffic areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC30%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban traffic	3.89	12.7%	-0.12	0.845	y = 0.711x + 8.74	0.061

Figure 4.7 shows the scatterplots for these comparisons.

Figure 4.7: Correlation between predicted grid values from background (left) and urban traffic (right) map layer (y-axis) versus measurements from urban/suburban background (left) and urban/suburban traffic stations (right) (x-axis) in average per city of the Urban Audit for NO₂ annual average 2019

The comparison shows a fair agreement, see the relative uncertainty (in terms of RRMSE) of 13 % in both urban background and urban traffic areas and R² from the scatter plots at the level of about 85 % for both the urban background areas and the urban traffic areas. A slight bias of -0.1 µg.m⁻³ is observed in both urban background and urban traffic areas. The fraction of the predicted gridded values outside ±30 % of the measured concentration levels is 0.045 (i.e., 22 of 494 cities) for the urban background areas and 0.061 (i.e., 27 of 444 cities) for the urban traffic areas. The higher fraction compared to both PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} is caused by a stricter 30 % requirement than 50 % for both PM fractions. Still, this is quite an acceptable result. Thus, the same conclusion as for PM can be stated, i.e., that the current mapping can be used at the city level across Europe.

In addition to the FAC30% indicator, a more detailed view on the differences between the predicted gridded and the measured concentrations is presented in Table 4.6, in both absolute and relative numbers. E.g., one can see that for cc. 95% of the cities, the differences are smaller than 5 µg.m⁻³ in the urban background areas and 7.5 µg.m⁻³ in the urban traffic areas.

Table 4.6: Ratio of absolute differences between predicted grid values from urban background (top) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers and relevant measurements from urban/suburban background or traffic stations in average per city of the Urban Audit for NO₂ annual mean 2019, which exceed certain absolute (left) and relative (right) difference levels

NO ₂ Annual Average	Urban background areas							
	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 4 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>25%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.344	0.209	0.087	0.057	0.428	0.247	0.119	0.071
NO ₂ Annual Average	Urban traffic areas							
	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 4 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	> 7.5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>25%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.414	0.297	0.189	0.052	0.426	0.264	0.142	0.090

Next to the comparison of the measurement and underlying gridded values, we have additionally calculated the population-weighted concentration for each individual city (i.e., suggested new approach for the city ranking) and compared it with the average of the concentration values measured

at the urban/suburban background stations located in the relevant city (i.e., the similar approach as the current city ranking) and with the average of the concentration values measured at all urban/suburban stations (both background and traffic) located in the relevant city. See Figure 4.8. As expected, the population-weighted concentrations show better agreement with the averages of the background stations compared to the averages of both background and traffic stations, due to better representativeness of the background stations.

Next to the scatterplot, the bias has been calculated, being $0.3 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for the comparison based on the urban/suburban background stations and $-4.8 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for the comparison based on all urban/suburban (i.e., both background and traffic) stations. As expected, the population-weighted averages give in general somewhat higher results compared to the averages of the background stations and deeply lower results compared to the averages of both background and traffic stations, as expected. This result is influenced by large number of traffic stations (see Section 3.1), as well as by a high traffic vs. background ratio of NO_2 values.

Figure 4.8: Correlation between the population-weighted concentration (y-axis) versus average of measurements from urban/suburban background (left) and all (right) stations (x-axis) located in relevant city of the Urban Audit for NO_2 annual average 2019

Quite a low correlation (i.e., R^2 of 0.75 in urban background areas and of 0.50 in urban traffic areas) is caused by a high level of spatial variability of NO_2 inside cities, namely in traffic areas. Again, we have compared the population-weighted concentrations with the average of the gridded mapped values in the locations of the stations within the relevant cities (in two variants), in order to examine which part of the variability shown in the scatterplots of Figure 4.8 is attributable to the interpolation and resolution smoothing effect and which part to the spatial variability within the city. See Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.9: Correlation between the population-weighted concentration (y-axis) versus average of predicted gridded values at locations of urban/suburban background (left) and all (right) stations (x-axis) located in relevant city of the Urban Audit for NO₂ annual average 2019

The relevant bias is 0.4 µg.m⁻³ and -4.8 µg.m⁻³ for the comparison based on the predicted gridded values at locations of urban/suburban background stations and all urban/suburban stations, respectively. Looking at Figures 4.7, 4.8 and 4.9, one can state that the smoothing effect of the interpolation and the variability within the city play a similar role in the variability between the population-weighted concentrations and the average of the urban/suburban background measurements. Thus, the variability within the city plays higher role compared to PM.

We can suppose that the population-weighted concentration and the average of measurements from quite randomly located stations provide a fairly good information for the whole city in a similar quality in general. Thus, in a potential update of the city ranking (if applied for NO₂), **the approach based on the population-weighted concentration can be further considered as a basis for an updated city ranking, preferably in a combination with the current approach** based on the averaged measurement data from the background stations in cities with at least one background measurement station.

4.1.4 Ozone

For the ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means in 2019, the comparison has been performed for 459 cities with at least one urban or suburban background station. Altogether, 599 urban/suburban background stations have been used in this analysis.

Table 4.7 shows the comparison between the city means of the predicted gridded mapped values and the relevant averages of the measurements in locations within individual cities, for urban background locations (and map layer).

Table 4.7: Comparison of predicted grid values from urban background map layer against relevant measurements from urban and suburban background stations in average per city of the Urban Audit, using RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from scatter plot and FAC50% for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means in 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE, R² and FAC50%.

Ozone, 93.2 Percentile of 8-hourly Daily Maximums	Urban background areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban background	6.09	5.5%	0.31	0.839	$y = 0.813x + 20.69$	0.002

Figure 4.10 shows the scatterplot for this comparison.

Figure 4.10: Correlation between predicted grid values from background map versus measurements from urban and suburban background stations (x-axis) in average per city of the Urban Audit for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means in 2019

The comparison shows a fair agreement, see the relative uncertainty (in terms of RRMSE) of 6% and R² from the scatter plots at the level of about 84 %. A slight bias of 0.3 µg.m⁻³ is observed. The fraction of deviations between the predicted gridded and the measured concentration levels bigger than 50 % is 0.002 (i.e., 1 of 459 cities), which is an acceptable result. Thus, the same conclusion as for PM and NO₂ can be stated, i.e., that the current mapping can be used at the city level across Europe.

In addition to the FAC50 % indicator, a more detailed view on the differences between the predicted gridded and the measured concentrations is presented in Table 4.8, in both absolute and relative numbers. E.g., one can see that for 92 % of the cities, the differences are smaller than 10 µg.m⁻³.

Table 4.8: Ratio of absolute differences between predicted grid values from urban background map layer and relevant measurements from urban/suburban background stations in average per city of the Urban Audit for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means in 2019, which exceed certain absolute (left) and relative (right) difference levels.

Ozone, 93.2 Percentile of 8-hourly Daily Maximums	Urban background areas							
	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	> 7.5 µg.m ⁻³	> 10 µg.m ⁻³	> 15 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>25%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.302	0.169	0.083	0.032	0.063	0.034	0.020	0.011

Next to the comparison of the measurement and underlying gridded values, we have additionally calculated the population-weighted concentration for each individual city (i.e., potential new approach for the city ranking, if applied for ozone) and compared it with the average of the concentration values measured at all urban/suburban background stations located in the relevant city (i.e., similar approach to the current city ranking for PM_{2.5}). See Figure 4.11.

Figure 4.11: Correlation between the population-weighted concentration (y-axis) versus average of measurements from urban and suburban background stations (x-axis) located in relevant city of the Urban Audit for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means in 2019

Next to the scatterplot, the bias has been calculated, being $0.5 \mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$ for the comparison based on the urban/suburban background stations. Again, we have also compared the population-weighted concentrations with the average of the gridded mapped values in the locations of the background stations within the relevant cities, in order to examine which part of the variability shown in the scatterplots of Figure 4.11 is attributable to the smoothing effect of the interpolation and the resolution and which part is attributable to the spatial variability within the city. See Figure 4.12.

Figure 4.12: Correlation between the population-weighted concentration (y-axis) versus average of predicted gridded values at locations of urban/suburban background stations (x-axis) located in relevant city of the Urban Audit for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means in 2019

The relevant bias is $0.2 \mu\text{g.m}^{-3}$ for the comparison based on the predicted gridded values at locations of urban/suburban background stations. Looking at Figures 4.10, 4.11 and 4.12, one can state that the most of the variability between the population-weighted concentrations and the average of the urban/suburban background measurements is caused by the smoothing effect of the interpolation, while the variability within the city plays a minor role, similarly as in the case of PM.

4.2 NUTS3 units

For the NUTS3 units, we have compared the average of all measurements within the limits of the relevant NUTS3 unit (see Section 3.4) with the average of the relevant gridded mapped values in the locations of these measurements. For PM and NO₂, the analysis has been done separately for the rural background, urban/suburban background and urban/suburban traffic stations: the comparison of the station values has been done against the rural background (in the first case), the urban background (in the second case) and the urban traffic (in the third case) map layers. For ozone, only first two cases have been applied, as only background stations are used in the ozone mapping.

4.2.1 PM₁₀

For PM₁₀ annual average 2019, the comparison has been performed for 292 NUTS3 units with at least one rural background station, for 636 NUTS3 units with at least one urban or suburban background station and for 462 NUTS3 units with at least one urban or suburban traffic station. (Altogether, 363 rural background stations, 1299 urban/suburban background stations and 745 urban/suburban traffic stations have been used in this analysis.)

Table 4.9 shows the comparison between the NUTS3 means of the predicted gridded mapped values and the relevant averages of the measurements in locations within individual NUTS3 units, separately for rural background, urban background and urban traffic locations (and map layers).

Table 4.9: Comparison of predicted grid values from separate rural background (top), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers against relevant measurements from rural background, urban/suburban background and rural/suburban traffic stations in average per NUTS3 unit, using RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from scatter plots for PM₁₀ annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE and R².

PM ₁₀ Annual Average	Rural background areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - rural background	1.83	13.0%	-0.09	0.859	y = 0.844x + 2.10	0.007
PM ₁₀ Annual Average	Urban background areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban background	1.94	10.1%	-0.06	0.894	y = 0.880x + 2.26	0.002
PM ₁₀ Annual Average	Urban traffic areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban traffic	1.97	9.2%	-0.06	0.905	y = 0.863x + 2.89	0.000

Figure 4.13 shows the scatterplots for these comparisons.

Figure 4.13: Correlation between predicted grid values from rural background (left), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (right) map layer (y-axis) versus measurements from rural background (left), urban/suburban background (middle) and urban/suburban traffic stations (right) (x-axis) in average per NUTS3 for PM₁₀ annual average 2019

In addition to the FAC50 % indicator, a more detailed view on the differences between the predicted gridded and the measured concentrations is presented in Table 4.10, in both absolute and relative numbers. E.g., one can see that for 97-98 % of the NUTS3 units, the differences are smaller than 5 µg.m⁻³.

Table 4.10: Ratio of absolute differences between predicted grid values from rural (top), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers and relevant measurements from rural background, urban/suburban background or urban/suburban traffic stations in average per NUTS3 unit for PM₁₀ annual mean 2019, which exceed certain absolute (left) and relative (right) difference levels

PM ₁₀ Annual Average	Rural background areas							
	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	> 7.5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>30%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.185	0.068	0.024	0.010	0.346	0.182	0.120	0.041
PM ₁₀ Annual Average	Urban background areas							
	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	> 7.5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>30%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.208	0.099	0.028	0.005	0.226	0.097	0.039	0.008
PM ₁₀ Annual Average	Urban traffic areas							
	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	> 7.5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>30%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.249	0.117	0.024	0.002	0.227	0.100	0.048	0.017

In general, quite similar results as for the cities of the Urban Audit have been observed.

4.2.2 PM_{2.5}

For PM_{2.5} annual average 2019, the comparison has been performed for 185 NUTS3 units with at least one rural background station, for 473 NUTS3 units with at least one urban or suburban background station and for 257 NUTS3 units with at least one urban or suburban traffic station. (Altogether, 213 rural background stations, 720 urban/suburban background stations and 364 urban/suburban traffic stations have been used in this analysis.)

Table 4.11 shows the comparison between the NUTS3 means of the predicted gridded mapped values and the relevant averages of the measurements in locations within individual NUTS3 units, separately for rural background, urban background and urban traffic locations (and map layers).

Table 4.11: Comparison of predicted grid values from separate rural background (top), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers against relevant measurements from rural background, urban/suburban background and rural/suburban traffic stations in average per NUTS3 unit, using RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from scatter plots for PM_{2.5} annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE and R².

PM _{2.5} Annual Average	Rural background areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - rural background	1.30	14.4%	-0.23	0.890	y = 0.863x + 1.01	0.011
PM _{2.5} Annual Average	Urban background areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban background	1.33	10.8%	0.05	0.915	y = 0.886x + 1.46	0.002
PM _{2.5} Annual Average	Urban traffic areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban traffic	1.44	11.6%	0.04	0.887	y = 0.854x + 1.84	0.000

Figure 4.14 presents the scatterplots for these comparisons.

Figure 4.14: Correlation between predicted grid values from rural background (left), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (right) map layer (y-axis) versus measurements from rural background (left), urban/suburban background (middle) and urban/suburban traffic stations (right) (x-axis) in average per NUTS3 for PM_{2.5} annual average 2019

In addition to the FAC50 % indicator, a more detailed view on the differences between the predicted gridded and the measured concentrations is presented in Table 4.12, in both absolute and relative numbers. E.g., one can see that for ca. 95 % of the NUTS3 units, the differences are smaller than 3 µg.m⁻³.

Table 4.12: Ratio of absolute differences between predicted grid values from rural (top), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers and relevant measurements from rural background, urban/suburban background or urban/suburban traffic stations in average per NUTS3 unit for PM_{2.5} annual mean 2019, which exceed certain absolute (left) and relative (right) difference levels

PM _{2.5} Annual Average	Rural background areas							
	> 1 µg.m ⁻³	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>30%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.357	0.081	0.038	0.011	0.405	0.254	0.130	0.049
PM _{2.5} Annual Average	Urban background areas							
	> 1 µg.m ⁻³	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>30%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.345	0.106	0.044	0.008	0.266	0.135	0.044	0.006
PM _{2.5} Annual Average	Urban traffic areas							
	> 1 µg.m ⁻³	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>30%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.370	0.117	0.062	0.012	0.307	0.152	0.082	0.031

As in the case of PM₁₀, quite similar results as for the cities of the Urban Audit have been observed.

4.2.3 NO₂

For the NO₂ annual average 2019, the comparison has been performed for 367 NUTS3 units with at least one rural background station, for 679 NUTS3 units with at least one urban or suburban background station and for 544 NUTS3 units with at least one urban or suburban traffic station. (Altogether, 456 rural background stations, 1330 urban/suburban background stations and 1075 urban/suburban traffic stations have been used in this analysis.)

Table 4.13 shows the comparison between the NUTS3 means of the predicted gridded mapped values and the relevant averages of the measurements in locations within individual NUTS3 units, separately for rural background, urban background and urban traffic locations (and map layers).

Table 4.13: Comparison of predicted grid values from separate rural background (top), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers against relevant measurements from rural background, urban/suburban background and rural/suburban traffic stations in average per NUTS3 unit, using RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from scatter plots for NO₂ annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE and R².

NO ₂ Annual Average	Rural background areas						
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC30%	
Mean predicted vs. observed values - rural background	1.16	15.9%	-0.30	0.948	y = 0.904x + 0.39	0.093	
NO ₂ Annual Average	Urban background areas						
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC30%	
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban background	2.81	15.5%	0.06	0.814	y = 0.775x + 4.16	0.065	
NO ₂ Annual Average	Urban traffic areas						
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	Regr. eq.	
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban traffic	3.92	13.3%	0.14	0.850	y = 0.703x + 8.90	0.077	

Figure 4.15 gives the scatterplots for these comparisons.

Figure 4.15: Correlation between predicted grid values from rural background (left), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (right) map layer (y-axis) versus measurements from rural background (left), urban/suburban background (middle) and urban/suburban traffic stations (right) (x-axis) in average per NUTS3 for NO₂ annual average 2019

In addition to the FAC30% indicator, a more detailed view on the differences between the predicted gridded and the measured concentrations is presented in Table 4.14, in both absolute and relative numbers. E.g., one can see that for ca. 95 % of the NUTS3 units, the differences are smaller than 3 µg.m⁻³ in the rural areas, 5 µg.m⁻³ in the urban background areas and 7.5 µg.m⁻³ in the urban traffic areas.

Table 4.14: Ratio of absolute differences between predicted grid values from rural (top), urban background (middle) and urban traffic (bottom) map layers and relevant measurements from rural background, urban/suburban background or urban/suburban traffic stations in average per NUTS3 unit for NO₂ annual mean 2019, which exceed certain absolute (left) and relative (right) difference levels

NO ₂ Annual Average	Rural background areas							
	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 4 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>25%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.079	0.038	0.019	0.005	0.305	0.234	0.163	0.120
NO ₂ Annual Average	Urban background areas							
	> 2 µg.m ⁻³	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 4 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>25%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.330	0.186	0.109	0.063	0.393	0.233	0.149	0.094
NO ₂ Annual Average	Urban traffic areas							
	> 3 µg.m ⁻³	> 4 µg.m ⁻³	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	> 7.5 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>25%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.384	0.279	0.169	0.046	0.421	0.257	0.153	0.110

Again, similar results as for the cities of the Urban Audit have been observed in general.

4.2.4 Ozone

For the ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means in 2019, the comparison has been performed for 405 NUTS units with at least one rural background station and for 628 NUTS3 units with at least one urban or suburban background station. (Altogether, 528 rural background stations and 1156 urban/suburban background stations have been used in this analysis.)

Table 4.15 shows the comparison between the NUTS3 means of the predicted gridded mapped values and the relevant averages of the measurements in locations within individual NUTS3 units, separately for rural background and urban background locations (and map layer).

Table 4.15: Comparison of predicted grid values from separate rural background (top) and urban background (bottom) map layers against relevant measurements from rural background and urban/suburban background in average per NUTS3 unit, using RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from scatter plots for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means in 2019. Units: $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ except for RRMSE and R².

Ozone, 93.2 Percentile of 8-hourly Daily Maximums	Rural background areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - rural background	4.34	3.7%	0.08	0.891	$y = 0.835x + 19.51$	0.000
Ozone, 93.2 Percentile of 8-hourly Daily Maximums	Urban background areas					
	RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.	FAC50%
Mean predicted vs. observed values - urban background	4.97	4.4%	-0.18	0.863	$y = 0.839x + 17.84$	0.000

Figure 4.16 gives the scatterplots for these comparisons.

Figure 4.16: Correlation between predicted grid values from rural background (left) and urban background (right) map layer (y-axis) versus measurements from rural background (left) and urban/suburban background (right) (x-axis) in average per NUTS3 for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means in 2019

In addition to the FAC50% indicator, a more detailed view on the differences between the predicted gridded and the measured concentrations is presented in Table 4.16, in both absolute and relative numbers. E.g., one can see that for 95 % of the NUTS3 units, the differences are smaller than $10 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$.

Table 4.16: Ratio of absolute differences between predicted grid values from rural (top) and urban background (bottom) map layer and relevant measurements from rural background or urban/suburban background stations in average per NUTS3 unit for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means in 2019, which exceed certain absolute (left) and relative (right) difference levels.

Ozone, 93.2 Percentile of 8-hourly Daily Maximums	Rural background areas							
	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	> 7.5 µg.m ⁻³	> 10 µg.m ⁻³	> 15 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>25%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.188	0.074	0.027	0.015	0.020	0.012	0.005	0.000
Ozone, 93.2 Percentile of 8-hourly Daily Maximums	Urban background areas							
	> 5 µg.m ⁻³	> 7.5 µg.m ⁻³	> 10 µg.m ⁻³	> 15 µg.m ⁻³	>10%	>15%	>20%	>25%
Ratio of absolute differences	0.209	0.110	0.053	0.019	0.045	0.022	0.010	0.005

For ozone, as for other pollutants, the results for the NUTS3 units are quite similar as for the cities of the Urban Audit.

5 Alternative dealing with rural, urban background and urban traffic stations

During the preparation of the paper Horálek et al. (2020), it was suggested to check the separate treatment of rural, urban background and urban traffic stations. This chapter compares mapping results created based on the current merging methodology (using separate map layers) against the mapping results created based on alternative approaches of the map layers. Section 5.1 examines alternative dealing of (i) rural and (ii) urban/suburban background stations. Section 5.2 searches different dealing of urban/suburban (i) background and (ii) traffic stations.

5.1 Rural and urban/suburban background stations

In this section, the current methodology labelled (C) using the merging of the rural and the urban background map layers is compared against the alternative methodology labelled (J), i.e., the joint rural-urban background map layer created based on all background stations (both rural and urban/suburban). The analysis has been performed for PM₁₀, NO₂ and ozone.

5.1.1 PM₁₀

Table 5.1 presents the cross-validation results of the PM₁₀ annual average mapping in the rural and urban background areas for two variants, i.e. the current (C) one and the alternate (J) one, in which the rural and the urban/suburban background stations are handled together. The green marking shows the better performance. For the green highlighting, the ad hoc criterion of more than ca. 5 % difference (in terms of RMSE, RRMSE, R² and slope) and 0.2 µg.m⁻³ (in terms of RMSE and bias) for result distinguishing has been applied, i.e., the similar criterion as in Horálek et al. (2020).

Table 5.1: Comparison of two spatial interpolation variants showing RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from cross-validation scatterplots in rural (top) and urban (bottom) background areas for PM₁₀ annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE and R².

PM ₁₀ Annual Average – Mapping variant		Rural background areas				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Current, merged separ. rural and urban backgr. map layers	3.7	25.2%	0.4	0.617	y = 0.766x + 3.9
(J)	Joint rural-urban background layer	3.7	25.1%	1.2	0.698	y = 0.920x + 2.4
PM ₁₀ Annual Average – Mapping variant		Urban background areas				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Current, merged separ. rural and urban backgr. map layers	6.6	29.3%	-0.4	0.633	y = 0.675x + 6.9
(J)	Joint rural-urban background layer	6.5	28.7%	-0.4	0.648	y = 0.671x + 7.0

Looking at the results, one can see that the current (C) mapping variant gives better results in terms of bias and worse results in terms of the R² and the regression equation in the rural areas, compared to the alternate (J) variant. In the urban background areas, both variants give almost the same results.

Due to the important issue of the bias in the rural areas (i.e., the overestimation of 1.2 µg.m⁻³, in average), it can be stated that the **alternate (J) variant does not improve the mapping methodology**. In the rural areas, the current mapping variant gives better results. However, the (J) variant using the joint rural-urban map layer (based on both rural and urban/suburban background stations) might be considered for applying in the urban background areas, specifically for the purposes of the city level mapping. Further testing (e.g. based on the data of another year) might take place.

5.1.2 NO₂

Table 5.2 shows the cross-validation results of the NO₂ annual average mapping in the rural and urban background areas for two variants, i.e. the current (C) one and the alternate (J) one, in which the rural and the urban/suburban background stations are handled together.

Table 5.2: Comparison of two spatial interpolation variants showing RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from cross-validation scatter plots in rural background (top) and urban background (bottom) areas for NO₂ annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except RRMSE and R².

NO ₂ Annual Average – Mapping variant		Rural background areas				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Current, merged separ. rural and urban backgr. map layers	2.6	33.9%	0.5	0.781	y = 0.885x + 1.4
(J)	Joint rural-urban background layer	3.4	45.8%	0.9	0.639	y = 0.824x + 2.2
NO ₃ Annual Average – Mapping variant		Urban background areas				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Current, merged separ. rural and urban backgr. map layers	5.1	27.5%	-0.4	0.618	y = 0.685x + 5.4
(J)	Joint rural-urban background layer	5.0	26.8%	-0.3	0.632	y = 0.683x + 5.6

One can see that the current (C) mapping variant gives better results compared to the alternate (J) variant in the rural areas. In the urban areas, both variants give almost the same results, with a tiny bit better results in the case of the alternate (J) variant.

The similar finding as in the case of PM₁₀ can be concluded. The alternate (J) variant does not improve the mapping methodology. In the rural areas, the current method gives better results. However, the (J) variant using the joint rural-urban map layer (based on both rural and urban/suburban background stations) might be considered for applying in the urban background areas, specifically for the purposes of the city level mapping. Further testing might take place.

5.1.3 Ozone

Table 5.3 presents the cross-validation results of the PM₁₀ annual average mapping in the rural and urban background areas for two variants, i.e. the current (C) one and the alternate (J) one, in which the rural and the urban/suburban background stations are handled together.

Table 5.3: Comparison of two spatial interpolation variants showing RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from cross-validation scatter plots in rural background (top) and urban background (bottom) areas for ozone indicator 93.2 percentile of maximum daily 8-hour means 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except RRMSE and R².

Ozone 93.2 Percentile of 8-hour Daily Maximums – Mapping variant		Rural background areas				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Current, merged separ. rural and urban backgr. map layers	8.2	7.0%	-0.6	0.600	y = 0.644x + 41.1
(J)	Joint rural-urban background layer	8.9	7.6%	-2.5	0.566	y = 0.617x + 42.5
Ozone 93.2 Percentile of 8-hour Daily Maximums – Mapping variant		Urban background areas				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Current, merged separ. rural and urban backgr. map layers	10.1	9.0%	0.5	0.581	y = 0.624x + 43.0
(J)	Joint rural-urban background layer	10.1	8.9%	1.1	0.566	y = 0.616x + 44.5

It can be seen that the current (C) mapping variant gives better results compared to the alternate (J) variant, especially in the rural areas, but in terms of bias also in the urban background areas. The use of a joint rural-urban map layer (based both on rural and urban background stations) instead of the current use of separate rural and urban background map layers with their subsequent merge does not improve the mapping methodology. The current mapping variant gives better results.

5.2 Urban/suburban background and traffic stations

In this section, two different comparisons have been performed. At first, a similar comparison like in Section 5.1 has been done. Here, the current methodology labelled (C) using the merge of the urban background and the urban traffic map layers is compared against the alternative methodology labelled (J), i.e., the joint urban background-traffic map layer created based on all urban/suburban stations (both background and traffic).

Next to this, additional potential improvement of the mapping methodology has been examined. It examines the alternative adjustment of the urban traffic layer in areas where its estimated concentration values are lower than the urban background map layer estimated concentration values. Currently, the urban traffic layer is quite simply adjusted based on the urban background layer (i.e., not to have values smaller than this layer, see Section 2.1). We have examined the improvement of the adjustment, using the joint urban background-traffic map layer (created based on both background and traffic urban/suburban stations), as described in Section 2.1.

The analysis has been performed for PM₁₀ and NO₂. No analysis for ozone has been performed, as the traffic stations are not used in the ozone mapping.

5.2.1 PM₁₀

Table 5.4 presents the cross-validation results of the PM₁₀ annual average mapping in the urban background and the urban traffic areas for two mapping variants, i.e. the current (C) one and the alternate (J) one, in which the urban/suburban background and the urban/suburban traffic stations are handled together. The green marking shows the better performance.

As the urban traffic areas are underestimated in the current 1x1 km² final merged maps while fairly represented in the urban traffic map layer (Horálek et al., 2022), the results for separate urban traffic map layer are also presented in addition.

Table 5.4: Comparison of two mapping variants showing RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from cross-validation scatterplots in urban background (top) and urban traffic (bottom) areas for PM₁₀ annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE and R².

PM ₁₀ Annual Average – Mapping variant		Urban background areas				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Current, merged separ. urban backgr. and urban traffic m. layers	6.4	28.1%	0.1	0.659	y = 0.689x + 7.1
(J)	Joint background-traffic urban layer	6.5	28.6%	0.9	0.653	y = 0.670x + 8.3
PM ₁₀ Annual Average – Mapping variant		Urban traffic areas				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Current, merged separ. urban backgr. and urban traffic m. layers	5.1	22.7%	-2.7	0.746	y = 0.761x + 2.7
	Current, separate urban traffic map layer	4.3	19.3%	-0.1	0.776	y = 0.776x + 4.9
(J)	Joint rural-urban background layer	4.5	20.1%	-1.8	0.766	y = 0.751x + 3.8

Looking at the results, one can see that the current (C) mapping variant gives better results in terms of bias in the urban background areas, compared to the alternate (J) variant. In the urban traffic areas, the (J) variant gives somewhat better results compared to the merged urban map in the current (C)

variant. However, be it noted that the results are related to the 1x1 km² resolution, in which the urban traffic areas (in both variants) are underestimated due to the spatial smoothing. The best results for the urban traffic areas are given by the urban traffic map layer, being an intermediate product of the current (C) variant. Note that the population exposure is currently calculated not based on the final merged 1x1 km² map, but based on separate map layers.

It can be summarized that the use of a joint urban background-traffic map layer (based both on urban/suburban background and urban/suburban traffic stations) instead of the current use of separate urban background and urban traffic map layers with their subsequent merge does not improve the mapping methodology. For future, if the urban traffic areas should be better represented in the final map, an increased resolution (e.g., 100x100 m² instead of the current 1x1 km²) is recommended.

Additionally, we have examined an alternative adjustment of the urban traffic layer in areas where it shows lower results compared to the urban background map layer. The current (C) and the alternative (A) adjustment have been compared using the simple comparison with the measurement data. Table 5.5 shows the simple comparison between the point observation values and the prediction gridded values of the adjusted traffic map layer in two variants.

Table 5.5: Statistical indicators RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from the scatter plots for the predicted grid values from urban traffic map layer in two variants versus the measurement point values for urban/suburban traffic stations for PM₁₀ annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE and R².

PM ₁₀ Annual Average – Mapping variant		Urban/suburban traffic stations				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Urban traffic map layer, current adjustment	2.9	13.2%	0.0	0.881	y = 0.869x + 2.9
(A)	Urban traffic map layer, alternative adjustment	2.7	12.1%	-0.1	0.901	y = 0.869x + 2.8

The results show that the alternative adjustment (A) of the traffic map layer gives slightly better results compared to the current (C) adjustment in terms of RMSE. A potential inclusion of this improvement in the mapping methodology should be carefully evaluated in relation to increased computationally demandingness of the improved mapping procedure.

5.2.2 NO₂

Table 5.6 shows the cross-validation results of the NO₂ annual average mapping in the urban background and the urban traffic areas for two variants, i.e. the current (C) one and the alternate (J) one, in which the rural and the urban/suburban background stations are handled together.

Table 5.6: Comparison of two mapping variants showing RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from cross-validation scatterplots in urban background (top) and urban traffic (bottom) areas for NO₂ annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE and R².

NO ₂ Annual Average – Mapping variant		Urban background areas				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Current, merged separ. urban backgr. and urban traffic m. layers	5.0	26.7%	1.0	0.647	y = 0.688x + 6.8
(J)	Joint background-traffic urban layer	7.0	37.6%	4.1	0.632	y = 0.665x + 6.2
NO ₂ Annual Average – Mapping variant		Urban traffic areas				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Current, merged separ. urban backgr. and urban traffic m. layers	7.7	24.6%	-1.3	0.519	y = 0.501x + 14.4
	Current, separate urban traffic map layer	7.6	24.2%	0.0	0.520	y = 0.530x + 14.7
(J)	Joint rural-urban background layer	9.5	30.4%	-5.2	0.473	y = 0.506x + 10.3

Looking at the results, one can see that the current (C) mapping variant gives better results in terms of bias both in the urban background and urban traffic areas, compared to the alternate (J) variant. In both mapping variants, the urban traffic areas are underestimated in the final 1x1 km² map. It can be stated that the (J) mapping variant does not improve the mapping methodology. For future, if the urban traffic areas should be better represented in the final map, an increased resolution (e.g., 100x100 m² instead of the current 1x1 km²) is recommended.

Additionally, we have examined an alternative adjustment of the urban traffic layer in areas where it shows lower results compared to the urban background map layer. The current (C) and the alternative (A) adjustment have been compared using the simple comparison with the measurement data. Table 5.7 shows the simple comparison between the point observation values and the prediction gridded values of the adjusted traffic map layer in two variants.

Table 5.7: Statistical indicators RMSE, RRMSE, bias, R² and regression equation from the scatter plots for the predicted grid values from urban traffic map layer in two variants versus the measurement point values for urban/suburban traffic stations for NO₂ annual mean 2019. Units: µg.m⁻³ except for RRMSE and R².

NO ₂ Annual Average – Mapping variant		Urban/suburban traffic stations				
		RMSE	RRMSE	Bias	R ²	Regr. eq.
(C)	Urban traffic map layer, current adjustment	5.3	17.0%	0.0	0.775	y = 0.674x + 10.2
(A)	Urban traffic map layer, alternative adjustment	5.3	17.0%	0.0	0.776	y = 0.675x + 10.2

One can see that the results of both current (C) and alternative adjustment of the urban traffic map layer are almost the same. The reason probably is that the areas where the urban traffic map layer shows lower concentration values compared to the urban background map layer are very limited in the case of NO₂. In any case, it can be stated that the alternative adjustment of the urban traffic map layer does not improve the mapping methodology in the case of NO₂.

6 Potential approaches for carrying out city-level mapping at the European scale

Under Section 5.2, an increased map resolution (e.g., 100x100 m² instead of the current 1x1 km²) is recommended, if the urban traffic areas should be better represented in the final map. This Chapter 6 provides several possibilities of future development towards European-wide city level mapping at a fine spatial resolution. All these approaches might be developed within the scope of the current RIMM mapping methodology.

6.1 Use of uEMEP model data

One of the overarching design principles of the RIMM methodology is that it is primarily based on observations. However, the method also makes use of model data from the EMEP model as a predictor variable in the regression. This model data is provided at a relatively coarse resolution, thus limiting the potential of the technique for high-resolution urban-scale mapping. One of the most promising approaches for city-level mapping at the European scale is therefore the use of high-resolution model output. The uEMEP (urban EMEP) model, recently developed at MET Norway (Denby et al., 2020), is currently being used to provide operational high-resolution (spatial resolution ranging from 250 m to 50 m for urban areas) hourly air quality forecasts for the area of Norway. In addition, the model can be used to calculate annual average concentrations of the main pollutants for all of Europe at a spatial resolution of ca. 250 m. See Figures 6.1 and 6.2 respectively for a map at the European scale as well an example of city-scale model output from uEMEP.

Given the recent availability of this spatially very detailed and comprehensive model information, it is recommended to explore the potential of using this data for extending the RIMM technique (Horálek et al., 2022) to the scale of individual cities and, if the initial results are promising, to eventually carry out such an analysis for all major cities in Europe. The adaptation of the RIMM technique to the urban scale could potentially begin with the use of a similar residual kriging framework as currently in use for the regional scale, however it seems likely that at least for pollutants with substantial spatial gradients such as nitrogen dioxide, the method will have to be modified to include also information on the spatial representativity of each observation site. This can for example be directly accomplished with a method like Optimal Interpolation (OI), which is conceptually identical to residual kriging but which has the advantage that the background/model error covariance can be directly designed independently for each observation site. Using such an approach would for example limit the effect of traffic sites to the nearby road network, whereas urban background sites similarly would only correct urban background areas.

For completeness, it should be noted that the uEMEP model is under continuous development. It is not clear yet to what extent annual average concentration maps will be produced on a routine basis. It should further be mentioned that at this point the uEMEP model results for nitrogen dioxide are of significantly higher accuracy than those for particulate matter.

Figure 6.1: Annual average NO₂ concentration for the year 2018 from the uEMEP model

Figure 6.2: Same as Figure 1 but zoomed in to only show the output for the greater Paris area as an example of the spatial detail available in uEMEP for a large metropolitan area

6.2 Geostatistical downscaling

Another potential approach for city-level mapping would be to use the existing output from the operational RIMM mapping and to apply statistical downscaling techniques. Such techniques increase the spatial resolution of an existing dataset by exploiting the additional information from a complementary proxy dataset that is in some way correlated with the coarse resolution dataset. One such method has been recently developed at NILU within the SAMIRA project funded by the European Space Agency (Stebel et al., 2021). The method uses a combination of (multi)linear regression and geostatistical area-to-point kriging to exploit the spatial patterns of the fine-resolution proxy dataset and provides a robust way of adding spatial detail to the coarse-resolution input dataset while keeping the overall levels the same as in the coarse-resolution input dataset (i.e. the method is mass conservative, which can be demonstrated by re-aggregating the downscaled output). Figure 6.3 provides an overview of the general concept and Figure 6.4 shows an example of downscaling a satellite-derived surface NO₂ dataset over the city of Oslo, Norway. While this example shows only a relatively modest increase in spatial resolution to 1000 m, the method is capable of scaling coarse-resolution input such as the current RIMM-based maps to very high spatial resolutions of 50 m or better depending on the spatial resolution of the available proxy dataset.

Figure 6.3: Concept of the geostatistical downscaling methodology developed within the SAMIRA project (Stebel et al., 2021).

Figure 6.4: Example demonstrating the effect of geostatistically downscaling a coarse-resolution input dataset. The left panel shows a surface NO₂ map over Oslo, Norway, derived from the Sentinel-5P satellite instrument and the right panel shows the outcome of applying the geostatistical downscaling algorithm.

In addition, Figure 6.5 shows an example of geostatistical downscaling of coarse-resolution satellite-based NO₂ to scales relevant for calculating human exposure (demonstrated for the city of Milan, Italy).

Figure 6.5: Geostatistical downscaling of satellite-based NO₂ data over a city centre, here for downtown Milan, Italy.

6.3 Low-cost sensor networks for urban air quality mapping

Finally, networks of low-cost air quality sensors could play a substantial role in moving towards city-level air quality mapping. While air quality models such as uEMEP are starting to provide information at the scale of individual streets, observational data sources which are the cornerstone of the RIMM methodology are spatially comparatively sparse when thinking of the perspective of individual cities. Typically, most medium-size and large cities in Europe have from a few to on the order of 10-20 monitoring stations. This is typically not enough observational information to provide data for all neighborhoods and certainly not for the majority of streets.

Networks of low-cost air quality sensors have the potential to fill in this gap as they can provide many dozens to many hundreds of data points within a city. One example of a very active low-cost sensor network in Europe is sensor.community (<https://sensor.community/en/>), which deploys currently about 14,000 particle sensors throughout all of Europe (see Figure 6.6). Exploiting this kind of information would be very valuable for potential city-level mapping within the ETC mapping task as long as proper QA/QC procedures (calibration and outlier removal) are applied to the sensor data. However, it should be noted that at this point such substantial low-cost sensor networks only exist for particulate matter. For gases such as nitrogen dioxide, typically electro-chemical sensors are used and they require significantly more expertise for proper calibration and operation. As a result, no Europe-wide low-cost sensor networks for gases are available, although various initiatives from individual projects exist in multiple cities (e.g. Oslo, Antwerp).

Figure 6.6: Spatial distribution of active sensors (N = 14,083) in the sensor.community particle sensor network in all of Europe (left panel) and in Berlin, Germany, as an example of a large city in Europe (right panel) (data as of December 2020).

6.4 Other potential approaches

The easiest simple way forward concerning the European-wide city level mapping probably is to construct maps for cities (e.g. for cities of the Urban audit) in 100x100 m² resolution, based on the current RIMM methodology. Currently, the maps are prepared in 1x1 km² only, although the merge of the urban background and the urban traffic map layers is performed based on buffers around the roads, which enables merge in a finer resolution. This might be done for pollutants, for which the urban map traffic layer is used in mapping, i.e., for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and NO₂. Such a map production in a more fine resolution would be in better agreement with the population exposure, which is currently calculated in fact in a finer than 1x1 km² resolution, using the buffers around the roads.

Another option might be to follow some recommendation of Horálek et al. (2018), e.g. to use land cover data in 100x100 m² resolution as a proxy or to couple kernel method with the RIMM mapping.

7 Conclusions and recommendations

The report examines city-level mapping at the European scale, with the aim to be able to provide consistent spatial information at NUTS3 and city levels across Europe in future. Among others, this would enable to introduce an improvement of the current city ranking.

The current mapping methodology has been evaluated with respect to city- and NUTS3-levels mapping. For the cities of the City Audit and for the NUTS3 units, a comparison between the measurements and the mapping data has been carried out. Based on the results of the city level analysis, it can be stated that the current mapping can be used at the city level across Europe, for all examined pollutants (i.e., PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and ozone), despite a slight positive bias in the urban background areas for PM and ozone and a mild smoothing effect at locations of the measurement stations. If the agreement of the predicted and observed values should be improved, a potential methodological adaption might be applied, i.e., a post-processing correction based on the kriging residuals, namely by interpolating them by some exact interpolator, which respects the measurement values. However, this would probably lead to the worsening of the cross-validation uncertainty for the whole interpolation.

Additionally, we have calculated the population-weighted concentration for individual cities as a potential new approach for the city ranking. We have compared this indicator with the average of the stations located in the relevant city in two variants (i.e., for all urban/suburban stations without regard on their type and for the urban/suburban background stations only, which is a similar approach to the current city ranking for PM_{2.5}). Based on the analysis, it seems that while the averaged measurement data from the background stations provides a superior information for the whole city in general (when the measurement error is neglected), the population-weighted concentration also fairly well represents the whole city (albeit a certain smoothing effect of the interpolation) and gives a consistent information for all cities, including those without station measurements. Thus, this indicator can be recommended for further evaluation for the city ranking index (preferably in a combination with the current approach based on the averaged measurement data from the background stations in cities with at least one background measurement station).

Apart from this, potential improvements of the mapping methodology have been examined. At first, the alternative mapping variant using the joint rural-urban background map layer created based on all background stations instead of the current variant using the merge of the rural and the urban background map layers has been compared with the current variant. It has been concluded that this alternative mapping variant does not improve the mapping methodology. However, in the cases of PM₁₀ and NO₂ (not ozone), this variant might be considered for applying in the urban background areas, specifically for the purposes of the city level mapping. Further testing might take place. Next to this, an alternative treatment of the background and traffic stations in the urban areas have been examined. The alternative mapping variant using the joint urban background-traffic map layer created based on all urban/suburban stations has been examined, however no improvement in the mapping has been found. In addition, an alternative adjustment of the urban traffic map layer has been examined. It has been found that it slightly improves PM₁₀ (not NO₂) mapping. A potential application of this slight improvement should be evaluated in relation to increased demandingness of the improved mapping procedure. In any case, urban traffic areas are underestimated in the final 1x1 km² maps. For future, if the urban traffic areas should be better represented in the final maps, an increased map resolution (e.g., 100x100 m² instead of the current 1x1 km²) is recommended.

Several possibilities of future development towards the European-wide city level mapping in a fine resolution have been suggested. This includes a) applying the existing methodology but exploiting a high-resolution model output (e.g. from the uEMEP model), b) downscaling of the existing spatial maps using a geostatistical downscaling technique in combination with fine-resolution proxy datasets, and c) the exploitation of existing low-cost sensor networks for providing additional information within a city in areas that is not adequately covered by traditional air quality stations.

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Annex 1

Numerical results for Cities of the Urban Audit

Table A.1 gives the numerical results for Cities for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, while Table A.2 for NO₂ and O₃.

Table A.1: Total population in thousands of inhabitants (POP), estimated population-weighted concentration in µg·m⁻³ (PWC), number of urban/suburban background (NB) and traffic (NT) stations, average of annual concentrations measured at these background and traffic stations (CSB, CST), averages of annual concentrations estimated at the underlying grid cells of urban background and urban traffic map layers (CMB, CMT) in cities of the Urban Audit for PM₁₀ annual average 2019 (left) and PM_{2.5} annual average 2019 (right)

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	PM ₁₀							PM _{2.5}						
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
AT001C1	Wien	1 741	18.8	11	17.4	18.3	2	19.6	21.1	13.1	11	12.3	12.7	2	13.4	14.5
AT002C1	Graz	275	23.8	5	19.1	24.5	2	23.8	25.4	16.2	2	14.0	17.2	1	18.4	17.5
AT003C1	Linz	208	19.1	1	17.7	17.1	1	21.0	19.9	13.7	1	12.5	12.2	1	15.0	13.4
AT004C1	Salzburg	158	19.4	2	14.5	20.2	1	18.4	20.6	13.7	1	9.3	14.3	1	10.3	13.5
AT005C1	Innsbruck	130	16.1	2	14.1	15.9				11.5	1	9.0	11.2			
AT006C1	Klagenfurt	100	21.5	1	15.7	22.4	1	20.0	23.7	14.9	1	8.5	15.0	1	11.5	16.1
BE001K1	Bruxelles / Brussel (gr. city)	1 192	18.8	3	16.8	18.3	1	16.0	19.4	11.4	3	11.1	11.2			
BE002C1	Antwerpen	544	22.4	3	23.0	22.4	2	26.2	24.0	12.9	3	12.6	12.8	2	14.0	13.6
BE003C1	Gent	277	21.7	1	25.5	22.0	1	21.9	21.9	12.9	2	13.6	13.0	1	12.6	12.9
BE004K1	Charleroi (greater city)	258	17.4	4	17.4	17.3				10.0	4	9.9	10.0			
BE005K1	Liege (greater city)	429	16.0	4	16.2	15.9				8.8	4	8.4	8.7			
BE006C1	Brugge	128	20.7							12.4	1	12.4	12.5			
BE007C1	Namur	116	16.5	1	18.0	16.7				9.3	1	9.4	9.3			
BE008C1	Leuven	114	18.4							11.0						
BE009K1	Mons (greater city)	167	18.3	1	20.1	18.7				10.9	1	10.5	11.1			
BE010C1	Kortrijk	89	20.2							12.6						
BE011C1	Oostende	80	20.8							11.8						
BE012C1	Mechelen	102	20.1							12.0						
BE013C1	Mouscron	41	19.8							12.4						
BE014K1	La Louvière (greater city)	110	17.6							10.3						
BE015K1	Verviers (greater city)	77	13.8							7.8						
BG001C1	Sofia	1 297	35.7	5	27.8	29.0	2	30.7	36.8	23.6	1	8.9				
BG002C1	Plovdiv	338	36.8	1	35.8	37.0	1	44.7	38.1	23.1	1	19.0	23.2			
BG003C1	Varna	345	25.9	2	27.4	26.1				17.4	1	18.5	17.7			
BG004C1	Burgas	213	25.4	2	22.9	25.7				16.2						
BG005C1	Pleven	132	30.2	1	36.3	31.1				21.1						
BG006C1	Ruse	168	28.0	1	36.0	28.8				18.2	1	20.1	18.7			
BG007C1	Vidin	68	36.4	1	41.3	38.8				25.0						
BG008C1	Stara Zagora	161	26.6				1	20.9	27.9	18.2	1	20.9	19.1			
BG009C1	Sliven	126	23.7	1	17.8	24.8				15.6						
BG010C1	Dobrich	91	24.3	1	26.3	24.3				16.7						
BG011C1	Shumen	94	27.0	1	29.5	28.4				18.3						
BG012C1	Pernik	97	28.3	2	31.1	28.1				18.8						
BG013C1	Yambol	75	25.4							15.8						
BG014C1	Haskovo	95	29.4	1	29.0	31.2				18.7						
BG015C1	Pazardzhik	116	30.0	1	33.7	32.5				19.8						
BG016C1	Blagoevgrad	78	26.2	1	30.0	29.0				17.2						
BG017C1	Veliko Tarnovo	89	26.9	1	31.3	28.4				18.8	1	22.9	19.8			
BG018C1	Vratsa	74	29.5	1	29.3	31.0				19.7						
CH001C1	Zurich	414	14.9	1	13.6	26.0	3	15.7	29.8	10.0	1	9.5	9.9			
CH002C1	Geneva	244	17.2	1	16.1	22.9				10.6						
CH003C1	Basel	190	14.7	1	15.2	22.5				9.9						

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	PM ₁₀							PM _{2.5}						
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
CH004C1	Bern	176	14.7	1	12.6	25.2	1	18.7	32.3	9.5				1	11.3	11.2
CH005C1	Lausanne	180	14.3	1	11.8	24.7	1	14.3	29.0	9.0						
CH006C1	Winterthur	116	13.3	1	12.5	20.3				9.0						
CH007C1	St. Gallen	83	12.7				1	13.0	28.0	8.6						
CH008C1	Lucerne	102	14.3				1	15.3	22.8	9.7						
CH009C2	Lugano	86	17.3	2	15.4	18.6				11.4	1	9.8	11.3			
CH010C1	Biel/Bienne	60	13.4							8.7						
CH011C1	Thun	53	13.4							8.9						
CH012C1	Zug	38	13.0							8.9						
CY001C1	Lefkosia	268	27.6				1	33.3	16.2	14.7	1	13.5	13.9			
CY002K1	Greater Larnaka	78	27.9							15.9						
CY501C1	Lemesos	191	29.2	1	26.0	14.9				15.3	1	13.3	14.9			
CZ001C1	Praha	1 291	19.9	8	19.0	16.3	5	24.6	18.0	13.9	3	12.9	13.9	1	17.3	15.6
CZ002C1	Brno	396	21.3	5	20.4	14.5	3	25.3	16.5	15.7	4	15.8	15.5	2	18.0	16.2
CZ003C1	Ostrava	310	27.7	3	25.1	14.5	1	30.9	13.6	20.9	2	18.5	20.6	1	22.5	22.9
CZ004C1	Plzeň	175	18.5	2	17.0	13.9	2	19.4	16.0	13.0	2	11.3	12.8	2	13.9	13.9
CZ005C1	Ústí nad Labem	96	20.8	2	19.5	13.5	1	23.7	37.4	14.7	1	11.4	14.8	1	16.2	14.9
CZ006C1	Olomouc	111	23.6	1	25.6	10.2				17.2	1	17.8	17.4			
CZ007C1	Liberec	108	19.8	1	16.8	17.1				14.1	1	12.5	14.2			
CZ008C1	České Budějovice	101	16.7	1	16.3	28.4				12.3	1	12.8	12.6			
CZ009C1	Hradec Králové	97	20.6	1	20.1	19.6	1	20.3	24.2	15.0	1	14.4	15.5	1	15.5	14.6
CZ010C1	Pardubice	96	20.4	1	20.4	20.8				14.9	1	14.8	15.0			
CZ011C1	Zlín	80	22.2	2	22.8	27.7				16.6	2	17.6	16.9			
CZ012C1	Kladno	75	18.8	2	21.2	18.4				12.9	1	12.0	13.0			
CZ013C1	Karlovy Vary	51	15.8	1	15.6	21.2				10.9						
CZ014C1	Jihlava	53	17.5	1	17.4	23.9				13.0	1	13.9	13.4			
CZ015C1	Havířov	80	26.8	1	27.8	19.9				19.9	1	20.3	20.2			
CZ016C1	Most	66	20.7	1	23.6	16.9				13.8	1	15.1	14.3			
CZ017C1	Karviná	61	29.7	1	28.7	21.3				21.8	1	20.9	22.1			
CZ018C2	Chomutov-Jirkov	70	18.7	1	19.3	20.5				12.7						
DE001C1	Berlin	3 374	18.5	6	17.4	22.4	5	22.2	24.5	12.4	3	13.1	12.6	1	15.7	13.4
DE002C1	Hamburg	1 779	18.1	5	18.3	18.9	3	20.7	30.9	11.4	3	10.5	11.3	2	12.6	12.4
DE003C1	München	1 399	15.1	2	14.4	15.9	2	21.5	20.0	10.1	2	9.8	10.2	2	11.6	11.6
DE004C1	Köln	1 027	16.7	1	16.2	17.8	2	20.2	22.2	10.7				1	12.7	12.7
DE005C1	Frankfurt am Main	720	18.0	3	17.7	27.3	1	21.6	20.9	11.4	2	10.1	11.1	1	12.8	12.5
DE006C1	Essen	584	16.6	1	20.0	21.2	2	19.6	21.8	11.0	2	10.9	11.1			
DE007C1	Stuttgart	618	16.8	1	15.3	30.1	3	23.8	20.8	10.6	1	10.0	10.5	2	12.2	12.8
DE008C1	Leipzig	524	16.1	1	14.1	19.5	2	21.2	20.0	10.5	1	9.4	10.3	1	11.7	11.5
DE009C1	Dresden	547	16.3	1	14.9	17.2	2	18.2	20.5	11.0	1	10.3	11.1	2	11.3	11.9
DE010C1	Dortmund	600	16.0				2	19.9	20.7	10.7	1	11.6	10.7			
DE011C1	Düsseldorf	617	16.8	1	14.4	18.0	1	22.8	20.3	11.0	1	10.5	11.2	1	14.8	13.1
DE012C1	Bremen	576	17.2	4	16.9	14.9	1	22.0	23.0	11.2	1	10.8	10.9			
DE013C1	Hannover	563	15.0	1	14.0	15.3	1	18.1	19.9	9.9	1	9.3	9.7	1	9.7	10.6
DE014C1	Nürnberg	502	16.5				1	21.6	18.9	11.0	1	11.5	11.2	1	11.1	11.9
DE015C1	Bochum	377	16.1							10.7						
DE017C1	Bielefeld	344	15.2				2	19.8	20.7	9.8						
DE018C1	Halle an der Saale	235	15.8	1	16.2	17.3	1	22.5	21.5	10.6	1	11.0	10.6	1	12.2	11.5
DE019C1	Magdeburg	231	16.0	1	15.4	17.2	2	20.0	20.7	10.6	1	10.9	10.6	1	10.3	11.3
DE020C1	Wiesbaden	285	16.5	1	14.6	16.2	2	16.0	18.5	10.8	1	9.5	10.9	2	10.3	11.2
DE021C1	Göttingen	122	14.7	1	12.0	15.9	1	19.3	19.8	9.4	1	8.0	9.3	1	11.1	11.2
DE022C1	Mülheim a.d.Ruhr	169	17.1	1	16.3	16.4				11.1						
DE023C1	Moers	112	16.7							11.1						
DE025C1	Darmstadt	163	15.9	1	14.1	16.8	1	16.1	19.6	10.2	1	8.5	10.0	1	9.5	11.1
DE026C1	Trier	119	14.2				1	16.4	20.2	8.5						
DE027C1	Freiburg im Breisgau	225	12.6	1	12.9	17.1	1	15.3	20.0	8.3	1	8.3	8.1	1	9.0	8.6
DE028C1	Regensburg	155	15.9				1	19.6	18.4	10.9						

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	PM ₁₀							PM _{2.5}						
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
DE029C1	Frankfurt (Oder)	64	18.3	1	16.9	14.7	1	19.1	19.0	12.7	1	11.6	12.9	1	12.3	12.9
DE030C1	Weimar	67	13.9	1	13.4	15.6	1	15.6	18.3	9.3	1	9.1	9.3	1	10.3	10.1
DE031C1	Schwerin	97	16.1				1	18.0	17.0	10.5				1	11.6	11.4
DE032C1	Erfurt	204	14.1	2	13.2	15.8	2	17.0	14.5	9.4	2	8.9	9.3	2	10.1	10.2
DE033C1	Augsburg	302	14.9	2	14.8	16.7	2	20.0	18.2	10.4	2	10.5	10.3			
DE034C1	Bonn	341	15.6	1	15.2	14.5				10.2						
DE035C1	Karlsruhe	315	16.2	1	14.7	17.2	1	16.3	19.7	10.7	1	9.9	11.0	1	11.1	12.7
DE036C1	Mönchengladbach	268	16.0	1	16.9	15.7	1	20.9	16.4	10.4	1	10.7	10.2			
DE037C1	Mainz	206	16.3	2	17.3	12.2	1	21.9	18.8	10.6	1	11.5	10.5	1	11.1	11.3
DE039C1	Kiel	265	17.1	1	15.8	18.5	1	21.7	16.9	10.9				1	12.2	11.8
DE040C1	Saarbrücken	197	15.3	2	14.6	13.8	1	18.9	19.4	10.1	1	10.2	10.2			
DE041C1	Potsdam	166	16.3	2	16.0	13.8	2	19.4	19.7	10.9	2	10.3	11.0	2	11.8	11.6
DE042C1	Koblenz	126	15.9				1	17.6	19.9	10.6				1	10.9	10.9
DE043C1	Rostock	208	16.7	1	16.3	14.7	2	21.0	18.9	10.9	1	10.6	10.7	2	12.4	11.9
DE044C1	Kaiserslautern	99	14.4	1	14.8	15.6				9.7	1	10.3	9.8			
DE045C1	Iserlohn	102	14.0							9.5						
DE046C1	Esslingen am Neckar	103	16.3				1	23.1	20.9	10.5						
DE047C1	Hanau	100	16.7	1	16.3	16.7				10.7						
DE048C1	Wilhelmshaven	80	17.0							10.6						
DE049C1	Ludwigsburg	97	16.5	1	14.9	16.3	1	22.8	18.9	10.5						
DE050C1	Tübingen	89	14.1	1	14.7	16.9	1	22.1	19.4	9.4	1	9.7	9.3			
DE051C1	Villingen-Schwenningen	86	11.8	1	12.1	15.4				7.8						
DE052C1	Flensburg	90	16.9				1	19.0	18.3	10.6				1	11.0	11.1
DE053C1	Marburg	77	15.5	1	15.7	16.3	1	15.6	20.1	10.5				1	10.2	10.8
DE054C1	Konstanz	79	13.6	1	14.0	16.5				9.4	1	9.6	9.4			
DE055C1	Neumünster	81	17.1							11.0						
DE056C1	Brandenburg an der Havel	75	15.6	1	15.7	14.3	1	19.7	22.7	10.5	1	10.8	10.6	1	11.4	11.3
DE057C1	Gießen	86	16.8				1	17.0	23.4	11.2				1	10.9	11.4
DE058C1	Lüneburg	82	15.1	1	14.6	16.6				9.9						
DE059C1	Bayreuth	75	15.2				1	16.6	20.1	10.5						
DE060C1	Celle	70	14.2							9.4						
DE061C1	Aschaffenburg	83	15.6							10.1	1	10.0	10.1			
DE062C1	Bamberg	79	15.1	1	15.0	15.9				10.3	1	10.3	10.3			
DE063C1	Plauen	67	14.4				1	14.4	19.9	10.0						
DE064C1	Neubrandenburg	66	16.0				2	17.7	17.1	10.6				1	12.3	11.4
DE065C1	Fulda	84	15.3	1	15.2	16.1	1	18.8	19.4	10.1				1	11.9	11.0
DE066C1	Kempten (Allgäu)	71	11.9							8.3	1	8.8	8.5			
DE067C1	Landshut	74	15.0				1	15.7	18.1	10.5						
DE068C1	Sindelfingen	70	14.9							9.6						
DE069C1	Rosenheim	64	13.9							10.0						
DE070C1	Frankenthal (Pfalz)	55	16.0							10.7						
DE071C1	Stralsund	58	16.3				1	17.9	16.7	10.3				1	11.5	11.4
DE072C1	Friedrichshafen	60	14.0	1	14.2	13.9				9.6						
DE073C1	Offenburg	64	14.4							9.5						
DE074C1	Görlitz	63	21.1				1	18.4	15.6	14.6						
DE075C1	Sankt Augustin	67	15.7							10.3						
DE076C1	Neu-Ulm	58	15.4	1	16.1	11.4				10.5	1	10.7	10.4			
DE077C1	Schweinfurt	64	16.1	1	17.2	15.6				10.6						
DE078C1	Greifswald	56	16.1							10.5						
DE079C1	Wetzlar	58	16.3	1	18.1	13.6				11.0						
DE080C1	Speyer	60	16.3							10.9	1	11.6	10.9			
DE081C1	Passau	50	16.2	1	18.1	15.7				11.4	1	12.4	11.6			
DE082C1	Dessau-Roßlau	88	15.7				1	16.4	18.2	10.5						
DE501C1	Duisburg	495	18.4	1	18.6	15.1	1	19.4	18.0	12.1						
DE502C1	Mannheim	303	16.7				1	20.2	17.1	10.9				1	12.3	12.1
DE503C1	Gelsenkirchen	281	17.2				2	23.1	18.7	11.5	1	13.9	11.5			

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
DE504C1	Münster	291	16.3	1	16.4	15.0	1	20.2	21.2	10.7						
DE505C1	Chemnitz	249	14.9	1	12.5	15.4	1	17.6	18.8	9.9				1	10.6	10.8
DE506C1	Braunschweig	250	14.7	1	12.7	14.1	1	17.2	22.2	9.6				1	9.7	10.6
DE507C1	Aachen	251	14.3	1	12.0	15.4	1	20.2	19.9	8.4						
DE508C1	Krefeld	229	16.4	1	14.3	16.1				10.9						
DE509C1	Oberhausen	211	17.4				1	21.9	21.3	11.5						
DE510C1	Lübeck	237	16.9	1	15.9	16.4	1	20.2	20.3	10.8	1	10.0	10.9			
DE511C1	Hagen	199	14.9				1	23.7	17.4	10.0						
DE513C1	Kassel	209	15.3	1	15.6	16.4	1	21.5	18.2	10.0	1	9.7	9.9			
DE514C1	Hamm	182	15.5							10.3						
DE515C1	Herne	158	17.0							11.2						
DE516C1	Solingen	177	15.3	1	13.7	18.7	1	19.0	18.4	10.0						
DE517C1	Osnabrück	176	15.8	1	14.7	16.2	1	20.2	21.1	10.2	1	9.3	10.2	1	11.4	11.6
DE518C1	Ludwigshafen am Rhein	163	16.6	1	17.7	14.6	1	20.8	20.2	11.0				1	11.9	12.1
DE519C1	Leverkusen	167	15.7	1	13.3	14.4				10.3				1	11.6	12.0
DE520C1	Oldenburg (Oldenburg)	169	17.0				1	18.4	20.0	10.8				1	11.3	11.3
DE521C1	Neuss	156	16.2	1	19.3	13.8				10.7						
DE522C1	Heidelberg	172	15.6	1	14.7	16.4				10.3						
DE523C1	Paderborn	145	14.8							9.6						
DE524C1	Würzburg	146	15.6	1	15.3	16.9	1	19.9	19.6	10.1	1	9.4	9.8			
DE525C1	Recklinghausen	127	16.7							11.1						
DE526C1	Wolfsburg	124	14.5	1	13.6	15.0	1	16.7	19.8	9.5						
DE527C1	Bremerhaven	117	17.1	1	16.8	15.1	1	19.6	20.2	11.0	1	11.1	11.0			
DE528C1	Bottrop	118	17.9							11.9						
DE529C1	Heilbronn	123	16.7	1	18.4	15.6	1	22.5	19.9	10.6	1	10.9	10.4	1	12.4	12.6
DE530C1	Remscheid	112	14.7							9.7						
DE531C1	Offenbach am Main	127	17.1				1	21.8	19.8	10.8						
DE532C1	Ulm	126	15.4	1	15.2	16.9				10.3	1	10.2	10.3			
DE533C1	Pforzheim	130	13.7	1	14.5	15.8				8.8	1	9.2	8.3			
DE534C1	Ingolstadt	133	15.5				1	16.5	19.1	10.8				1	10.7	11.6
DE535C1	Gera	100	14.7	1	15.4	16.5				10.0						
DE536C1	Salzgitter	105	13.9							9.3						
DE537C1	Reutlingen	121	14.0	1	13.9	15.5	1	20.9	17.9	9.2				1	11.2	10.3
DE538C1	Fürth	119	15.9				1	17.3	19.9	10.8						
DE539C1	Cottbus	101	17.3	1	16.3	15.1	1	17.8	21.8	11.6	1	11.1	11.6	1	12.8	12.1
DE540C1	Siegen	109	14.5							9.8						
DE541C1	Bergisch Gladbach	121	14.9							9.9						
DE542C1	Hildesheim	105	14.3				1	17.2	19.9	9.3				1	9.8	10.4
DE543C1	Witten	105	15.6							10.4						
DE544C1	Zwickau	106	14.9				1	16.6	18.3	10.1						
DE545C1	Erlangen	112	15.8							10.7						
DE546C1	Wuppertal	355	15.4	1	16.0	14.5	1	19.3	18.7	10.0	1	9.6	9.8			
DE547C1	Jena	107	14.3	1	14.1	17.0				9.6						
DE548C1	Düren, Stadt	99	14.1							8.6						
DE549C1	Bocholt, Stadt	73	16.9							11.1						
DK001C1	København	668	16.3	1	16.5	16.4	2	23.4	18.5	9.8	1	10.9	9.8	2	12.5	11.2
DK002C1	Århus	312	16.6				1	19.4	18.4	9.5	1	9.4	9.5	1	11.7	11.1
DK003C1	Odense	193	17.0				1	20.3	17.9	10.3						
DK004C2	Aalborg	200	16.5							8.9	1	9.6	9.7			
EE001C1	Tallinn	405	12.2	1	9.9	15.2	1	17.5	16.5	6.3	1	4.6	5.5			
EE002C2	Tartu linn	105	14.6	1	15.1	12.8				6.5	1	5.4	6.3			
EE003C1	Narva linn	59	12.7	1	10.0	14.7				6.1	1	4.8	6.0			
EL001K1	Athens	3 313	29.3	4	25.3	12.8	3	33.4	19.8	18.0	3	13.8	15.6	2	18.4	18.0
EL002K1	Thessaloniki	789	29.3				1	41.9	20.3	20.4				1	20.5	21.5
EL003C1	Patra	172	22.8				1	29.2	20.2	14.5				1	15.6	15.1
EL004C1	Iraklio	156	35.2							17.0						

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
EL005C1	Larissa	142	22.4				1	32.3	20.3	15.1						
EL006C1	Volos	102	22.9				1	28.7	16.9	15.3				1	15.8	16.1
EL007C1	Ioannina	76	27.1							17.5						
EL008C1	Kavala	56	26.5							17.6						
EL009C1	Kalamata	54	21.5							12.8						
EL010C1	Trikala	62	21.9							14.6						
EL011C1	Serres	60	24.4							16.6						
EL012C1	Katerini	61	20.6							14.0						
EL013C1	Xanthi	57	28.6							17.8						
EL014C1	Chania	66	31.1							15.9						
ES001C1	Madrid	3 230	17.8	7	15.9	17.3	6	19.4	34.4	8.7	2	9.4	8.4	5	10.1	10.5
ES002C1	Barcelona	1 637	24.7	6	25.8	14.9	3	28.8	41.5	15.3	4	16.6	14.8	3	19.4	17.3
ES003C1	Valencia	909	20.4	2	21.6	14.2	4	23.0	28.9	12.6	2	13.3	12.8	3	14.5	13.6
ES004C1	Sevilla	712	21.3							9.9						
ES005C1	Zaragoza	699	16.1	2	15.2	16.3	4	10.7	30.4	7.5	1	9.6	7.6			
ES006C1	Málaga	573	24.1				1	30.9	29.5	11.5						
ES007C1	Murcia	465	21.5				1	29.2	19.5	12.1						
ES008C1	Palmas de Gran Canaria, Las															
ES009C1	Valladolid	336	14.7				3	16.3	27.9	7.8				3	11.9	10.8
ES010C1	Palma de Mallorca	424	20.2				1	22.9	23.4	10.9						
ES011C1	Santiago de Compostela	116	17.8	1	17.9	10.8	1	18.4	15.8	8.9	1	7.8	9.1	1	11.6	10.5
ES012C1	Vitoria-Gasteiz	242	16.6				3	14.1	30.7	10.2				2	8.1	10.3
ES013C1	Oviedo	228	20.9	1	15.4	14.4	2	19.3	23.2	12.6	1	7.8	12.2	1	13.7	13.3
ES014C1	Pamplona/ Iruña	268	15.4	2	13.7	12.9	1	16.7	16.4	8.8						
ES015C1	Santander	183	19.0	1	20.2	28.8	1	24.8	22.2	11.1						
ES016C1	Toledo	90	20.4	1	21.2	17.6				10.3	1	11.9	10.6			
ES017C1	Badajoz	152	14.6	1	14.1	24.5				6.0						
ES018C1	Logroño	155	18.1	1	22.7	20.4				10.4						
ES019C1	Bilbao	358	18.2	1	12.9	16.2	2	17.9	19.0	11.8	1	9.1	11.1			
ES020C1	Córdoba	331	23.9							11.2						
ES021C1	Alicante/Alacant	342	18.1				1	22.1	16.7	10.5	1	12.9	10.8			
ES022C1	Vigo	303	18.7				2	22.5	21.7	9.3				1	10.5	10.6
ES023C1	Gijón	278	20.5	2	19.3	18.5	4	22.7	16.4	11.3	2	9.8	11.0	1	12.1	12.1
ES024C1	Hospitalet de Llobregat, L'	256	25.0	1	21.5	20.9				15.5						
ES025C1	Santa Cruz de Tenerife															
ES026C1	Coruña, A	261	24.1	1	33.6	15.3	1	26.1	20.1	11.7	1	15.3	11.8	1	11.8	11.7
ES027C1	Barakaldo	123	18.2							11.6						
ES028C1	Reus	112	17.2				1	17.7	18.6	10.7						
ES029C1	Telde															
ES030C1	Parla	123	19.7							9.9						
ES031C1	Lugo	100	17.0				1	12.6	19.4	10.0				1	10.6	10.1
ES032C1	San Fernando	97	24.7							9.9						
ES033C1	Girona	110	18.4							11.9						
ES034C1	Cáceres	96	14.0	1	13.5	18.8				5.5						
ES035C1	Torre Vieja	92	19.9				1	12.4	20.7	10.7				1	9.9	11.2
ES036C1	Pozuelo de Alarcón	83	16.7							7.8						
ES037C1	Puerto de Santa María, El	95	21.8							9.8						
ES038C1	Coslada	113	19.5				1	21.3	21.9	9.9				1	12.3	11.3
ES039C1	Avilés	96	21.0				2	20.8	24.5	11.8				1	7.4	12.3
ES040C1	Talavera de la Reina	88	18.4	1	21.1	20.6				8.5						
ES041C1	Palencia	81	13.7				1	14.9	18.0	7.4						
ES042C1	Sant Boi de Llobregat	89	23.0							13.9						
ES043C1	Ferrol	96	22.4				1	17.9	17.1	10.8				1	7.9	11.3
ES044C1	Pontevedra	99	18.9				1	18.1	19.9	9.3				1	11.4	10.9
ES045C1	Ceuta	84	20.4	1	18.1	13.5				8.7	1	10.5				
ES046C1	Gandia	88	16.6				1	15.8	20.1	9.5						

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	PM ₁₀							PM _{2.5}						
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
ES047C1	Rozas de Madrid, Las	91	15.6													7.3
ES048C1	Guadalajara	87	19.8	1	26.7	18.2										10.3
ES049C1	Sant Cugat del Vallès	85	23.0													14.1
ES050C1	Manresa	91	20.9													13.2
ES051C1	Getxo	113	16.7													10.1
ES052C1	Rubí	77	22.7	1	21.0	17.1										14.0
ES053C1	Ciudad Real	76	24.3	1	25.9	20.2										12.1
ES054C1	Benidorm	83	16.4													9.2
ES055C1	Melilla	81	24.0													11.6
ES056C1	Viladecans	98	22.6													13.7
ES057C1	Ponferrada	71	13.2													7.9
ES058C1	San Sebastián de los Reyes	87	16.8													8.4
ES059C1	Zamora	65	13.0					1	12.7	22.1						6.6
ES060C1	Fuengirola	83	22.9													11.0
ES061C1	Cerdanyola del Vallès	83	23.6													14.7
ES062C1	Sanlúcar de Barrameda	68	20.4													9.1
ES063C1	Vilanova i la Geltrú	90	19.4													11.8
ES064C1	Prat de Llobregat, El	63	23.8													14.4
ES065C1	Línea de la Concepción, La	71	24.3													11.6
ES066C1	Cornellà de Llobregat	99	23.1													14.0
ES067C1	Majadahonda	76	16.3	1	13.4	25.3										7.5
ES068C1	Torremolinos	66	24.2													11.8
ES069C1	Castelldefels	65	20.2													11.8
ES070C1	Irun	64	16.0													8.8
ES071C1	Granollers	87	22.4					1	28.1	15.7						13.7
ES072C1	Arrecife															
ES073C1	Elda	78	16.6	1	14.6	24.6										9.6
ES074C1	Santa Lucía de Tirajana															
ES075C1	Mollet del Vallès	56	24.7													15.7
ES501C1	Granada	272	31.3													16.9
ES503C1	Badalona	234	23.0													14.2
ES504C1	Móstoles	214	17.8	1	16.6	13.7										8.5
ES505C1	Elche/Elx	239	18.8													10.9
ES506C1	Cartagena	227	22.0	1	24.4	18.5										12.0
ES507C1	Sabadell	222	23.3													14.3
ES508C1	Jerez de la Frontera	222	21.6	1	21.0	20.5										10.1
ES509C1	Fuenlabrada	189	18.6													9.1
ES510C1	Donostia/San Sebastián	235	16.9	1	15.0	20.0	2	20.0	23.1						2	8.4
ES511C1	Alcalá de Henares	203	19.7					1	19.9	20.4					1	12.5
ES512C1	Terrassa	227	22.4													10.3
ES513C1	Leganés	199	18.3					1	20.8	18.3					1	12.0
ES514C1	Almería	198	42.0													11.0
ES515C1	Burgos	180	13.5					1	18.6	13.9						18.5
ES516C1	Salamanca	162	14.5	1	16.5	22.8	1	15.9	26.6							6.9
ES517C1	Alcorcón	170	17.4													6.7
ES518C1	Getafe	164	18.7													8.4
ES519C1	Albacete	172	22.2	1	25.5	24.3										9.3
ES520C1	Castellón/Castelló de la Pl.	187	16.0													9.7
ES521C1	Huelva	156	21.4					1	24.4	19.7						11.3
ES522C1	Cádiz	124	22.4													13.7
ES523C1	León	158	13.9	1	11.9	15.6	1	20.2	20.2							9.0
ES524C1	San Cristóbal de La Laguna															8.8
ES525C1	Tarragona	141	18.2													9.1
ES526C1	Santa Coloma de Gramenet	134	23.0													11.5
ES527C1	Jaén	118	25.9													11.5
ES528C1	Lleida	142	19.2													14.2

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT		
ES529C1	Ourense	113	15.5					1	23.6	16.2	8.6					1	10.2	9.3
ES530C1	Mataró	129	21.6								13.4							
ES531C1	Dos Hermanas	129	21.3								9.9							
ES532C1	Algeciras	120	23.1								11.1							
ES533C1	Marbella	141	21.1					1	34.7	15.1	9.8							
ES534C1	Torrejón de Ardoz	124	19.9	1	21.4	16.4					10.2	1	10.8	10.0				
ES535C1	Alcobendas	105	16.7					1	15.5	20.5	8.3							
ES536C1	Alcalá de Guadaíra	79	21.8								10.2							
ES537C1	Alcoy/Alcoi	61	15.0	1	13.4	17.6					7.7							
ES538C1	Ávila	59	14.2	1	13.5	22.6					5.9							
ES539C1	Benalmádena	63	23.3								11.1							
ES540C1	Chiclana de la Frontera	82	27.1								10.5							
ES541C1	Collado Villalba	63	15.2								6.9				1	10.6	9.6	
ES542C1	Cuenca	57	20.2	1	24.6	21.6					10.6							
ES543C1	Eivissa	55	19.4								9.0							
ES544C1	Linares	61	26.2								13.5							
ES545C1	Lorca	93	22.4								11.4							
ES546C1	Mérida	64	14.7	1	14.5	17.0					5.9							
ES547C1	Sagunto/Sagunt	76	16.5	1	17.8	14.5					9.7							
ES548C1	Torrelavega	61	21.4	2	19.7	22.2	1	19.5	25.7	13.6								
ES549C1	Valdemoro	74	19.3								9.8	1	11.2	9.7				
ES550C1	Puerto de la Cruz																	
ES551C1	Paterna	118	17.4								10.3							
ES552C1	Igualada	54	18.4								11.1							
ES553C1	Torrent	91	17.7								10.4							
ES554C1	Mislata	66	18.0								10.7							
ES555C1	Rivas-Vaciamadrid	80	19.7	1	21.5	13.6					9.9							
ES556C1	Santurtzi	75	16.5								9.9							
ES557C1	Esplugues de Llobregat	61	23.5								14.1							
ES558C1	San Vicente del Raspeig	55	17.8								10.3							
FI001C2	Helsinki	575	13.2	1	10.6	19.8	2	18.4	17.8	5.9	2	5.4	5.6	1	7.3	6.1		
FI002C1	Tampere	219	9.9					2	10.8	18.7	5.1	1	3.9	4.9	1	5.8	5.5	
FI003C1	Turku	183	11.2								6.2							
FI004C3	Oulu	188	9.1	1	9.7	14.8	1	10.9	29.2	5.6				1	5.1	6.1		
FI005C1	Espoo	254	12.5					1	17.1	18.0	6.0			1	6.1	7.6		
FI006C1	Vantaa	207	14.4					1	14.7	21.5	6.8			1	6.6	7.3		
FI007C2	Lahti	120	10.8					2	14.8	15.4	5.4			1	4.3	6.2		
FI008C3	Kuopio	114	7.0					2	12.4	11.2	4.7							
FI009C1	Jyväskylä	133	8.8	1	7.8	13.9	1	11.4	12.1	5.6								
FR001P1	City of Paris	7 194	19.9	7	18.9	20.4	6	30.5	17.9	11.8	3	11.0	11.1	2	15.9	14.7		
FR003C2	City of Lyon	1 038	17.1	3	17.1	14.2	4	22.6	17.2	10.4	2	11.3	10.0	1	12.9	11.9		
FR004C2	City of Toulouse	597	15.2	3	15.0	16.5	2	21.1	14.0	9.0	2	8.5	8.9	1	10.6	10.8		
FR006C2	City of Strasbourg	405	19.0	1	19.2	21.5	2	23.0	11.7	12.8	1	14.0	12.9					
FR007C1	City of Bordeaux	617	17.0	2	16.5	19.5	3	18.8	12.5	10.0	1	9.8	9.8					
FR008C1	City of Nantes	443	16.8	2	16.2	10.9	1	19.3	29.0	9.8	1	9.8	9.8	1	10.4	11.0		
FR009C1	City of Lille	907	20.6	2	20.5	10.0	1	20.5	20.9	12.9	1	13.3	13.1	2	12.3	12.9		
FR010C1	City of Montpellier	287	15.5	1	15.3	9.6	1	18.4	20.2	8.1	1	7.2	7.9	1	9.2	10.0		
FR011C1	City of Saint-Étienne	207	15.1	1	13.0	18.7	1	18.6	22.3	9.2	1	8.3	9.2					
FR012C1	City of Le Havre	203	17.7	2	17.7	16.4	1	24.2	19.2	10.4	1	10.9	10.1	1	10.0	10.8		
FR013C2	City of Rennes	218	15.6	1	13.5	14.8	1	18.2	19.7	9.7	1	9.1	9.6	1	9.8	10.1		
FR014C2	City of Amiens	146	18.1	1	18.9	18.3				11.3				1	11.7	11.8		
FR016C1	City of Nancy	232	17.0	1	16.1	17.0				10.3	1	8.8	10.2	1	10.1	11.1		
FR017C2	City of Metz	179	16.5	2	17.0	16.6	1	18.7	21.0	10.1	1	10.3	10.1					
FR018C1	City of Reims	208	18.0	2	17.6	21.2	1	22.7	19.6	11.4	1	11.4	11.4	1	11.4	11.4		
FR019C1	City of Orléans	221	14.8	1	11.8	15.5	1	18.7	18.0	8.9	1	10.0	8.9					
FR020C2	City of Dijon	203	14.8	2	14.9	14.9				8.2	1	6.8	8.1	1	7.9	9.1		

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
FR021C2	City of Poitiers	105	15.2	2	14.4	17.4	1	21.0	21.3	9.2	1	9.8	9.1			
FR022C2	City of Clermont-Ferrand	203	13.7	3	13.7	15.6	2	15.5	17.9	8.2	1	8.1	8.5	1	9.4	9.6
FR023C2	City of Caen	163	16.4	2	16.1	17.8	1	18.9	19.1	9.8	1	9.1	9.7			
FR024C2	City of Limoges	161	14.2	1	13.2	16.9	1	16.1	21.7	8.7	1	8.1	8.5			
FR025C1	City of Besançon	124	15.0	1	14.8	16.3				9.2	1	9.2	9.2			
FR026C2	City of Grenoble	313	18.5	2	17.6	17.8	2	22.0	19.2	11.5	1	10.9	11.7	1	9.7	11.3
FR028C1	City of Saint-Denis															
FR030C1	City of Fort-de-France															
FR032C2	City of Toulon	335	21.0	1	23.3	13.7	1	27.5	19.5	10.4	1	12.3	10.5			
FR034C2	City of Valenciennes	128	19.6	1	17.4	14.8	1	22.8	15.7	12.4				1	12.4	13.0
FR035C2	City of Tours	248	15.5	1	15.7	14.9	1	17.3	17.9	9.6	1	10.5	9.8			
FR036C2	City of Angers	185	16.2	1	15.8	13.8				9.7	1	9.5	9.7			
FR037C1	City of Brest	149	17.2	1	17.3	16.2	1	18.3	17.5	8.5	1	7.5	8.0			
FR038C2	City of Le Mans	163	15.3	1	15.1	14.0				9.4	1	9.3	9.2			
FR039C2	City of Avignon	113	18.0	1	16.7	14.9	1	27.2	21.0	10.5	1	11.0	10.3			
FR040C2	City of Mulhouse	196	16.9	2	15.8	18.6	1	19.4	28.0	11.7	1	12.0	11.6			
FR042C1	City of Dunkerque	150	22.8	2	21.4	21.0				12.2	1	11.4	12.1			
FR043C2	City of Perpignan	134	15.4	2	13.8	19.5				8.7	1	9.6	8.5			
FR044C2	City of Nîmes	151	17.2	1	15.3	15.1	1	21.4	22.4	9.3	1	8.2	9.2			
FR045C2	City of Pau	125	15.9	1	13.2	16.0	1	17.4	17.9	8.5	1	6.0	8.4			
FR046C2	City of Bayonne	116	16.6	2	18.0	17.0	1	23.2	18.4	8.3	1	6.5	7.8			
FR047C2	City of Annemasse	62	16.8	2	16.5	14.9	1	19.7	24.3	10.8	1	9.9	10.5			
FR048C1	City of Annecy	128	16.5	2	16.5	17.5	1	21.4	19.3	10.1	1	8.8	9.7			
FR049C2	City of Lorient	83	15.9	1	15.1	16.8				9.2	1	9.3	9.1			
FR051C2	City of Troyes	112	16.1	2	16.5	21.9				9.8	1	11.2	9.8			
FR052C2	City of Saint-Nazaire	72	16.5	1	17.2	15.2				8.5	1	8.2	8.5			
FR053C1	City of La Rochelle	91	17.0	1	17.0	16.9				9.2	1	9.1	9.2			
FR057C2	City of Boulogne-sur-Mer	81	19.6	1	17.5	15.7	1	22.2	22.1	11.3				1	11.8	11.7
FR058C2	City of Chambéry	95	17.8	2	14.5	16.5	1	17.4	18.3	11.1	1	9.0	11.4			
FR060C2	City of Chartres	84	14.1	1	14.6	16.4				8.4				1	10.5	10.5
FR062C1	City of Calais	81	20.2	2	22.0	15.9				11.8	1	10.2	11.8			
FR063C2	City of Béziers	79	14.3							7.9						
FR064C2	City of Arras	77	18.1	1	19.6	15.6				11.4						
FR065C2	City of Bourges	73	13.5	1	13.9	15.9	1	15.1	19.7	8.0						
FR066C1	City of Saint-Brieuc	76	15.5	1	15.5	16.5				9.3						
FR069C1	C. of Cherbourg-en-Cotentin	85	17.1	1	17.7	16.8				9.5						
FR076C2	City of Belfort	70	15.4				1	15.2	19.4	10.3						
FR077C1	City of Roanne	57	14.8	1	13.7	19.1				9.0						
FR079C2	City of Saint-Quentin	63	17.7	1	17.6	17.9				11.1				1	13.0	11.8
FR084C1	City of Creil	77	18.6	2	18.1	13.7				11.7	1	11.5	11.6			
FR099C1	City of Fréjus	88	19.9	1	18.8	20.1				11.2						
FR202C1	City of Aix-en-Provence	152	19.0	1	18.6	18.4	1	24.8	19.3	10.4	1	10.5	10.3			
FR203C1	City of Marseille	894	20.9	2	19.2	13.4	1	33.2	22.6	10.5	1	9.7	10.6	1	12.5	12.6
FR205C2	City of Nice	710	22.4	1	20.0	15.5	1	29.9	20.6	12.9	1	11.2	12.6	1	13.0	13.4
FR207C1	City of Lens	202	19.2				1	20.8	15.8	12.3						
FR209C2	City of Douai	99	18.9	1	20.0	17.0				12.0	1	12.4	12.0			
FR214C1	City of Valence	96	16.5	1	16.3	14.6	1	18.6	17.1	9.9	1	10.4	9.8	1	9.7	10.0
FR215C2	City of Rouen	334	18.5	2	18.0	17.4	2	23.7	25.1	11.9	1	11.9	11.9	1	14.0	13.6
FR304C1	City of Melun	90	17.5				1	25.6	29.8	10.7				1	13.6	13.0
FR305C1	City of Meaux	67	17.2							10.7						
FR306C1	City of Mantes-la-Jolie	88	16.3							9.9						
FR324C1	City of Martigues	67	23.6							10.5						
FR506C1	City of Colmar	75	16.5	1	16.2	18.2				11.1						
FR520C1	City of Les Abymes															
FR521C1	City of Cayenne															
FR522C1	City of Mamoudzou															

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
HR001C1	Zagreb	797	24.5	1	30.9	20.0	1	25.2	26.5	17.5	1	15.8	17.3			
HR002C1	Rijeka	138	17.1							10.9	1	10.6	11.1			
HR003C1	Slavonski Brod	67	31.0							26.3	1	30.2	26.0			
HR004C1	Osijek	109	27.2				1	39.2	21.2	20.1						
HR005C1	Split	184	21.8				1	16.1	18.4	13.0				1	10.5	13.0
HR006C1	Pula	59	19.6							11.8						
HR007C1	Zadar	76	20.6							11.8						
HU001C1	Budapest	1 775	23.6	3	24.2	18.6	2	31.8	23.7	14.9	2	14.4	14.8			
HU002C1	Miskolc	173	25.1				1	35.6	24.5	17.2						
HU003C1	Nyíregyháza	122	23.6				1	31.9	26.4	16.3						
HU004C1	Pécs	162	22.3	1	22.1	19.9	1	26.1	34.2	15.0	1	13.6	15.1			
HU005C1	Debrecen	213	25.2	1	26.1	21.2				17.1						
HU006C1	Szeged	171	24.8	1	26.8	18.8				15.4	1	15.6	15.3			
HU007C1	Győr	132	20.2	1	23.3	16.1				14.0						
HU008C1	Kecskemét	114	22.5							14.1						
HU009C1	Székesfehérvár	101	21.3							13.9						
HU010C1	Szombathely	81	18.4							12.5						
HU011C1	Szolnok	74	23.7							14.8						
HU012C1	Tatabánya	70	19.8				1	19.4	21.7	13.5						
HU013C1	Veszprém	62	18.4	1	19.3	16.2				12.9	1	14.4	13.2			
HU014C1	Békéscsaba	62	23.3							14.9						
HU015C1	Kaposvár	67	20.2							13.9						
HU016C1	Eger	57	23.1							15.3						
HU017C1	Dunaújváros	49	24.6							15.1						
HU018C1	Zalaegerszeg	61	18.6							12.6						
HU019C1	Sopron	65	16.4							11.1						
IE001C1	Dublin	561	13.8	4	13.1	13.3	3	16.0	16.7	9.0	4	9.0	8.9	2	9.5	9.7
IE002C1	Cork	129	14.3	2	13.4	14.0	1	17.8	17.5	8.9	2	8.2	8.9			
IE003C1	Limerick	63	16.6							11.2						
IE004C1	Galway	73	14.0	1	12.5	14.0				8.7						
IE005C1	Waterford	51	15.6	1	14.9	15.5				10.5	1	10.5	10.6			
IS001C1	Reykjavík	202	9.8	2	10.6	10.8	1	16.7	16.7	4.6	1	5.9	5.6			
IT001C1	Roma	2 747	23.8	8	24.6	24.0	4	27.7	26.4	13.9	6	13.1	13.9	1	14.1	15.2
IT002C1	Milano	1 370	29.1	1	29.4	29.5	3	32.9	32.5	19.5	1	20.9	20.1	1	20.8	19.8
IT003C1	Napoli	1 159	26.8	2	22.8	25.1	5	28.8	29.1	12.4	2	9.2	10.9	2	16.4	15.9
IT004C1	Torino	921	28.5	2	27.5	28.8	2	31.1	30.5	20.8	2	19.8	21.3	1	24.6	18.7
IT005C1	Palermo	677	20.9							12.3						
IT006C1	Genova	610	18.2	1	15.8	18.1	4	21.0	22.2	10.8	1	7.1	10.2	1	12.8	13.9
IT007C1	Firenze	387	20.3	2	18.1	20.1	2	24.2	23.7	13.1	1	11.8	12.9	1	15.5	14.3
IT008C1	Bari	347	22.3	3	22.9	22.5	2	25.2	23.1	13.5				2	13.8	13.6
IT009C1	Bologna	408	24.2	2	23.5	23.9	1	25.5	26.8	15.4	1	13.8	14.8	1	16.3	16.0
IT010C1	Catania	346	21.5							13.0						
IT011C1	Venezia	251	28.8	1	29.8	30.9	1	34.5	31.3	19.8	1	22.4	21.3			
IT012C1	Verona	282	31.0	1	30.4	30.5	1	32.8	32.6	21.1	1	19.4	20.5			
IT013C1	Cremona	77	32.7	1	35.1	32.9	1	33.0	33.5	22.7	1	26.0	22.8	1	20.5	22.6
IT014C1	Trento	119	21.1	1	18.6	22.1	1	21.7	20.1	15.1	1	13.0	15.9			
IT015C1	Trieste	205	17.9	2	18.4	18.0	1	18.4	19.8	11.6	1	11.3	11.6			
IT016C1	Perugia	176	20.8	1	23.6	21.5	2	18.8	21.9	13.0	1	15.7	13.4	2	12.8	14.3
IT017C1	Ancona	104	22.9	1	20.8	23.4				13.3	1	14.0	13.4			
IT019C1	Pescara	128	20.5	1	24.2	20.2	2	23.4	23.8	12.8	1	13.0	12.5	1	14.0	14.1
IT020C1	Campobasso	53	20.2							11.3	1	10.4	11.4			
IT021C1	Caserta	89	26.8	1	21.4	26.8	1	33.1	30.5	14.8	1	13.5	14.8	1	13.5	15.7
IT022C1	Taranto	211	21.6	2	20.6	21.2	1	22.4	22.1	13.1				1	10.9	13.2
IT023C1	Potenza	68	20.4				2	16.7	21.3	10.0						
IT024C1	Catanzaro	93	19.9	1	15.0	18.6	1	24.8	23.6	11.4	1	9.6	10.3			
IT025C1	Reggio di Calabria	186	22.0	1	23.0	22.2	1	22.4	23.1	12.6	1	11.4	12.7			

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT		
IT026C1	Sassari	126	20.1	1	24.6	21.2	1	18.7	21.2	8.2	1	5.8	8.1					
IT027C1	Cagliari	172	20.2				1	30.1	28.2	10.5				1	19.2	16.8		
IT028C1	Padova	253	32.7	1	31.7	32.8	1	34.9	35.0	21.9								
IT029C1	Brescia	218	34.0	1	33.2	32.8	1	29.1	33.1	24.3	1	24.6	23.5	1	18.5	23.7		
IT030C1	Modena	188	28.3	1	30.0	28.4	1	33.2	31.6	18.2	1	18.1	18.2					
IT031C1	Foggia	154	21.5	1	22.5	21.6				11.9	1	13.1	12.0					
IT032C1	Salerno	145	25.2	1	27.7	25.2	1	21.7	25.7	11.2	1	9.2	11.0	1	12.0	14.2		
IT033C1	Piacenza	105	27.2	1	27.0	27.1	1	30.5	30.2	18.8	1	20.8	18.8					
IT034C1	Bolzano	106	19.0				1	15.5	20.5	13.3								
IT035C1	Udine	99	19.9	2	18.8	19.8	1	20.6	21.2	13.7	1	14.5	13.7					
IT036C1	La Spezia	104	18.8	1	20.6	19.3	3	19.4	19.3	10.7	1	11.1	11.1	1	12.3	11.6		
IT037C1	Lecce	112	22.3				2	21.1	22.6	13.6				2	11.7	13.7		
IT038C1	Barletta	94	21.4	1	22.0	21.4				11.9	1	11.2	11.9					
IT039C1	Pesaro	96	24.9	1	32.8	25.3				14.5	1	17.3	14.7					
IT040C1	Como	104	22.1				1	25.9	24.9	15.0				1	19.8	16.4		
IT041C1	Pisa	95	22.4	1	21.7	23.1	1	24.9	24.3	13.9	1	12.4	14.3	1	15.9	14.9		
IT042C1	Treviso	111	30.6	1	30.7	30.3	1	32.4	32.4	21.5	1	20.3	21.5					
IT043C1	Varese	106	22.5				1	23.6	25.2	15.2				1	18.8	17.2		
IT044C1	Busto Arsizio	103	26.3	1	22.7	26.8				17.7								
IT045C1	Asti	80	25.8	1	29.1	26.6	1	30.4	29.4	17.8								
IT046C1	Pavia	75	27.4	1	29.1	27.0	1	35.6	31.1	19.2	1	23.3	19.0					
IT047C1	Massa	79	20.0				1	19.2	20.0	11.7				1	11.4	11.6		
IT048C1	Cosenza	85	21.2	1	21.6	21.4				12.3	1	12.5	12.6					
IT052C1	Savona	67	18.1	1	15.9	17.8	1	17.4	21.2	11.3	1	9.3	11.2	1	12.7	13.5		
IT054C1	Matera	58	21.1							12.3								
IT056C1	Acireale	66	21.2							12.6								
IT057C1	Avellino	68	24.4				1	27.7	26.1	11.5				1	14.6	13.5		
IT058C1	Pordenone	61	23.6				1	24.5	25.6	17.3				1	17.5	17.3		
IT060C1	Lecco	51	20.8	1	17.3	20.0	1	21.8	22.7	14.1	1	12.8	13.9					
IT061C1	Altamura	70	21.3				1	19.2	21.4	12.1				1	11.7	12.2		
IT062C1	Bitonto	59	21.4							12.7								
IT063C1	Molfetta	61	21.7				1	23.1	21.9	12.5								
IT064C1	Battipaglia	53	23.3	1	23.9	23.8				10.7	1	9.2	10.4					
IT065C1	Bisceglie	54	21.3							12.2								
IT066C1	Carpi	72	29.6	1	29.8	30.1				19.3								
IT067C1	Cerignola	60	21.8							11.8								
IT068C1	Gallarate	77	25.3							17.1								
IT069C1	Gela	76	21.6	1	23.3	21.3	1	31.1	30.1	12.6								
IT070C1	Saronno	48	26.2	1	26.9	26.0				17.5	1	16.8	17.3					
IT071C1	Bagheria	64	19.9							11.6								
IT072C1	Anzio	69	21.7							12.2								
IT073C1	Sassuolo	48	24.3	1	25.1	24.7				15.5	1	14.2	15.8					
IT501C1	Messina	245	22.5	1	22.6	22.8	1	22.0	23.2	13.3								
IT502C1	Prato	202	23.6	1	23.4	24.2	1	25.1	25.3	15.6	1	15.5	16.1	1	15.6	15.5		
IT503C1	Parma	194	27.3	1	30.4	27.0	1	29.6	28.6	17.4	1	17.2	17.0					
IT504C1	Livorno	154	18.9	2	17.7	19.1	1	23.1	22.1	10.9	1	9.1	10.9	1	12.4	12.8		
IT505C1	Reggio nell'Emilia	183	27.5	1	26.7	26.9	1	32.2	29.9	17.7	1	17.8	17.3					
IT506C1	Ravenna	154	26.2	1	26.3	30.7	1	30.2	30.0	16.9	1	18.9	18.2					
IT507C1	Ferrara	146	27.3	1	26.3	27.1	1	32.0	31.0	18.0	1	17.1	17.9					
IT508C1	Rimini	155	24.3	1	29.3	24.6	1	29.9	27.7	14.7	1	15.9	15.0					
IT509C1	Siracusa	126	20.3	2	20.5	21.7	2	25.1	26.1	12.2								
IT510C1	Monza	171	28.4	2	27.6	27.5				19.2	1	20.2	19.4					
IT511C1	Bergamo	163	27.5	1	26.0	29.7	1	27.2	29.1	19.5	1	20.1	20.9					
IT512C1	Forli	122	23.1	1	22.1	23.6	1	27.1	27.0	15.0	1	14.2	15.4					
IT513C1	Latina	126	22.0	2	22.6	22.4	1	23.5	26.0	13.4	1	11.9	13.1					
IT514C1	Vicenza	133	34.4	1	32.5	34.7				24.1	1	25.6	24.4					

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
IT515C1	Terni	112	20.9	1	25.3	21.3	2	26.7	23.8	13.8	1	17.4	14.1	2	17.3	15.4
IT516C1	Novara	110	26.8	1	24.3	27.0	1	26.8	30.3	18.1	1	17.0	18.1			
IT517C1	Giugliano in Campania	201	27.0							13.0						
IT518C1	Alessandria	90	26.3	1	28.9	26.7	1	34.7	31.0	17.5	1	19.9	17.8			
IT519C1	Arezzo	102	19.1	1	17.9	19.8	1	23.4	22.3	12.2	1	11.8	12.8			
IT520C1	Grosseto	78	16.7	1	16.8	16.4	1	24.1	20.8	10.0	1	9.3	9.3			
IT521C1	Brindisi	89	21.4	2	20.8	21.5	1	24.8	22.7	13.1	1	12.2	13.2	1	12.6	13.2
IT522C1	Trapani	94	21.3	1	20.6	20.6				11.7						
IT523C1	Ragusa	72	22.2							11.9						
IT524C1	Andria	101	21.5				1	21.8	21.6	11.9				1	12.3	12.4
IT525C1	Trani	57	21.4							12.2						
IT526C1	L'Aquila	68	18.3	1	15.6	18.3				11.1	1	10.1	11.4			
LT001C1	Vilnius	552	21.5	2	21.1	21.5	1	29.8	29.2	14.1	1	11.1	14.3	1	15.9	14.7
LT002C1	Kaunas	325	24.3				1	34.0	30.9	15.2				1	11.4	15.9
LT003C1	Panevėžys	105	23.7	1	26.1	23.8				15.1						
LT004C1	Alytus	60	20.1							13.0						
LT501C1	Klaipėda	164	20.5				2	22.9	22.5	11.9				1	15.6	12.6
LT502C1	Šiauliai	113	23.6				1	23.8	25.1	13.6						
LU001C1	Luxembourg	103	15.9	1	20.3	15.7	1	17.4	17.8	8.4	1	7.2	8.1	1	9.8	10.4
LV001C1	Rīga	669	22.7	1	20.2	24.1	1	34.5	32.4	13.0	1	12.1	13.9			
LV002C1	Liepāja	77	19.9				1	21.3	21.8	11.5				1	13.4	12.4
LV003C1	Jelgava	64	23.2							13.5						
LV501C1	Daugavpils	96	20.4							13.2						
MT001C1	Valletta (greater)	228	28.3				1	41.3	37.8	12.4				1	14.0	15.3
NL001C2	Greater 's-Gravenhage	752	19.0	2	18.2	18.8	1	22.4	20.8	10.4	1	8.6	9.9			
NL002C2	Greater Amsterdam	934	18.8	2	19.0	18.8	4	20.4	20.1	11.2	2	11.5	11.1	3	10.9	11.2
NL003C2	Greater Rotterdam	1 232	19.2	4	19.4	19.3	5	20.5	20.5	10.9	3	11.3	10.9	4	12.8	12.0
NL004C2	Greater Utrecht	422	18.7				2	18.5	19.5	11.1	1	10.5	11.0	1	11.4	11.3
NL005C2	Greater Eindhoven	265	18.9	1	18.5	18.4	2	19.8	20.1	11.8	1	11.9	11.2			
NL006C1	Tilburg	216	19.2							11.2						
NL007C1	Groningen	195	17.6				1	22.2	20.9	9.6	1	8.7	9.5	1	8.6	9.7
NL008C1	Enschede	155	16.8							10.5	1	8.9	10.4			
NL009C2	Greater Arnhem	186	17.6							11.3						
NL010C2	Greater Heerlen	209	15.6	1	15.8	15.3	1	18.1	18.7	9.4	1	8.5	9.3	1	9.9	10.8
NL011C1	Almere	190	17.4							10.5						
NL012C1	Breda	180	19.2	1	20.0	19.3	1	19.6	20.0	10.7	1	9.1	10.7	1	10.5	11.4
NL013C1	Nijmegen	173	17.8				1	20.8	19.9	11.3	1	10.5	11.3	1	11.0	11.3
NL014C1	Apeldoorn	163	16.5							10.5						
NL015C1	Leeuwarden	124	17.1							9.5						
NL016C2	Greater Sittard-Geleen	129	16.6							10.2						
NL018C1	Hilversum	108	18.1							11.0						
NL020C1	Roosendaal	81	19.7							11.0						
NL021C2	Greater Nissewaard	145	19.7							11.1						
NL023C1	Purmerend	82	18.1							10.5						
NL026C1	Alphen aan den Rijn	112	18.8							10.8						
NL028C1	Bergen op Zoom	68	19.3							10.9						
NL030C1	Gouda	75	18.8							10.8						
NL031C1	Hoorn	73	17.3							10.0						
NL032C2	Greater Middelburg	93	19.6							11.1						
NL501C2	Greater Haarlem	270	18.6				1	18.0	19.6	10.4						
NL502C1	Zaanstad	152	18.9	1	18.3	18.8				10.9	1	11.1	10.9			
NL503C1	's-Hertogenbosch	156	18.8							11.3						
NL504C1	Amersfoort	152	18.1							11.2						
NL505C1	Maastricht	125	16.4							9.8						
NL507C2	Greater Leiden	257	18.7							10.3						
NL508C1	Haarlemmermeer	167	18.5							10.5						

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NL509C1	Zoetermeer	120	18.9								10.7					
NL511C1	Zwolle	122	17.1								10.7					
NL512C2	Greater Ede	156	18.2								11.3					
NL513C1	Deventer	103	17.2								11.0					
NL514C2	Greater Alkmaar	200	18.0								10.1					
NL515C1	Venlo	107	16.6								11.0					
NL516C1	Helmond	93	18.4								11.6					
NL517C1	Hengelo	84	16.9								10.7					
NL519C1	Almelo	79	17.3								10.8					
NL520C1	Lelystad	76	17.4								10.1					
NL521C1	Oss	99	18.4								11.4					
NL522C1	Assen	70	16.9								9.8					
NL524C1	Veenendaal	63	19.2								11.5					
NL528C1	Greater Heemskerk	92	18.5								10.2					
NL529C1	Greater Soest	71	17.6								10.8					
NO001C1	Oslo	613	13.9	2	13.3	13.5	8	17.3	16.4	8.0	1	7.0	8.1	8	7.5	8.0
NO002C1	Bergen	260	9.2	2	8.2	9.0	3	13.0	13.2	5.3	2	5.0	5.3	3	6.1	6.3
NO003C1	Trondheim	175	10.5	1	10.0	10.2	3	12.4	12.8	6.2	1	6.2	6.0	3	5.1	6.4
NO004C1	Stavanger	133	12.0	1	11.4	12.1	1	10.8	12.9	6.8	1	7.1	6.9	1	7.8	7.5
NO005C1	Kristiansand	84	13.6	1	15.8	14.1	1	20.7	18.3	7.6						
NO006C1	Tromsø	68	9.9	1	12.3	11.2	1	19.5	16.9	5.0				1	6.3	6.0
PL001C	M. Warszawa	1 759	28.4	6	24.4	28.6	1	37.5	36.4	20.7	5	17.8	20.6	1	24.7	23.7
PL002C	M. Łódź	747	33.2	4	31.5	34.2	1	33.0	35.3	22.9	3	21.2	23.3			
PL003C	M. Kraków	782	38.4	4	32.8	35.3	2	42.2	40.9	27.9	1	24.7	30.0	1	29.2	29.8
PL004C	M. Wrocław	642	26.6	2	23.8	27.4				18.4	2	16.8	19.7	1	19.1	19.0
PL005C	M. Poznań	601	28.0	4	26.7	27.7				19.0	1	18.2	18.9			
PL006C	M. Gdańsk	471	22.2	4	22.4	23.5				14.6	1	12.4	13.6			
PL007C	M. Szczecin	433	22.1	2	19.5	21.5	1	23.6	24.6	15.2	1	13.7	12.8	1	16.9	17.3
PL008C	M. Bydgoszcz	367	28.0	1	28.6	28.0	1	33.1	28.6	18.5	1	14.6	16.7	1	21.7	18.6
PL009C	M. Lublin	359	27.1	2	24.5	27.3				19.5	2	18.2	19.7			
PL010C	M. Katowice	314	37.3	1	33.0	37.6	1	40.5	39.0	25.4	1	24.1	25.4	1	27.7	25.8
PL011C	M. Białystok	306	23.2	2	20.1	23.5				15.8	2	14.6	16.2			
PL012C	M. Kielce	208	29.7	2	28.5	29.8				19.7	2	18.1	19.8			
PL013C	M. Toruń	209	24.9	2	25.9	25.6	1	22.9	26.1	16.4	1	15.3	16.9			
PL014C	M. Olsztyn	179	21.8	1	20.2	21.9				15.8	1	15.0	16.1			
PL015C	M. Rzeszów	192	26.9	1	24.5	26.8	1	22.5	27.1	20.2	1	16.9	20.1	1	19.8	20.3
PL016C	M. Opole	137	29.6	2	28.3	29.9				20.2	1	18.0	20.6			
PL017C	M. Gorzów Wielkopolski	129	22.7	2	21.3	22.9				16.0	1	14.8	16.2			
PL018C	M. Zielona Góra	140	22.2	1	20.3	23.4				15.8	1	13.9	16.7			
PL019C	M. Jelenia Góra	88	21.7	2	22.3	21.9				15.8	1	20.1	16.8			
PL020C	M. Nowy Sącz	93	29.6	1	35.3	30.2				22.5	1	27.3	23.0			
PL021C	M. Suwałki	70	20.2	1	19.8	19.8				12.9	1	12.0	12.9			
PL022C	M. Konin	84	26.4	1	23.3	26.9				18.2						
PL023C	M. Żory	65	34.2	1	35.9	34.6				24.1	1	24.9	24.2			
PL024C	M. Częstochowa	244	31.8	1	26.3	32.2	1	34.5	33.0	21.5	1	20.3	21.7			
PL025C	M. Radom	229	26.6	2	27.3	26.8				19.5	2	20.9	19.7			
PL026C	M. Płock	128	27.4	2	23.6	27.5				19.2	2	18.0	19.2			
PL027C	M. Kalisz	110	29.2	1	26.9	29.6				21.2	1	21.4	21.6			
PL028C	M. Koszalin	113	19.4	1	19.1	19.1	1	21.5	21.5	12.9	1	13.7	12.6			
PL029C	M. Słupsk	99	20.4	1	18.0	20.8				13.1	1	11.2	13.5			
PL030C	M. Jastrzębie-Zdrój	98	33.4							23.8						
PL031C	M. Siedlce	80	25.2	1	25.7	25.1				18.9	1	19.6	19.1			
PL032C	M. Piotrków Trybunalski	78	29.9	1	33.6	30.3				20.9	1	24.9	21.3			
PL033C	Lubin	78	23.6							16.4						
PL034C	Piła	75	24.5	1	24.5	24.7				16.6						
PL035C	Inowrocław	77	25.5	1	22.1	25.7				17.2						

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	PM ₁₀							PM _{2.5}						
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
PL036C	Ostrowiec Świętokrzyski	78	24.8							17.8						
PL037C	Gniezno	73	26.1	1	27.3	26.6				18.2						
PL038C	Stargard	71	21.1							14.4						
PL039C	Ostrów Wielkopolski	77	28.1	1	31.3	28.4				20.0						
PL040C	M. Przemyśl	70	23.0	1	23.6	23.1				18.2	1	19.4	18.4			
PL041C	M. Zamość	70	25.3	1	26.4	25.5				18.6	1	18.4	18.7			
PL042C	M. Chełm	70	23.7	1	23.5	23.8				17.8	1	18.2	17.9			
PL043C	Pabianice	75	29.0	1	28.8	29.2				20.0						
PL044C	Głogów	71	26.1	1	24.3	25.8				18.6						
PL045C	Stalowa Wola	67	25.2	1	25.4	25.3				18.5						
PL046C	Tomaszów Mazowiecki	69	28.9	1	29.9	29.6				20.1						
PL047C	M. Łomża	67	22.6	1	23.9	22.4				17.5	1	21.4	17.7			
PL048C	M. Leszno	65	27.0	1	25.9	25.3				19.2						
PL049C	Świdnica	63	25.3	1	25.4	25.5				17.3						
PL050C	Zgierz	59	29.7	1	34.8	30.9				20.9	1	27.0	21.8			
PL051C	Tczew	63	21.2							14.0						
PL052C	Elk	60	20.0	1	19.7	19.9				14.0						
PL501C	M. Gdynia	265	19.4	3	17.1	18.4				12.7						
PL502C	M. Sosnowiec	261	36.5	1	29.5	36.5				25.1						
PL503C	M. Gliwice	211	35.1	1	33.3	36.2				24.6	1	26.4	25.2			
PL504C	M. Zabrze	173	36.2	1	38.7	35.7				25.1						
PL505C	M. Bytom	199	37.9							26.0						
PL506C	M. Bielsko-Biała	185	31.1	1	27.5	32.3				22.1	1	21.6	22.4	1	27.6	22.9
PL507C	M. Ruda Śląska	154	36.9							25.1						
PL508C	M. Rybnik	161	34.9	1	44.1	32.7				25.0						
PL509C	M. Tychy	133	35.2	1	31.6	31.5				24.6						
PL511C	M. Wałbrzych	132	24.4	1	23.9	24.7				16.8	1	15.4	17.0			
PL512C	M. Elbląg	126	21.4	1	20.9	21.9				14.6	1	15.1	14.9			
PL513C	M. Włocławek	119	24.1	1	26.5	24.2	2	26.3	26.3	16.8	1	17.2	17.0	1	22.9	17.2
PL514C	M. Tarnów	121	30.8	1	26.4	29.9	1	34.1	32.7	22.7	1	20.1	22.3	1	22.6	23.5
PL515C	M. Chorzów	160	38.3							26.0						
PL516C	M. Legnica	106	26.3	1	28.5	26.9				18.0	1	17.0	18.3			
PL517C	M. Grudziądz	102	24.9	1	27.4	25.2				17.1	1	19.6	17.3			
PT001C1	Lisboa	628	23.8	1	17.1	24.5	3	21.6	22.9	13.1	1	9.2	13.5	1	11.7	14.8
PT002C1	Porto	238	19.0							9.3						
PT003C1	Braga	191	19.0							9.8						
PT004C1	Funchal															
PT005C1	Coimbra	151	17.6	1	17.5	18.7	1	22.2	20.0	8.6						
PT006C1	Setúbal	134	19.0	1	20.1	19.1	1	18.5	19.8	9.0						
PT007C1	Ponta Delgada															
PT008C1	Aveiro	85	23.0	1	23.5	22.9	1	22.4	23.4	10.4	1	9.0	10.5			
PT009C1	Faro	68	20.4	1	17.5	20.9				8.5						
PT010C1	Seixal	162	20.1							10.0						
PT011C1	Amadora	168	17.4	1	15.8	17.4				8.4						
PT012C1	Almada	180	20.1	1	21.2	20.6				10.1	1	10.0	10.5			
PT013C1	Odivelas	157	20.8				1	19.7	18.9	10.9						
PT014C1	Viseu	103	12.8							6.3						
PT015C1	Valongo	106	18.5							9.2						
PT016C1	Viana do Castelo	93	18.3							8.3						
PT017C1	Paredes	99	17.2				1	9.6	17.1	8.7						
PT018C1	Barreiro	100	20.0	1	21.7	20.1				9.3						
PT019C1	Póvoa de Varzim	84	18.1							8.3						
PT501C1	Sintra	385	17.4	1	18.1	17.5				8.2	1	8.1	8.3			
PT502C1	Vila Nova de Gaia	326	19.3							9.4						
PT503C1	Matosinhos	205	19.5	1	17.6	21.0	1	16.4	18.8	9.5						
PT504C1	Gondomar	179	19.2							9.6						

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
PT505C1	Guimarães	190	17.1				1	16.2	17.3	8.8						
PT508C1	Vila Franca de Xira	152	17.7	1	17.6	18.0				8.3						
RO001C1	MUNICIPIUL BUCURESTI	1940	28.2	1	28.9	27.4	2	35.1	32.3	18.4	1	16.4	18.0	1	16.3	19.0
RO002C1	MUNICIPIUL CLUJ-NAPOCA	331	21.2							14.6						
RO003C1	MUNICIPIUL TIMISOARA	326	24.8	1	23.4	24.2	1	30.7	30.1	17.0	1	16.8	16.8			
RO004C1	MUNICIPIUL CRAIOVA	272	34.6							23.5						
RO005C1	MUNICIPIUL BRAILA	181	18.7							13.3						
RO006C1	MUNICIPIUL ORADEA	199	26.6							17.7						
RO007C1	MUNICIPIUL BACAU	149	27.5							19.5						
RO008C1	MUNICIPIUL ARAD	159	23.1							15.3						
RO009C1	MUNICIPIUL SIBIU	148	22.0	1	18.5	22.1				14.8						
RO010C1	MUNICIPIUL TIRGU MURES	147	24.9							16.1						
RO011C1	MUNIC. PIATRA NEAMT	86	20.4	1	20.2	19.5				14.1						
RO012C1	MUNICIPIUL CALARASI	73	24.4	1	26.7	24.0				16.9						
RO013C1	MUNICIPIUL GIURGIU	62	27.8	1	23.8	28.1	1	27.4	27.9	18.0						
RO014C1	MUNICIPIUL ALBA IULIA	64	23.1	1	23.8	23.0				16.4						
RO015C1	MUNICIPIUL FOCSANI	81	19.6							14.2						
RO016C1	MUNICIPIUL TIRGU JIU	86	29.5							21.0						
RO017C1	MUNICIPIUL TULCEA	75	19.0				1	28.2	26.1	12.9						
RO018C1	MUNICIPIUL TIRGOVISTE	83	23.6							16.0						
RO019C1	MUNICIPIUL SLATINA	72	34.1							23.6						
RO020C1	MUNICIPIUL BIRLAD	56	20.3							14.6						
RO021C1	MUNICIPIUL ROMAN	53	26.8							18.3						
RO022C1	MUNICIPIUL BISTRITA	76	16.6	1	11.1	16.7				11.5						
RO501C1	MUNICIPIUL CONSTANTA	284	23.0							16.1						
RO502C1	MUNICIPIUL IASI	311	28.6	1	32.1	28.3	1	37.3	34.6	19.4						
RO503C1	MUNICIPIUL GALATI	253	18.3	2	14.3	17.6	1	19.0	23.2	12.9						
RO504C1	MUNICIPIUL BRASOV	256	23.1	1	25.0	23.2	2	29.1	28.0	15.8	1	17.1	16.0			
RO505C1	MUNICIPIUL PLOIESTI	216	25.2	1	22.3	26.0	2	25.1	27.7	17.3						
RO506C1	MUNICIPIUL PITESTI	161	29.0							19.4						
RO507C1	MUNICIPIUL BAIA MARE	128	24.9	2	18.7	19.9	1	18.7	26.0	17.4						
RO508C1	MUNICIPIUL BUZAU	119	21.0							14.9						
RO509C1	MUNICIPIUL SATU MARE	107	21.0	1	19.5	21.0				14.6						
RO510C1	MUNICIPIUL BOTOSANI	111	27.3	1	27.4	26.6				16.7	1	13.4	16.2			
RO511C1	MUNIC. RAMNICU VALCEA	102	26.4	1	30.9	29.0				18.7						
RO512C1	MUNICIPIUL SUCEAVA	99	23.3	1	22.6	22.7				15.3						
RO513C1	M. DROBETA-TURNU SEVER	99	34.2							23.7						
SE001C1	Stockholm	967	14.0	1	11.1	18.3	6	19.0	20.8	5.7	1	4.8	6.1	4	6.2	7.4
SE002K1	Greater Göteborg	581	13.8	1	12.8	14.5	2	20.9	20.2	6.7	1	6.8	7.1	1	6.2	8.9
SE003C1	Malmö	312	15.7	1	15.3	15.8	1	16.8	17.5	8.5	1	9.5	8.6	1	10.1	9.8
SE004C1	Jönköping	130	11.0	1	11.5	11.8	1	15.7	16.3	6.0						
SE005C1	Umeå	117	7.3				1	16.1	16.4	3.5	1	3.7	3.8	1	4.8	5.5
SE006C1	Uppsala	203	10.0	1	10.3	11.0	1	17.1	15.5	5.1	1	5.3	5.5	1	5.9	6.2
SE007C1	Linköping	149	10.9				1	22.0	20.1	5.2						
SE008C1	Örebro	139	10.5				1	12.0	14.4	4.5						
SE009C1	Södertälje	91	8.6				2	19.8	15.7	4.4						
SE501C1	Västerås	141	9.9				1	12.3	14.7	4.7				1	6.0	6.7
SE502C1	Norrköping	133	10.3				2	20.7	19.2	5.0						
SE503C1	Helsingborg	134	15.4				1	17.3	17.8	8.6						
SE504C1	Lund	117	15.1				1	12.7	16.1	8.6						
SE505C1	Borås	105	10.8				1	16.6	16.3	5.7						
SI001C1	Ljubljana	285	26.3	2	20.4	26.8	1	23.7	28.6	18.4	1	16.2	19.5			
SI002C1	Maribor	118	21.3				1	22.6	23.4	14.3	1	12.9	14.4			
SK001C1	Bratislava	413	19.8	3	20.7	20.5	1	24.2	23.8	13.3	3	13.5	13.8			
SK002C1	Košice	250	26.0	1	22.6	26.1	1	28.8	29.5	17.6	1	13.7	17.9	1	18.4	19.3
SK003C1	Banská Bystrica	85	19.6	1	16.3	19.5	1	25.8	24.0	13.7	1	10.2	13.5	1	17.6	16.1

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SK004C1	Nitra	81	20.3	1	20.5	19.7	1	23.5	23.9	14.1	1	14.7	13.8	1	15.4	15.8
SK005C1	Prešov	96	24.8				1	27.6	27.6	17.7				1	18.2	18.5
SK006C1	Žilina	89	22.8	1	23.3	23.8				17.0	1	18.4	17.8			
SK007C1	Trnava	70	19.7				1	23.9	23.2	13.6				1	16.2	15.2
SK008C1	Trenčín	60	19.9				1	24.9	23.6	14.3				1	17.7	16.1
UK002C1	Birmingham	1 082	15.5	1	15.2	15.2	1	15.4	17.0	9.7	2	9.4	9.6	1	9.8	10.8
UK003C1	Leeds	753	15.3	1	16.4	14.9	1	15.8	17.1	10.9	1	12.3	10.8	1	12.3	11.1
UK004C1	Glasgow City	670	11.7	1	11.3	11.9	1	10.7	12.3	7.2	1	6.7	7.3	1	6.3	7.6
UK005C1	Bradford	533	14.9							10.5						
UK006C1	Liverpool	496	15.5							9.5						
UK007C1	City of Edinburgh	485	11.4	1	10.9	11.1				6.6	1	6.3	6.4			
UK008C1	Manchester	512	15.9							10.5	1	11.5	10.5			
UK009C1	Cardiff	357	16.1				1	18.8	18.8	10.4						
UK010C1	Sheffield	557	14.8	1	14.9	15.1				10.1	1	10.4	10.3	1	14.5	11.5
UK011C1	Bristol, City of	457	16.1	1	16.0	16.0	1	20.9	19.6	10.5	1	10.8	10.5			
UK012C2	Belfast	351	15.0	1	15.3	14.7	1	18.2	17.6	10.1	1	10.6	10.1			
UK013C1	Newcastle upon Tyne	288	14.2	1	15.2	14.3	1	16.2	16.0	8.8	1	8.8	9.0			
UK014C1	Leicester	383	15.8				1	22.5	19.5	10.6	1	11.2	10.6			
UK016C1	Aberdeen City	226	11.5	1	13.7	14.0				6.1	1	7.3	7.7			
UK017C1	Cambridge	135	15.7							11.0						
UK018C1	Exeter	121	15.1							10.2						
UK019C1	Lincoln	99	15.2							10.4						
UK020C1	Gravesham	109	17.2							11.4						
UK021C1	Stevenage	91	15.4							10.6						
UK022C1	Wrexham	138	13.3				1	12.1	14.5	8.4				1	7.9	9.1
UK023C1	Portsmouth	212	16.8	1	15.0	15.9	1	19.5	19.9	9.7	1	8.9	9.6			
UK024C1	Worcester	103	14.6							9.4						
UK025C1	Coventry	317	15.3				1	19.5	17.7	9.9	1	9.1	9.7			
UK026C1	Kingston upon Hull, City of	273	16.0				1	21.0	20.3	11.0	1	10.8	11.0			
UK027C1	Stoke-on-Trent	261	15.1				1	19.7	17.5	9.7	1	9.5	9.5			
UK028C1	Wolverhampton	255	15.2							9.6						
UK029C1	Nottingham	368	16.2	1	18.1	16.2	1	19.8	19.0	10.6	1	10.8	10.7			
UK030C1	Wirral	320	14.7							8.9	1	8.0	8.6			
UK031C1	Bath and N. East Somerset	183	15.4							10.0						
UK032C1	Thurrock	160	17.3	1	20.5	17.2	1	17.3	20.4	11.5				1	11.5	12.3
UK033C1	Guildford	153	14.9							9.9						
UK034C1	Thanet	134	18.5							11.1						
UK035C1	Nuneaton and Bedworth	129	15.3							10.0						
UK038C1	Waveney	118	16.5							10.5						
UK040C1	Tunbridge Wells	127	16.2							10.6						
UK041C1	Ashford	119	17.0							10.8						
UK043C1	East Staffordshire	121	15.0							9.8						
UK044C1	Darlington	112	14.3							9.8						
UK045C1	Worthing	113	16.3							9.9				1	10.0	10.8
UK046C1	Mansfield	112	15.0							10.0						
UK047C1	Chesterfield	110	14.5	1	12.7	14.3	1	14.1	16.8	9.8	1	8.4	9.6	1	8.9	11.0
UK050C1	Burnley	94	14.5							9.7						
UK051C1	Great Yarmouth	98	16.1							10.4						
UK052C1	Woking	104	15.1							10.1						
UK053C1	Hartlepool	93	16.8							11.2						
UK054C1	Cannock Chase	108	15.1							9.6						
UK055C1	Eastbourne	107	17.8	1	15.5	16.5				10.2	1	10.5	10.5			
UK056C1	Hastings	94	18.1							10.6						
UK057C1	Hyndburn	82	15.0							9.8						
UK059C1	Redditch	86	14.5							9.3						
UK060C1	Tamworth	82	15.4							9.9						

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	
UK061C1	Harlow	84	16.5							11.2							
UK062C1	Halton	126	15.1							9.4							
UK101C1	City of London	4	18.1							11.8							
UK102C1	Barking and Dagenham	188	17.1							11.4							
UK103C1	Barnet	380	16.4							11.0							
UK104C1	Bexley	258	16.7							11.1	1	11.6	11.1				
UK105C1	Brent	301	16.7							11.1							
UK106C1	Bromley	319	16.2							10.8							
UK107C1	Camden	192	17.7	1	17.6	16.8	1	19.5	22.5	11.7	1	10.8	11.4	1	11.1	13.1	
UK108C1	Croydon	368	16.0							10.7							
UK109C1	Ealing	322	16.2					1	27.9	22.4	10.9						
UK110C1	Enfield	318	16.4							11.0							
UK111C1	Greenwich	237	16.6							11.0	1	10.9	10.9				
UK112C1	Hackney	265	17.7							11.7							
UK113C1	Hammersmith and Fulham	188	16.9							11.1							
UK114C1	Haringey	246	17.3							11.5							
UK115C1	Harrow	250	15.8							10.6							
UK116C1	Havering	239	16.9							11.3							
UK117C1	Hillingdon	303	15.7							10.7							
UK118C1	Hounslow	270	16.5							11.1							
UK119C1	Islington	205	17.9							11.7							
UK120C1	Kensington and Chelsea	151	17.4	1	14.5	16.2				11.4	1	9.6	11.0				
UK121C1	Kingston upon Thames	176	15.8							10.6							
UK122C1	Lambeth	324	17.3							11.4							
UK123C1	Lewisham	272	16.6	1	14.7	16.1				11.0	1	9.9	10.9				
UK124C1	Merton	191	16.5							11.0							
UK125C1	Newham	328	17.4							11.5							
UK126C1	Redbridge	292	17.1							11.4							
UK127C1	Richmond upon Thames	209	16.4							11.0	1	11.8	10.9				
UK128C1	Southwark	271	17.0					1	23.6	21.8	11.2						
UK129C1	Sutton	200	15.7							10.5							
UK130C1	Tower Hamlets	258	17.9							11.7							
UK131C1	Waltham Forest	240	17.3							11.5							
UK132C1	Wandsworth	323	16.9							11.3							
UK133C1	Westminster	228	17.8					1	24.0	22.7	11.7	1	12.5	11.1	1	14.3	13.2
UK501C1	Kirklees	425	15.1							10.5							
UK502C1	North Lanarkshire	350	11.1							6.7							
UK503C1	Wakefield	328	15.2							10.8							
UK504C1	Dudley	314	15.0							9.5							
UK505C1	Wigan	322	15.5							9.8	1	9.6	9.6				
UK506C1	Doncaster	306	15.1							10.6							
UK507C1	Stockport	292	15.1							10.0							
UK508C1	Sefton	286	15.3							9.2							
UK509C1	Sandwell	305	15.5							9.8							
UK510C1	Sunderland	274	15.1							9.5	1	9.4	9.2				
UK511C1	Bolton	283	15.6							10.1							
UK512C1	Walsall	269	15.6							9.8							
UK513C1	Medway	264	17.3					1	22.9	21.0	11.4				1	13.9	12.4
UK514C1	Rotherham	267	15.1							10.4							
UK515C1	Brighton and Hove	280	16.8							10.2							
UK516C1	Plymouth	262	16.4	1	16.9	17.1				10.2	1	11.1	10.6				
UK517C1	Swansea	245	15.5					1	18.4	18.0	9.5				1	9.9	9.8
UK518C1	Derby	261	15.9							10.3							
UK519C1	Barnsley	230	14.9							10.3							
UK520C1	Southampton	245	16.3	1	17.1	16.3	1	16.6	18.0	10.1	1	9.6	10.1				
UK521C1	Oldham	226	15.3							10.3							

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	PM ₁₀							PM _{2.5}						
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT
UK522C1	Salford	231	15.8	1	15.3	15.5				10.3	1	9.5	10.2			
UK523C1	Tameside	219	15.1							10.1						
UK524C1	Trafford	228	15.5							10.1						
UK525C1	Milton Keynes	253	14.8							10.3						
UK526C1	Rochdale	216	15.1							10.1						
UK527C1	Solihull	218	15.8							9.9						
UK528C1	Northampton	218	15.1							10.5	1	11.5	10.5			
UK529C1	North Tyneside	198	14.7							8.8						
UK530C1	Gateshead	208	14.1							8.8						
UK531C1	Warrington	204	15.3							9.8						
UK532C1	Luton	217	15.4							10.6						
UK533C1	York	201	14.7	1	14.0	14.7	1	21.9	18.7	10.7	1	11.1	10.9			
UK534C1	Bury	180	15.4					1	17.7	18.0	10.2					
UK535C1	Swindon	213	15.1							9.8						
UK536C1	Stockton-on-Tees	192	15.0					1	13.6	16.0	10.2			2	8.2	10.1
UK537C1	St. Helens	193	15.4					1	20.5	18.1	9.6					
UK538C1	Basildon	185	17.3							11.4						
UK539C1	Bournemouth	192	16.0							10.1	1	10.8	10.0			
UK540C1	Wycombe	187	14.7							9.9						
UK541C1	Southend-on-Sea	182	17.4							11.3	1	10.6	11.2			
UK542C1	Telford and Wrekin	170	14.2							9.0						
UK543C1	North East Lincolnshire	163	16.0							10.7						
UK544C1	Chelmsford	173	16.8							11.2						
UK545C1	Peterborough	205	15.3							10.7						
UK546C1	Colchester	178	16.8							11.1						
UK547C1	South Tyneside	151	17.1							10.3						
UK548C1	Basingstoke and Deane	176	14.8							9.7						
UK549C1	Bedford	176	15.1							10.5						
UK550C1	Dundee City	156	10.7							6.0						
UK551C1	Falkirk	161	11.4							6.9						
UK552C1	Reading	184	15.3					1	17.2	18.7	10.2					
UK553C1	Blackpool	153	15.5							8.7	1	9.2	8.7			
UK554C1	Maidstone	162	16.9							11.1						
UK555C1	Poole	161	16.1							10.3						
UK556C1	Dacorum	153	15.1							10.3						
UK557C1	Blackburn with Darwen	150	14.9							9.7						
UK558C1	Newport	153	15.4	1	15.2	15.0				9.9	1	9.5	9.8			
UK559C1	Middlesbrough	148	14.7							9.9						
UK560C1	Oxford	160	15.1	1	14.2	14.8				9.9	1	8.9	9.7			
UK561C1	Torbay	132	15.9							9.9						
UK562C1	Preston	150	15.4							9.7	1	9.4	9.8			
UK563C1	St Albans	156	15.6							10.6						
UK564C1	Warwick	138	14.6	1	14.4	14.7	1	13.3	16.5	9.6	1	9.8	9.7	1	9.2	10.6
UK565C1	Newcastle-under-Lyme	126	15.0							9.6						
UK566C1	Norwich	162	15.6	1	14.0	15.2				10.6	1	10.3	10.6			
UK567C1	Slough	148	15.4							10.4						
UK568C2	Cheshire West and Chester	348	14.5							9.3						
UK569C1	Ipswich	144	16.6							11.1						
UK571C1	Cheltenham	118	14.8							9.6						
UK572C1	Gloucester	132	15.3							10.0						
UK573C1	Bracknell Forest	135	15.0							10.0						
UK575C1	Carlisle	110	11.9					1	18.6	16.1	7.5			1	10.8	8.9
UK576C1	Crawley	113	16.2							10.8						
UK577C1	Watford	112	15.5							10.4						
UK578C1	Gosport	84	15.9							9.5						
UK579C1	Eastleigh	131	16.2							10.1						

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	PM ₁₀							PM _{2.5}							
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	
UK580C1	Rushmoor	106	14.9								9.8						
UK581C1	Rugby	107	14.6								9.8						
UK582C1	Corby	60	14.8								10.4						
UK583C1	Kettering	96	15.0								10.4						
UK584C1	Inverclyde (Greenock)	81	10.7					1	11.8	11.8	6.4				1	6.6	6.7
UK585C1	Renfrewshire (Paisley)	184	11.4								6.9						
UK586C1	Derry & Strabane	148	11.8	1	11.5	12.0					8.4	1	9.4	9.0			

Cities with no data presented are outside the mapping area (e.g. in French oversea departments).

Table A.2: Total population in thousands of inhabitants (POP), estimated population-weighted concentration in $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ (PWC), number of urban/suburban background (NB) and traffic (NT) stations, average of annual concentrations measured at these background and traffic stations (CSB, CST), averages of annual concentrations estimated at the underlying grid cells of urban background and urban traffic map layers (CMB, CMT) in cities of the Urban Audit for NO_2 annual average 2019 (left) and O_3 indicator 93.2 percentile of daily 8-hour maximums in 2019 (right). Urban traffic stations and areas are relevant NO_2 only.

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	NO_2								O_3			
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	
AT001C1	Wien	1 741	23.7	13	19.2	20.1	3	33.2	32.4	119.9	5	121.3	120.5	
AT002C1	Graz	275	23.7	4	23.7	23.3	2	31.6	31.8	118.3	4	115.8	117.8	
AT003C1	Linz	208	22.9	2	25.5	24.6	2	33.6	31.3	120.5	2	116.9	120.1	
AT004C1	Salzburg	158	19.7	1	20.6	20.5	2	30.0	32.6	118.0	2	121.9	118.2	
AT005C1	Innsbruck	130	26.4	2	24.6	24.3	1	29.1	33.8	120.4	1	122.6	120.1	
AT006C1	Klagenfurt	100	19.5	1	19.7	20.0	3	26.5	26.6	114.5	2	114.2	113.8	
BE001K1	Bruxelles / Brussel (gr. city)	1 192	26.8	5	24.4	25.0	3	37.2	36.7	103.8	4	105.1	103.7	
BE002C1	Antwerpen	544	27.3	3	28.4	28.3	20	36.5	36.6	99.4	1	86.9	98.8	
BE003C1	Gent	277	21.9	1	23.7	23.3	21	31.2	31.3	103.2	1	110.1	102.7	
BE004K1	Charleroi (greater city)	258	21.0	2	23.4	21.6				107.9	1	106.3	106.7	
BE005K1	Liege (greater city)	429	19.8	2	21.2	20.4				112.4	2	111.5	112.4	
BE006C1	Brugge	128	16.1							100.1				
BE007C1	Namur	116	19.1	1	23.8	20.4				110.3				
BE008C1	Leuven	114	20.4							111.8				
BE009K1	Mons (greater city)	167	18.8	1	22.5	18.3				105.5	1	99.8	104.8	
BE010C1	Kortrijk	89	18.4							103.9				
BE011C1	Oostende	80	14.9							101.9				
BE012C1	Mechelen	102	21.0							107.5				
BE013C1	Mouscron	41	17.7							105.3				
BE014K1	La Louvière (greater city)	110	18.9							107.7				
BE015K1	Verviers (greater city)	77	16.1							112.6				
BG001C1	Sofia	1 297	28.3	3	27.9	27.6	2	27.2	32.5	92.7	3	89.0	92.0	
BG002C1	Plovdiv	338	24.3	1	19.9	21.2	1	47.1	38.9	101.4	1	103.7	101.3	
BG003C1	Varna	345	23.6	2	27.6	24.3				102.2	1	106.2	102.2	
BG004C1	Burgas	213	18.1	1	12.6	14.1				95.4	1	90.7	90.3	
BG005C1	Pleven	132	17.0	1	16.6	18.5				95.1				
BG006C1	Ruse	168	22.8	1	21.7	24.4				98.4	1	103.1	98.3	
BG007C1	Vidin	68	17.7							102.4				
BG008C1	Stara Zagora	161	18.1				1	14.9	22.9	102.0				
BG009C1	Sliven	126	18.4							97.6				
BG010C1	Dobrich	91	19.3							99.8				
BG011C1	Shumen	94	17.6	1	19.3	19.0				99.9	1	101.9	99.1	
BG012C1	Pernik	97	18.1	1	16.4	18.8				99.3				
BG013C1	Yambol	75	19.2							97.3				
BG014C1	Haskovo	95	16.7							103.0				
BG015C1	Pazardzhik	116	19.2							101.8				
BG016C1	Blagoevgrad	78	19.7	1	17.8	18.3				99.7	1	106.7	98.7	
BG017C1	Veliko Tarnovo	89	18.3							93.6				
BG018C1	Vratsa	74	18.1	1	19.3	19.2				94.0	1	90.0	91.8	
CH001C1	Zurich	414	26.4	1	25.8	25.6	1	29.2	38.7	115.9	1	122.3	116.3	
CH002C1	Geneva	244	23.9							112.4				
CH003C1	Basel	190	23.4							108.3				
CH004C1	Bern	176	21.4	6	21.3	21.2	4	35.3	34.5	120.4	5	121.8	121.5	
CH005C1	Lausanne	180	18.2	4	19.4	19.7	3	32.9	31.9	117.9	3	117.6	116.4	
CH006C1	Winterthur	116	18.9	2	17.6	18.0	1	31.6	33.3	114.8	2	119.6	115.5	
CH007C1	St. Gallen	83	16.6	2	14.4	14.7	2	18.7	21.9	115.6	2	114.0	115.4	
CH008C1	Lucerne	102	17.6	2	17.2	17.3	1	31.0	29.1	124.2	2	130.6	124.1	
CH009C2	Lugano	86	18.0	1	20.1	18.2				115.1				

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	NO ₂						O ₃					
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	
CH010C1	Biel/Bienne	60	13.6	1	14.1	15.4					117.9	1	118.3	117.6
CH011C1	Thun	53	14.9	1	12.9	15.2					114.0	1	103.9	113.8
CH012C1	Zug	38	14.4					1	18.2	22.6	118.6	1	118.5	118.6
CY001C1	Lefkosia	268	15.2	1	13.6	13.9					118.4	1	119.2	118.3
CY002K1	Greater Larnaka	78	14.5	2	15.8	16.2					115.0	2	113.4	115.6
CY501C1	Lemesos	191	16.5	1	15.0	16.1					122.1	1	119.4	122.0
CZ001C1	Praha	1 291	14.3								119.0			
CZ002C1	Brno	396	13.3	1	12.7	13.5					115.6	1	119.4	115.4
CZ003C1	Ostrava	310	18.7								112.5			
CZ004C1	Plzeň	175	19.7	1	19.4	20.2					123.8	1	121.3	123.3
CZ005C1	Ústí nad Labem	96	18.6	1	18.7	19.3					114.3	1	115.4	114.3
CZ006C1	Olomouc	111	18.6								122.9			
CZ007C1	Liberec	108	21.8	6	20.6	20.7	42	39.4	39.1		117.5	3	117.5	116.7
CZ008C1	České Budějovice	101	21.4	7	21.8	22.2	4	42.8	42.0		108.2	4	108.9	108.2
CZ009C1	Hradec Králové	97	26.8	3	22.3	23.3	2	52.5	47.3		122.4	3	122.2	121.5
CZ010C1	Pardubice	96	26.9	2	24.5	23.0	11	37.7	38.3		117.0	2	117.9	115.4
CZ011C1	Zlín	80	30.2	5	28.1	27.7	6	45.3	44.9		117.6	3	116.4	114.4
CZ012C1	Kladno	75	25.1	2	25.0	22.3	8	37.0	37.0		122.5	1	121.7	119.7
CZ013C1	Karlovy Vary	51	25.3	1	24.6	26.1	4	45.8	44.3		121.1	1	124.7	122.0
CZ014C1	Jihlava	53	16.9	1	13.8	16.4	2	34.2	30.7		117.8	2	114.6	117.8
CZ015C1	Haviřov	80	17.3	1	17.1	19.1	2	30.7	30.5		120.8	1	119.8	120.7
CZ016C1	Most	66	22.1	1	23.7	22.0	4	39.6	40.2		120.8	1	117.8	121.8
CZ017C1	Karviná	61	27.1	1	22.2	26.4	5	41.6	40.0		114.3	1	118.9	113.0
CZ018C2	Chomutov-Jirkov	70	20.4	4	20.0	20.3	1	34.2	36.5		109.8	3	114.1	110.1
DE001C1	Berlin	3 374	18.3	1	15.8	16.1	5	39.1	38.3		114.3	1	117.3	114.1
DE002C1	Hamburg	1 779	24.4	1	25.4	23.9	2	35.7	35.1		119.0	1	113.6	119.1
DE003C1	München	1 399	22.7				1	38.0	38.9		123.0			
DE004C1	Köln	1 027	17.9	1	20.7	18.6	4	33.8	35.0		117.0	1	112.4	116.0
DE005C1	Frankfurt am Main	720	16.1	1	16.1	16.5	1	35.6	30.2		120.4	1	118.1	120.4
DE006C1	Essen	584	15.6	1	16.2	16.9	2	26.1	28.6		118.8	1	119.0	119.7
DE007C1	Stuttgart	618	25.4	1	25.8	25.9	2	44.5	40.0		120.9	1	130.1	120.3
DE008C1	Leipzig	524	15.4	1	13.3	14.1	1	32.4	33.0		115.6	1	117.8	115.2
DE009C1	Dresden	547	24.9	1	21.9	25.3	2	32.9	35.7		119.9	1	121.3	120.0
DE010C1	Dortmund	600	24.6								115.1			
DE011C1	Düsseldorf	617	18.1	1	19.3	19.2					94.0	1	90.0	91.8
DE012C1	Bremen	576	26.4	1	25.8	25.6	1	29.2	38.7		115.9	1	122.3	116.3
DE013C1	Hannover	563	23.9								112.4			
DE014C1	Nürnberg	502	23.4								108.3			
DE015C1	Bochum	377	21.4	6	21.3	21.2	4	35.3	34.5		120.4	5	121.8	121.5
DE017C1	Bielefeld	344	18.2	4	19.4	19.7	3	32.9	31.9		117.9	3	117.6	116.4
DE018C1	Halle an der Saale	235	18.9	2	17.6	18.0	1	31.6	33.3		114.8	2	119.6	115.5
DE019C1	Magdeburg	231	16.6	2	14.4	14.7	2	18.7	21.9		115.6	2	114.0	115.4
DE020C1	Wiesbaden	285	17.6	2	17.2	17.3	1	31.0	29.1		124.2	2	130.6	124.1
DE021C1	Göttingen	122	18.0	1	20.1	18.2					115.1			
DE022C1	Mülheim a.d.Ruhr	169	13.6	1	14.1	15.4					117.9	1	118.3	117.6
DE023C1	Moers	112	14.9	1	12.9	15.2					114.0	1	103.9	113.8
DE025C1	Darmstadt	163	23.7	1	22.3	23.1	3	45.1	41.0		124.4	1	118.4	124.2
DE026C1	Trier	119	18.3				2	30.9	30.5		116.6			
DE027C1	Freiburg im Breisgau	225	17.6	1	15.7	18.6	1	36.4	34.8		123.0	1	123.8	123.5
DE028C1	Regensburg	155	21.1				1	35.3	32.1		117.7			
DE029C1	Frankfurt (Oder)	64	13.4	1	11.6	13.7	1	31.0	30.2		119.1	1	120.9	119.1
DE030C1	Weimar	67	13.7	1	15.4	15.3	2	24.6	24.6		120.0			
DE031C1	Schwerin	97	12.2				1	16.4	22.7		111.9			
DE032C1	Erfurt	204	15.8	2	15.2	15.2	3	26.1	27.0		119.8	2	120.8	119.4
DE033C1	Augsburg	302	21.7	2	20.0	21.5	2	30.9	33.3		121.7	2	123.9	121.9
DE034C1	Bonn	341	22.7	1	25.5	23.6	2	37.5	37.2		121.9			

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	NO ₂							O ₃			
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB
DE035C1	Karlsruhe	315	22.9	1	21.2	20.9	1	34.3	34.8	122.2	1	129.0	122.7
DE036C1	Mönchengladbach	268	22.7	1	21.4	23.2	2	31.3	34.0	117.5	1	120.2	117.9
DE037C1	Mainz	206	25.1	3	25.2	26.2	22	35.1	35.8	123.4	1	117.8	120.3
DE039C1	Kiel	265	15.6	1	13.0	14.0	2	43.7	38.3	101.9	1	98.0	101.7
DE040C1	Saarbrücken	197	18.6	3	20.8	17.8	1	34.5	32.3	120.2	3	111.0	120.4
DE041C1	Potsdam	166	15.2	2	13.8	13.3	2	29.3	30.6	121.1	2	116.6	122.1
DE042C1	Koblenz	126	24.1	4	25.1	24.4	6	32.3	32.7	119.3			
DE043C1	Rostock	208	13.6	1	12.4	9.4	2	29.5	28.1	104.7	1	100.2	105.9
DE044C1	Kaiserslautern	99	17.9	1	19.5	19.2				120.3	1	119.1	120.0
DE045C1	Iserlohn	102	15.9							120.9			
DE046C1	Esslingen am Neckar	103	23.1				1	39.1	40.2	122.6			
DE047C1	Hanau	100	24.0	1	24.3	24.6				121.2	1	121.9	121.1
DE048C1	Wilhelmshaven	80	16.2							107.4			
DE049C1	Ludwigsburg	97	22.8	1	22.1	22.4	1	45.9	40.4	122.5	1	123.8	122.5
DE050C1	Tübingen	89	18.7	1	19.3	20.2	1	39.2	38.0	122.1	1	118.0	122.1
DE051C1	Villingen-Schwenningen	86	14.9	1	14.2	13.7				119.7	1	115.2	119.3
DE052C1	Flensburg	90	14.1				1	27.2	28.1	104.2			
DE053C1	Marburg	77	19.3	1	21.0	20.9	2	32.3	34.6	119.2	1	121.9	118.8
DE054C1	Konstanz	79	18.4	1	19.0	19.3				124.2	1	121.7	123.1
DE055C1	Neumünster	81	16.0							104.1			
DE056C1	Brandenburg an der Havel	75	12.8	1	12.1	12.9	1	23.5	26.3	120.2	1	118.3	119.3
DE057C1	Gießen	86	23.4	1	24.1	23.8	1	40.2	39.3	119.5			
DE058C1	Lüneburg	82	14.2	1	14.5	13.6				117.9	1	119.5	118.2
DE059C1	Bayreuth	75	17.2				1	27.2	26.8	117.5			
DE060C1	Celle	70	14.8							120.7			
DE061C1	Aschaffenburg	83	21.2	1	25.0	21.6				121.2	1	120.8	120.7
DE062C1	Bamberg	79	19.0	1	20.9	19.8				119.9			
DE063C1	Plauen	67	14.8				1	20.6	23.1	116.7	1	113.2	116.3
DE064C1	Neubrandenburg	66	11.5				2	21.4	22.0	111.4			
DE065C1	Fulda	84	18.6	1	19.7	19.2	1	37.9	36.2	117.3	1	118.7	116.8
DE066C1	Kempten (Allgäu)	71	19.0	1	19.4	20.1				117.1	1	123.3	117.1
DE067C1	Landshut	74	19.7				1	24.3	27.8	120.4			
DE068C1	Sindelfingen	70	20.7				1	37.6	38.2	121.0			
DE069C1	Rosenheim	64	20.2							117.9			
DE070C1	Frankenthal (Pfalz)	55	24.1				1	28.3	32.7	118.5			
DE071C1	Stralsund	58	10.7				1	17.4	18.1	104.8			
DE072C1	Friedrichshafen	60	18.3	1	20.9	19.2				121.5	1	116.9	121.3
DE073C1	Offenburg	64	18.6							123.1			
DE074C1	Görlitz	63	13.7				1	21.2	25.6	117.0			
DE075C1	Sankt Augustin	67	21.6							123.4			
DE076C1	Neu-Ulm	58	21.6	1	27.4	23.3				120.7	1	123.5	120.1
DE077C1	Schweinfurt	64	18.9	1	20.9	19.4				117.7	1	115.6	117.5
DE078C1	Greifswald	56	11.6							106.4			
DE079C1	Wetzlar	58	22.3	2	23.7	22.7				120.4	1	104.1	119.5
DE080C1	Speyer	60	23.6	1	27.9	22.4	1	26.0	30.8	122.9	1	121.5	122.9
DE081C1	Passau	50	19.8	1	29.2	22.3				121.9			
DE082C1	Dessau-Roßlau	88	13.3				1	16.2	22.6	122.0			
DE501C1	Duisburg	495	26.4	1	25.8	26.7	3	35.9	36.0	113.8			
DE502C1	Mannheim	303	27.3				2	39.7	38.1	118.5			
DE503C1	Gelsenkirchen	281	24.9	1	22.5	21.0	2	36.7	36.8	122.0			
DE504C1	Münster	291	17.8	1	15.7	18.3	2	33.0	33.9	123.1	1	124.2	123.2
DE505C1	Chemnitz	249	17.0	1	12.2	12.8	1	33.0	29.4	118.6	1	120.8	118.5
DE506C1	Braunschweig	250	15.9	1	12.1	11.7	2	30.0	30.5	116.1	1	115.6	115.6
DE507C1	Aachen	251	16.9	1	9.7	14.2	3	35.4	34.2	116.8	1	116.0	117.0
DE508C1	Krefeld	229	24.6				2	33.2	34.5	116.9	1	125.6	117.1
DE509C1	Oberhausen	211	26.9				2	42.0	39.4	119.7			

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	NO ₂							O ₃			
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB
DE510C1	Lübeck	237	15.6	1	13.6	14.4	2	27.4	29.6	105.8	1	111.5	106.4
DE511C1	Hagen	199	18.6				2	44.6	38.9	121.6			
DE513C1	Kassel	209	19.0	1	20.0	19.5	1	38.3	38.4	117.4	1	120.3	117.4
DE514C1	Hamm	182	18.8				1	33.0	34.3	119.5			
DE515C1	Herne	158	24.3				1	38.9	37.2	122.2			
DE516C1	Solingen	177	20.0	1	17.6	20.6	1	34.3	36.5	120.9	1	117.3	120.9
DE517C1	Osnabrück	176	17.5	1	16.4	18.4	2	41.1	39.0	122.2	1	124.0	122.3
DE518C1	Ludwigshafen am Rhein	163	28.0	1	21.7	25.7	4	37.3	37.7	118.8	1	119.1	118.0
DE519C1	Leverkusen	167	22.1	1	22.4	23.6	1	38.3	37.0	119.3	1	119.1	120.0
DE520C1	Oldenburg (Oldenburg)	169	17.8				1	38.9	37.4	110.4			
DE521C1	Neuss	156	25.7	1	30.4	27.3	3	38.0	38.2	115.7			
DE522C1	Heidelberg	172	21.9	1	21.2	21.3	1	33.9	33.5	120.9	1	119.0	120.0
DE523C1	Paderborn	145	16.4				3	37.5	35.8	115.3			
DE524C1	Würzburg	146	20.9				1	30.5	33.7	117.8	1	116.2	117.7
DE525C1	Recklinghausen	127	22.1				1	34.6	36.4	122.8			
DE526C1	Wolfsburg	124	14.1	1	15.4	13.9	1	28.5	29.8	119.1	1	119.3	118.8
DE527C1	Bremerhaven	117	17.3	1	19.6	17.8	1	33.1	31.5	108.1	1	106.8	108.8
DE528C1	Boitrop	118	25.5				1	34.3	37.7	120.9			
DE529C1	Heilbronn	123	23.5	1	23.6	20.5	1	47.4	40.3	120.6	1	122.7	120.2
DE530C1	Remscheid	112	17.5				1	31.0	35.0	122.7			
DE531C1	Offenbach am Main	127	27.6				4	40.8	41.6	120.9			
DE532C1	Ulm	126	22.1	1	23.8	24.0	1	38.4	37.7	121.5	1	117.5	121.5
DE533C1	Pforzheim	130	21.0	1	23.2	20.2	1	33.0	35.4	121.6	1	114.2	121.5
DE534C1	Ingolstadt	133	20.9				1	22.9	28.4	119.2			
DE535C1	Gera	100	15.0	1	16.9	16.5	2	27.8	26.2	119.3	1	118.2	119.0
DE536C1	Salzgitter	105	13.2							115.1			
DE537C1	Reutlingen	121	20.7	1	23.3	21.2	1	46.0	40.4	122.2	1	117.8	122.7
DE538C1	Fürth	119	22.7							119.2			
DE539C1	Cottbus	101	14.1	1	11.9	13.9	1	25.8	29.0	119.6	1	121.4	119.6
DE540C1	Siegen	109	18.7				1	37.8	37.6	122.5			
DE541C1	Bergisch Gladbach	121	19.8							120.4			
DE542C1	Hildesheim	105	15.7				2	33.0	33.1	113.7			
DE543C1	Witten	105	19.8				1	38.1	37.5	122.3			
DE544C1	Zwickau	106	15.4				1	21.5	24.9	119.2			
DE545C1	Erlangen	112	19.9	1	15.7	16.0				119.6	1	126.1	119.5
DE546C1	Wuppertal	355	20.0	1	20.0	19.2	1	43.0	37.2	122.1	1	121.2	122.4
DE547C1	Jena	107	14.8	1	14.6	15.2	1	25.2	25.5	120.3	1	121.0	120.7
DE548C1	Düren, Stadt	99	19.2				1	39.5	35.4	116.8			
DE549C1	Bocholt, Stadt	73	18.7							119.1			
DK001C1	København	668	16.0	1	11.9	14.8	2	28.4	27.6	103.1	1	111.7	103.1
DK002C1	Århus	312	10.5	1	11.4	13.4	1	22.8	23.8	102.1	1	101.2	103.0
DK003C1	Odense	193	10.3	1	9.9	11.8	1	14.6	21.5	103.6	1	109.3	103.7
DK004C2	Aalborg	200	9.6	1	10.2	13.5				100.2	1	96.9	100.2
EE001C1	Tallinn	405	10.9	1	8.4	12.3	1	16.1	16.6	99.5	1	98.8	99.8
EE002C2	Tartu linn	105	10.1	1	9.9	11.1				102.7	1	107.8	102.7
EE003C1	Narva linn	59	10.4	1	7.7	11.2				99.2	1	99.8	99.2
EL001K1	Athens	3 313	29.3	4	20.5	22.9	4	45.5	47.7	113.7	4	129.7	116.9
EL002K1	Thessaloniki	789	29.5				1	23.6	34.2	94.6			
EL003C1	Patra	172	18.7				1	31.2	28.0	114.6			
EL004C1	Iraklio	156	18.3							120.5			
EL005C1	Larissa	142	22.4							110.1			
EL006C1	Volos	102	20.0							102.5			
EL007C1	Ioannina	76	18.8							115.7			
EL008C1	Kavala	56	14.9							96.1			
EL009C1	Kalamata	54	12.6							114.1			
EL010C1	Trikala	62	18.0							109.9			

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	
EL011C1	Serres	60	21.8								102.1			
EL012C1	Katerini	61	18.1								102.9			
EL013C1	Xanthi	57	16.6								98.4			
EL014C1	Chania	66	12.7								115.7			
ES001C1	Madrid	3 230	35.2	15	31.0	31.9	9	40.5	41.6	117.7	11	117.8	119.0	
ES002C1	Barcelona	1 637	37.2	6	28.1	31.5	2	46.5	44.9	102.7	4	109.3	103.0	
ES003C1	Valencia	909	25.4	2	20.2	22.2	5	27.0	27.1	106.1	2	109.6	106.0	
ES004C1	Sevilla	712	22.0	4	18.9	20.0	2	33.1	34.1	116.5	3	117.0	116.2	
ES005C1	Zaragoza	699	21.9	2	24.2	20.7	5	22.9	23.4	108.6	2	108.8	108.3	
ES006C1	Málaga	573	22.7	2	22.2	20.9	1	35.8	31.6	114.0	2	111.2	113.2	
ES007C1	Murcia	465	17.2				1	38.1	30.0	110.9				
ES008C1	Palmas de Gran Canaria, Las													
ES009C1	Valladolid	336	16.9				4	19.9	18.6	115.3				
ES010C1	Palma de Mallorca	424	19.5				1	32.1	26.4	109.0				
ES011C1	Santiago de Compostela	116	14.1	1	10.2	12.8	1	18.2	20.0	91.9	1	101.3	91.3	
ES012C1	Vitoria-Gasteiz	242	20.1				3	18.6	23.0	104.7				
ES013C1	Oviedo	228	20.3	1	12.5	16.3	2	27.8	25.8	93.7	1	103.4	93.5	
ES014C1	Pamplona/ Iruña	268	19.0	2	20.0	20.1	1	28.1	25.6	101.1	1	88.8	101.2	
ES015C1	Santander	183	17.5	1	13.0	15.5	1	28.4	24.0	92.4	1	101.5	92.4	
ES016C1	Toledo	90	15.9	1	19.3	17.2				119.3	1	116.9	119.3	
ES017C1	Badajoz	152	13.9	1	8.2	10.1				112.8	1	114.1	110.0	
ES018C1	Logroño	155	18.2	1	18.8	19.6				103.5	1	90.4	104.2	
ES019C1	Bilbao	358	22.5	1	23.0	19.1	2	31.9	26.3	92.7	1	86.1	93.0	
ES020C1	Córdoba	331	17.2	2	13.9	15.9	1	29.8	28.7	120.1	2	121.1	120.6	
ES021C1	Alicante/Alacant	342	18.5	1	19.4	18.2	1	23.0	21.9	114.8	1	110.0	113.6	
ES022C1	Vigo	303	19.8				2	23.5	23.2	85.9				
ES023C1	Gijón	278	22.3	2	17.7	16.5	4	24.6	25.0	94.7	1	96.1	93.8	
ES024C1	Hospitalet de Llobregat, L'	256	36.7	1	33.3	38.8				103.4				
ES025C1	Santa Cruz de Tenerife													
ES026C1	Coruña, A	261	17.2	1	13.3	14.8	1	25.8	20.2	91.6	1	98.4	91.7	
ES027C1	Barakaldo	123	22.0	1	23.4	24.1				93.2				
ES028C1	Reus	112	19.3				1	17.5	18.8	110.8				
ES029C1	Telde													
ES030C1	Parla	123	26.2							119.9				
ES031C1	Lugo	100	13.7				1	12.2	15.2	93.2				
ES032C1	San Fernando	97	14.4	1	11.5	14.5				114.8	1	111.0	114.8	
ES033C1	Girona	110	20.8				1	26.4	27.3	121.5				
ES034C1	Cáceres	96	13.0	1	6.3	7.4				116.2	1	123.9	116.2	
ES035C1	Torreveja	92	14.2				1	11.6	17.7	118.2				
ES036C1	Pozuelo de Alarcón	83	23.1							120.0				
ES037C1	Puerto de Santa María, El	95	14.7							112.0				
ES038C1	Coslada	113	30.7				1	39.3	31.8	119.4				
ES039C1	Avilés	96	16.8				2	20.8	21.1	89.9				
ES040C1	Talavera de la Reina	88	18.9	1	15.9	13.1				120.5	1	124.1	120.5	
ES041C1	Palencia	81	13.1				1	6.9	11.3	114.6				
ES042C1	Sant Boi de Llobregat	89	27.1							104.4				
ES043C1	Ferrol	96	13.2				1	12.6	16.2	92.1				
ES044C1	Pontevedra	99	15.7				1	18.1	20.0	92.4				
ES045C1	Ceuta	84	16.9	1	29.8					112.8	1	114.2	112.8	
ES046C1	Gandia	88	14.8				1	10.8	19.1	111.6				
ES047C1	Rozas de Madrid, Las	91	18.4							126.3				
ES048C1	Guadalajara	87	15.4	1	14.3	17.2				124.6	1	119.8	124.5	
ES049C1	Sant Cugat del Vallès	85	24.1	1	24.8	26.4				111.6	1	101.6	111.6	
ES050C1	Manresa	91	21.5				1	26.4	25.9	120.5				
ES051C1	Getxo	113	18.7							96.2				
ES052C1	Rubí	77	26.2	1	23.4	22.2				111.9	1	116.1	111.6	

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	
ES053C1	Ciudad Real	76	17.5	1	15.5	12.4					119.1	1	117.1	119.1
ES054C1	Benidorm	83	13.1	1	8.2	9.2					114.8	1	109.3	114.7
ES055C1	Melilla	81	16.4								103.7			
ES056C1	Viladecans	98	24.9	1	25.3	26.3					110.2	1	106.5	108.1
ES057C1	Ponferrada	71	14.8								99.9			
ES058C1	San Sebastián de los Reyes	87	25.1								125.9			
ES059C1	Zamora	65	13.8				1	9.0	13.7		114.5			
ES060C1	Fuengirola	83	17.7								116.1			
ES061C1	Cerdanyola del Vallès	83	28.7								107.7			
ES062C1	Sanlúcar de Barrameda	68	15.0								111.0			
ES063C1	Vilanova i la Geltrú	90	18.2				1	17.4	21.2		113.5			
ES064C1	Prat de Llobregat, El	63	28.7	2	32.5	27.7					107.6	1	101.6	108.1
ES065C1	Línea de la Concepción, La	71	21.1								97.2			
ES066C1	Cornellà de Llobregat	99	30.5								104.4			
ES067C1	Majadahonda	76	20.0	1	22.4	19.6					121.9	1	118.3	121.7
ES068C1	Torremolinos	66	18.2								120.4			
ES069C1	Castelldefels	65	20.8								116.3			
ES070C1	Irun	64	13.2								97.7			
ES071C1	Granollers	87	27.1				1	34.6	33.4		114.3			
ES072C1	Arrecife													
ES073C1	Elda	78	15.4	1	5.9	8.9					116.7	1	120.4	116.7
ES074C1	Santa Lucía de Tirajana													
ES075C1	Mollet del Vallès	56	27.6				1	38.5	35.5		112.2			
ES501C1	Granada	272	25.0				1	42.7	37.3		118.9	1	111.8	120.2
ES503C1	Badalona	234	32.5	1	33.3	30.0					112.5	1	108.1	116.3
ES504C1	Móstoles	214	27.0	1	25.8	27.1					120.6	1	122.4	120.4
ES505C1	Elche/Elx	239	18.0	1	12.3	11.5	1	16.1	19.1		113.9	1	117.6	113.2
ES506C1	Cartagena	227	13.7	1	16.5	14.5					109.4	1	112.9	109.0
ES507C1	Sabadell	222	29.1				1	34.1	35.4		112.6			
ES508C1	Jerez de la Frontera	222	15.9	1	14.5	15.9					110.2	1	115.3	108.3
ES509C1	Fuenlabrada	189	27.8								120.0			
ES510C1	Donostia/San Sebastián	235	15.1				2	21.6	21.3		99.4	1	96.5	98.9
ES511C1	Alcalá de Henares	203	23.6				1	28.4	26.1		126.4			
ES512C1	Terrassa	227	27.5				1	36.5	34.4		115.1			
ES513C1	Leganés	199	30.9				1	35.5	34.1		117.0			
ES514C1	Almería	198	16.8	1	11.7	11.6	1	24.2	23.1		118.8	1	116.5	121.4
ES515C1	Burgos	180	14.7				1	13.2	17.2		111.3			
ES516C1	Salamanca	162	15.1	1	9.1	10.0	1	12.1	14.4		117.0	1	116.0	116.9
ES517C1	Alcorcón	170	29.2	1	29.9	25.2					120.5	1	127.1	120.4
ES518C1	Getafe	164	30.4				1	33.1	31.9		119.6			
ES519C1	Albacete	172	18.0	1	13.5	11.8					111.2	1	107.3	111.1
ES520C1	Castellón/Castelló de la Pl.	187	20.2				1	18.3	23.0		112.2			
ES521C1	Huelva	156	17.1				1	14.2	20.1		113.9			
ES522C1	Cádiz	124	15.5				1	12.0	17.6		113.7			
ES523C1	León	158	16.9	1	14.0	13.0	1	24.1	22.2		110.6	1	107.6	110.9
ES524C1	San Cristóbal de La Laguna													
ES525C1	Tarragona	141	17.9	1	21.6	23.1					110.8	1	113.0	110.6
ES526C1	Santa Coloma de Gramenet	134	35.4	1	33.1	36.3					107.5			
ES527C1	Jaén	118	18.1	2	14.1	14.6					120.6	2	123.7	120.5
ES528C1	Lleida	142	19.6				1	20.6	22.1		110.2			
ES529C1	Ourense	113	17.2				1	24.8	21.9		91.3			
ES530C1	Mataró	129	24.5	1	22.7	25.4					117.0	1	118.1	116.2
ES531C1	Dos Hermanas	129	17.6	1	14.7	16.7					116.5	1	116.8	116.6
ES532C1	Algeciras	120	20.2								98.3			
ES533C1	Marbella	141	15.1				1	26.9	24.4		117.0			
ES534C1	Torrejón de Ardoz	124	26.6	1	28.8	23.1					121.8	1	129.3	119.4

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB
ES535C1	Alcobendas	105	27.4				1	26.6	29.0	125.1			
ES536C1	Alcalá de Guadaíra	79	16.5	1	17.0	16.4				116.2	1	116.8	115.9
ES537C1	Alcoy/Alcoi	61	12.7	1	8.5	13.8				114.6	1	106.6	114.6
ES538C1	Ávila	59	11.3	1	5.4	9.2				120.7	1	119.1	120.6
ES539C1	Benalmádena	63	16.4							118.8			
ES540C1	Chiclana de la Frontera	82	11.7							109.2			
ES541C1	Collado Villalba	63	14.9				1	27.1	22.0	124.2			
ES542C1	Cuenca	57	20.3	1	33.6	22.0				111.1	1	103.8	111.0
ES543C1	Eivissa	55	12.2							110.2			
ES544C1	Linares	61	16.5							120.3			
ES545C1	Lorca	93	13.4							111.3			
ES546C1	Mérida	64	11.7	1	9.1	11.2				113.6	1	114.5	113.7
ES547C1	Sagunto/Sagunt	76	15.8	1	13.1	15.2	1	15.5	16.8	116.1	1	108.5	113.1
ES548C1	Torrelavega	61	15.9	2	15.6	14.4	1	27.5	24.7	87.8	1	86.6	87.8
ES549C1	Valdemoro	74	21.0	1	21.8	22.3				121.5	1	118.6	121.4
ES550C1	Puerto de la Cruz												
ES551C1	Paterna	118	20.2	1	16.9	15.4				107.3	1	109.0	112.2
ES552C1	Igualada	54	19.4							118.5			
ES553C1	Torrent	91	18.7							110.0			
ES554C1	Mislata	66	26.5							106.0			
ES555C1	Rivas-Vaciamadrid	80	23.4	1	29.1	27.0				121.4	1	129.6	119.4
ES556C1	Santurtzi	75	20.6							94.5			
ES557C1	Esplugues de Llobregat	61	31.0							104.4			
ES558C1	San Vicente del Raspeig	55	16.6							112.0			
FI001C2	Helsinki	575	14.0	2	12.8	13.7	2	27.0	21.8	96.6	2	96.6	97.7
FI002C1	Tampere	219	10.4	1	9.9	11.9	1	13.1	17.2	98.5	1	101.6	98.5
FI003C1	Turku	183	10.9							98.7			
FI004C3	Oulu	188	8.0	1	10.3	10.5	1	19.2	18.4	92.1	1	90.4	91.1
FI005C1	Espoo	254	11.2				1	19.6	22.7	96.8			
FI006C1	Vantaa	207	13.2				1	19.2	22.6	96.2			
FI007C2	Lahti	120	9.9	1	7.4	9.6				99.3	1	95.3	98.9
FI008C3	Kuopio	114	7.7				2	12.8	14.9	97.3			
FI009C1	Jyväskylä	133	8.7	1	6.7	7.9	1	16.8	18.8	97.2			
FR001P1	City of Paris	7 194	32.0	16	28.8	29.6	9	52.6	53.6	103.3	7	108.1	104.4
FR003C2	City of Lyon	1 038	25.6	3	24.8	23.5	4	45.9	43.4	119.7	3	120.2	119.5
FR004C2	City of Toulouse	597	17.9	3	17.6	17.9	2	40.4	35.5	117.7	3	119.7	117.9
FR006C2	City of Strasbourg	405	22.6	3	19.6	20.4	2	42.2	41.1	121.4	1	127.6	121.3
FR007C1	City of Bordeaux	617	16.2	2	14.4	17.1	3	27.6	29.0	112.6	2	114.3	113.1
FR008C1	City of Nantes	443	13.5	2	13.2	13.8	1	30.8	29.9	107.0	1	112.8	108.2
FR009C1	City of Lille	907	20.9	1	22.5	22.9	2	29.3	30.6	100.7	2	104.2	100.7
FR010C1	City of Montpellier	287	21.0	2	22.6	20.1	2	33.1	33.6	120.2	1	112.9	119.8
FR011C1	City of Saint-Étienne	207	17.7	1	16.8	18.1	1	32.6	32.5	122.2	1	122.1	122.4
FR012C1	City of Le Havre	203	16.2	2	15.0	15.0	1	32.9	30.3	98.1	2	95.5	98.9
FR013C2	City of Rennes	218	15.7	1	15.2	15.1	2	24.6	27.0	101.2	1	100.3	101.1
FR014C2	City of Amiens	146	16.6	1	15.7	15.8				105.1	1	104.2	105.0
FR016C1	City of Nancy	232	18.5	1	18.0	19.3	2	23.8	26.6	118.6	1	118.6	118.7
FR017C2	City of Metz	179	18.7	2	18.1	18.1	1	28.6	30.9	118.9	1	119.9	119.0
FR018C1	City of Reims	208	17.7	2	14.6	14.3	1	40.7	35.5	110.3	2	111.1	110.8
FR019C1	City of Orléans	221	13.8	2	9.3	9.4	1	27.9	30.4	116.7	1	118.5	118.1
FR020C2	City of Dijon	203	17.2	2	17.6	16.7	1	20.6	24.3	119.1	1	120.7	119.0
FR021C2	City of Poitiers	105	13.7	2	14.8	13.7	1	33.8	27.9	108.5	2	106.6	108.5
FR022C2	City of Clermont-Ferrand	203	18.1	4	14.8	14.6	3	31.5	31.3	118.5	4	120.0	118.4
FR023C2	City of Caen	163	15.7	2	14.0	14.1	1	25.0	27.2	96.4	2	95.8	96.3
FR024C2	City of Limoges	161	14.4	1	15.8	14.8	1	27.3	26.8	107.1	1	107.2	107.0
FR025C1	City of Besançon	124	16.5	1	16.9	16.4	1	22.4	26.5	119.9	1	122.1	120.0
FR026C2	City of Grenoble	313	22.9	2	20.3	21.1	2	39.5	38.6	120.9	2	125.0	120.7

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB
FR028C1	City of Saint-Denis												
FR030C1	City of Fort-de-France												
FR032C2	City of Toulon	335	18.5	2	20.1	19.2	1	38.1	33.3	119.9	1	119.7	119.2
FR034C2	City of Valenciennes	128	17.3	1	17.4	17.2	1	31.5	27.9	106.0	1	99.0	106.6
FR035C2	City of Tours	248	13.2	2	11.3	11.4	1	28.5	28.1	113.7	1	115.2	113.6
FR036C2	City of Angers	185	12.4	2	11.6	12.2				111.8	1	115.3	111.3
FR037C1	City of Brest	149	10.3	1	11.2	9.5	1	26.7	25.8	99.1	1	96.8	99.1
FR038C2	City of Le Mans	163	12.6	2	11.9	12.2				110.5	1	115.0	110.5
FR039C2	City of Avignon	113	17.7	2	16.2	16.4	1	24.4	28.4	128.0	1	134.8	128.4
FR040C2	City of Mulhouse	196	21.0	2	20.1	19.6	1	34.2	33.2	122.1	1	123.6	121.5
FR042C1	City of Dunkerque	150	17.8	1	17.7	18.3				96.4	1	95.1	96.9
FR043C2	City of Perpignan	134	16.1	2	14.9	16.1				112.8	1	116.2	112.9
FR044C2	City of Nîmes	151	17.1	1	15.4	16.2	1	31.7	32.2	123.4	1	122.2	122.1
FR045C2	City of Pau	125	15.3	1	11.6	12.4	1	25.8	25.9	106.6	1	108.1	106.8
FR046C2	City of Bayonne	116	13.0	2	13.5	12.1	1	24.0	23.1	102.7	2	105.2	103.4
FR047C2	City of Annemasse	62	20.1	2	18.3	20.4	1	26.3	29.8	119.4	2	124.6	119.1
FR048C1	City of Annecy	128	19.4	2	19.0	19.7	1	32.9	32.7	120.6	2	126.2	120.2
FR049C2	City of Lorient	83	10.4	2	9.3	8.6				99.4	1	98.1	99.3
FR051C2	City of Troyes	112	15.6	2	14.2	14.3				113.6	1	111.3	113.6
FR052C2	City of Saint-Nazaire	72	9.9	2	9.1	9.9				105.4	1	104.1	107.1
FR053C1	City of La Rochelle	91	11.6	1	16.8	11.5				105.7	1	99.2	105.2
FR057C2	City of Boulogne-sur-Mer	81	14.6	1	10.2	8.7				97.3	1	99.5	102.0
FR058C2	City of Chambéry	95	18.5	2	17.5	18.3	1	28.7	32.7	122.4	2	124.4	122.4
FR060C2	City of Chartres	84	12.9				1	19.5	25.4	116.2	1	116.5	116.1
FR062C1	City of Calais	81	15.3	1	14.4	14.0				93.5	1	96.9	94.0
FR063C2	City of Béziers	79	14.4							111.9			
FR064C2	City of Arras	77	15.2	1	15.4	14.4				105.2	1	108.7	105.3
FR065C2	City of Bourges	73	10.8	1	10.1	10.8	1	14.0	19.5	113.1	1	110.9	113.1
FR066C1	City of Saint-Brieuc	76	10.7	1	11.1	10.4				99.1	1	95.2	99.0
FR069C1	C. of Cherbourg-en-Cotentin	85	10.7	1	13.0	12.1				96.5	1	94.2	96.0
FR076C2	City of Belfort	70	16.2				1	22.6	25.2	120.3			
FR077C1	City of Roanne	57	16.6	1	17.7	16.6				118.5	1	115.9	118.5
FR079C2	City of Saint-Quentin	63	16.4	1	18.0	16.3				107.0	1	102.6	106.8
FR084C1	City of Creil	77	18.6	2	20.1	19.0				115.5	2	115.7	115.5
FR099C1	City of Fréjus	88	14.9	1	9.7	13.7				124.9	1	124.7	124.4
FR202C1	City of Aix-en-Provence	152	21.2	1	22.6	21.5	1	39.2	35.1	128.6	1	130.6	130.2
FR203C1	City of Marseille	894	25.3	2	29.4	26.3	1	44.9	40.2	120.8	1	116.4	120.5
FR205C2	City of Nice	710	25.5	3	26.6	24.5	1	37.8	37.2	120.7	4	122.6	120.6
FR207C1	City of Lens	202	15.8							104.5			
FR209C2	City of Douai	99	15.6	1	15.9	16.1				106.4	1	110.3	105.9
FR214C1	City of Valence	96	17.1	1	20.2	17.0	1	30.8	31.0	126.5	1	117.0	126.5
FR215C2	City of Rouen	334	18.5	3	19.3	18.7	2	42.7	39.4	103.8	3	103.8	104.7
FR304C1	City of Melun	90	19.1	1	18.5	17.7	1	39.0	35.8	116.7	1	107.4	117.2
FR305C1	City of Meaux	67	18.1							114.6			
FR306C1	City of Mantes-la-Jolie	88	17.8	1	19.1	16.3				112.7	1	110.9	112.6
FR324C1	City of Martigues	67	16.8	1	15.8	17.2				123.3	1	132.9	122.4
FR506C1	City of Colmar	75	21.4	1	25.2	21.4				122.2	1	125.5	122.2
FR520C1	City of Les Abymes												
FR521C1	City of Cayenne												
FR522C1	City of Mamoudzou												
HR001C1	Zagreb	797	22.6	1	27.7	22.0	1	40.6	36.0	116.3	1	117.1	116.2
HR002C1	Rijeka	138	16.8	1	14.0	17.7				116.2	1	115.6	113.9
HR003C1	Slavonski Brod	67	18.1							116.7	1	114.1	117.7
HR004C1	Osijek	109	18.0				1	25.7	26.2	111.2			
HR005C1	Split	184	16.3				1	23.7	23.8	121.4			
HR006C1	Pula	59	12.7	1	9.1	11.2				122.4	1	131.5	122.5

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	
HR007C1	Zadar	76	13.8								116.9			
HU001C1	Budapest	1 775	27.2	3	23.9	20.6	2	40.7	39.6	106.2	3	103.3	106.5	
HU002C1	Miskolc	173	15.7				1	32.2	28.8	109.5				
HU003C1	Nyíregyháza	122	17.3				1	23.5	27.2	105.8				
HU004C1	Pécs	162	15.9	1	16.9	17.1	1	43.3	34.3	106.7	1	84.0	106.7	
HU005C1	Debrecen	213	20.1	1	20.2	19.5				106.0	1	110.4	105.4	
HU006C1	Szeged	171	17.7	1	15.3	19.1				105.9				
HU007C1	Győr	132	15.1							113.9	1	104.1	113.7	
HU008C1	Kecskemét	114	16.2							106.1				
HU009C1	Székesfehérvár	101	16.6							110.7				
HU010C1	Szombathely	81	15.1							118.1				
HU011C1	Szolnok	74	16.7							106.5				
HU012C1	Tatabánya	70	14.6				1	16.5	21.8	110.0				
HU013C1	Veszprém	62	15.6	1	19.3	16.1				107.7	1	120.6	107.6	
HU014C1	Békéscsaba	62	18.6							102.7				
HU015C1	Kaposvár	67	15.4							105.6				
HU016C1	Eger	57	16.3							106.4				
HU017C1	Dunaújváros	49	16.6							108.7				
HU018C1	Zalaegerszeg	61	13.8							115.5				
HU019C1	Sopron	65	13.6							121.2				
IE001C1	Dublin	561	21.7	2	18.3	20.8	3	35.3	37.0	121.1	2	126.5	123.0	
IE002C1	Cork	129	25.2	1	35.2	23.5				118.3	1	109.4	118.3	
IE003C1	Limerick	63	22.7	1	23.0	22.0	1	43.9	39.5	121.5	1	114.0	121.1	
IE004C1	Galway	73	19.3	1	17.9	18.1	1	33.0	33.4	120.7	1	121.8	120.6	
IE005C1	Waterford	51	20.3	1	17.1	19.0	1	32.1	32.5	121.9	1	127.0	122.3	
IS001C1	Reykjavik	202	17.4	1	15.1	17.2				123.5	1	122.7	123.7	
IT001C1	Roma	2 747	18.1				1	33.3	33.0	119.9				
IT002C1	Milano	1 370	20.2				1	35.3	34.9	125.3				
IT003C1	Napoli	1 159	21.4	2	22.3	21.8				142.8	2	154.5	143.7	
IT004C1	Torino	921	17.6							123.3				
IT005C1	Palermo	677	17.7							124.8				
IT006C1	Genova	610	17.5							126.8				
IT007C1	Firenze	387	20.9	2	20.6	19.6	3	31.7	34.2	83.0	2	82.5	82.9	
IT008C1	Bari	347	12.1	1	9.6	12.0	1	21.0	24.7	92.7	1	91.5	92.0	
IT009C1	Bologna	408	14.5							91.4				
IT010C1	Catania	346	11.4							95.9				
IT011C1	Venezia	251	9.1							89.6				
IT012C1	Verona	282	12.9	1	11.1	12.2	1	22.3	24.7	90.6				
IT013C1	Cremona	77	31.3	7	32.4	32.0	4	51.1	47.2	108.6	8	110.4	109.1	
IT014C1	Trento	119	42.3	1	37.0	40.6	4	45.5	48.1	141.5	1	133.6	140.7	
IT015C1	Trieste	205	28.9	2	17.1	23.0	5	45.2	42.7	111.8	2	100.4	113.1	
IT016C1	Perugia	176	36.7	2	35.2	36.6	2	56.6	51.8	138.1	2	139.1	137.7	
IT017C1	Ancona	104	20.0	1	15.8	16.9	2	47.5	41.9	107.8	1	111.9	107.2	
IT019C1	Pescara	128	21.9	3	19.4	20.2	5	46.0	41.5	119.0	3	120.7	120.7	
IT020C1	Campobasso	53	25.1	1	20.8	22.2	2	46.0	41.2	118.9				
IT021C1	Caserta	89	18.3	3	20.2	19.7	2	36.5	32.6	112.6	2	111.1	112.2	
IT022C1	Taranto	211	16.8	2	9.4	10.6	1	24.0	24.8	115.5	2	113.2	116.0	
IT023C1	Potenza	68	15.1							122.3				
IT024C1	Catanzaro	93	12.1	1	10.4	12.0	1	20.8	21.3	112.0	1	114.2	112.1	
IT025C1	Reggio di Calabria	186	12.8	1	14.2	14.9	1	19.3	24.7	101.9	1	76.1	101.8	
IT026C1	Sassari	126	9.8	1	10.6	9.6	1	23.0	24.6	98.4	1	105.0	96.4	
IT027C1	Cagliari	172	13.7				1	26.4	28.4	95.6				
IT028C1	Padova	253	29.6	1	31.6	27.7	1	37.5	37.0	133.6	1	130.4	134.1	
IT029C1	Brescia	218	31.9	1	29.0	30.7	2	45.0	43.0	143.9	1	133.2	143.6	
IT030C1	Modena	188	23.2	1	24.2	25.3	1	40.7	37.6	136.7	1	135.6	136.9	
IT031C1	Foggia	154	19.9	1	20.2	22.4				120.7				

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IT032C1	Salerno	145	24.9	2	29.1	25.7	1	36.7	31.6	115.7	2	106.4	115.3
IT033C1	Piacenza	105	25.8	1	23.3	24.6	1	32.9	32.3	138.9	1	147.0	138.9
IT034C1	Bolzano	106	26.5	1	28.0	26.5	2	37.6	36.6	128.1	1	124.4	127.9
IT035C1	Udine	99	19.1	1	17.0	20.0	1	23.5	27.7	125.7	2	123.4	126.0
IT036C1	La Spezia	104	16.1	2	15.6	15.5	3	30.4	27.8	115.4	2	112.2	114.9
IT037C1	Lecce	112	13.6				2	19.7	22.0	114.7			
IT038C1	Barletta	94	19.4	1	19.7	17.7				115.5	1	113.7	115.5
IT039C1	Pesaro	96	18.9	1	26.9	18.3				114.0	1	94.2	113.5
IT040C1	Como	104	23.4				1	39.9	35.4	148.8			
IT041C1	Pisa	95	21.6	1	18.1	18.0	1	32.7	32.3	117.1	1	111.4	117.0
IT042C1	Treviso	111	25.8	1	28.9	27.7	1	27.1	31.4	128.5	1	128.4	128.0
IT043C1	Varese	106	22.3	1	21.6	21.9	1	32.8	34.2	146.8	1	148.7	146.4
IT044C1	Busto Arsizio	103	28.6	1	30.4	27.0				149.7	1	148.0	149.2
IT045C1	Asti	80	21.1	1	22.8	23.2	1	34.0	33.3	130.1	1	128.0	129.7
IT046C1	Pavia	75	25.1	1	28.6	26.8	1	34.9	31.4	138.0	1	142.5	137.7
IT047C1	Massa	79	17.2				1	18.1	25.3	117.0			
IT048C1	Cosenza	85	17.4	1	20.3	20.1				109.8	1	112.1	109.7
IT052C1	Savona	67	15.8	1	12.9	14.8	1	27.9	28.2	120.7	1	121.3	120.3
IT054C1	Matera	58	14.8							119.9			
IT056C1	Acireale	66	14.5							112.1			
IT057C1	Avellino	68	20.3	1	18.9	22.5	1	21.0	25.3	125.9	1	142.2	125.7
IT058C1	Pordenone	61	22.8				1	26.6	29.6	125.8			
IT060C1	Lecco	51	21.4	1	21.5	24.0	1	35.3	31.2	149.3	1	155.9	149.3
IT061C1	Altamura	70	16.7				1	24.2	24.1	118.7			
IT062C1	Bitonto	59	15.0							113.6			
IT063C1	Molfetta	61	16.5				1	22.3	23.4	115.5			
IT064C1	Battipaglia	53	19.1	1	19.3	21.7				116.8	1	128.1	115.4
IT065C1	Bisceglie	54	15.4							113.9			
IT066C1	Carpi	72	23.4	1	27.7	22.3				137.7	1	137.1	136.9
IT067C1	Cerignola	60	17.9							121.4			
IT068C1	Gallarate	77	28.2							147.5			
IT069C1	Gela	76	11.7	1	7.5	11.1	1	24.6	25.0	115.2	1	127.7	117.5
IT070C1	Saronno	48	31.3	1	26.7	32.7				153.7	1	142.5	153.6
IT071C1	Bagheria	64	11.9							111.5			
IT072C1	Anzio	69	17.7							107.4			
IT073C1	Sassuolo	48	21.2	1	18.7	22.0				135.0	1	139.7	135.5
IT501C1	Messina	245	12.7				1	30.0	26.7	101.7	1	100.9	100.8
IT502C1	Prato	202	23.6	1	29.3	25.9	1	27.7	34.0	119.9			
IT503C1	Parma	194	21.0	1	19.8	23.8	1	33.6	32.8	137.2	1	131.4	137.0
IT504C1	Livorno	154	20.8	2	17.2	17.1	1	41.1	34.3	122.4			
IT505C1	Reggio nell'Emilia	183	21.4	1	22.8	22.3	1	34.5	34.4	136.6	1	135.1	136.9
IT506C1	Ravenna	154	17.0	1	19.8	19.3	1	28.4	30.0	122.1	1	121.8	119.1
IT507C1	Ferrara	146	20.4	1	18.8	20.4	1	36.0	33.1	133.6	1	129.6	133.6
IT508C1	Rimini	155	19.4	1	20.7	19.4	1	41.6	34.9	119.6	1	124.1	120.2
IT509C1	Siracusa	126	13.2	2	16.7	12.4	2	18.0	21.1	106.9	1	71.0	106.6
IT510C1	Monza	171	39.8	1	45.7	41.5				146.2	2	140.1	145.4
IT511C1	Bergamo	163	28.9	1	28.0	30.1	1	38.6	37.8	148.9	1	167.0	146.1
IT512C1	Forlì	122	18.3	1	21.5	20.4	1	28.3	30.7	124.7	1	121.5	124.8
IT513C1	Latina	126	19.1	2	23.2	22.3	1	27.7	26.5	105.1	1	91.8	102.1
IT514C1	Vicenza	133	27.6	1	31.8	28.8	1	31.7	34.7	139.7	1	145.4	138.4
IT515C1	Terni	112	18.2	1	16.9	18.1	2	22.7	23.9	121.7	1	118.4	121.4
IT516C1	Novara	110	23.7	1	26.9	26.1	1	34.8	32.0	138.6	1	124.3	138.5
IT517C1	Giugliano in Campania	201	22.6							114.4			
IT518C1	Alessandria	90	23.7	1	24.9	22.1	1	32.4	33.2	131.8	1	143.6	132.7
IT519C1	Arezzo	102	15.0	1	14.8	15.6	1	31.0	28.9	116.0	1	116.0	115.9
IT520C1	Grosseto	78	14.8	1	16.8	14.6	1	35.1	29.3	112.5			

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	NO ₂							O ₃			
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB
IT521C1	Brindisi	89	13.4	2	12.3	14.9	2	21.0	21.9	115.5	1	113.9	115.7
IT522C1	Trapani	94	11.5	1	11.9	9.6				110.0	1	106.7	109.9
IT523C1	Ragusa	72	11.2	2	9.8	10.4				108.1	1	101.8	106.6
IT524C1	Andria	101	19.5				1	24.4	25.5	116.2			
IT525C1	Trani	57	15.9							115.9			
IT526C1	L'Aquila	68	15.9	2	14.3	15.9				115.3	2	114.1	113.7
LT001C1	Vilnius	552	15.2	2	14.5	15.1	1	30.4	27.0	105.8	1	108.4	105.5
LT002C1	Kaunas	325	15.1				1	19.6	22.1	105.2			
LT003C1	Panevėžys	105	15.3	1	17.3	14.8				103.0	1	101.6	103.0
LT004C1	Alytus	60	13.5							106.9			
LT501C1	Klaipėda	164	11.8				2	20.5	19.4	106.1			
LT502C1	Šiauliai	113	13.6				1	18.8	20.3	103.7			
LU001C1	Luxembourg	103	23.7	1	30.6	25.5	1	27.5	33.5	106.6	1	105.0	106.3
LV001C1	Rīga	669	16.9	1	22.2	18.1				89.1	1	76.9	82.0
LV002C1	Liepāja	77	9.2				2	17.8	15.8	107.9			
LV003C1	Jelgava	64	11.6							101.2			
LV501C1	Daugavpils	96	11.2							104.4			
MT001C1	Valletta (greater)	228	13.6				1	30.3	27.3	104.0			
NL001C2	Greater 's-Gravenhage	752	23.5	2	23.3	23.4	1	29.9	31.5	101.4	2	93.6	101.6
NL002C2	Greater Amsterdam	934	24.2	5	20.8	22.5	5	36.7	34.8	99.5	2	104.4	97.4
NL003C2	Greater Rotterdam	1 232	25.7	4	25.5	25.8	5	32.8	32.9	98.7	3	100.5	98.5
NL004C2	Greater Utrecht	422	21.7	1	18.9	21.9	2	24.9	27.3	103.8	1	109.8	105.4
NL005C2	Greater Eindhoven	265	22.2	1	16.9	19.3	2	24.1	28.7	108.2	1	102.1	108.6
NL006C1	Tilburg	216	22.5							106.1			
NL007C1	Groningen	195	16.5	1	10.7	11.6	1	24.2	27.0	106.2	1	112.8	105.4
NL008C1	Enschede	155	18.7							121.8			
NL009C2	Greater Arnhem	186	20.1							110.8			
NL010C2	Greater Heerlen	209	17.8	1	14.8	15.2	1	23.5	32.1	114.9	1	119.2	113.8
NL011C1	Almere	190	18.9							112.8			
NL012C1	Breda	180	22.0	1	21.6	23.4	1	29.5	28.7	103.6	1	96.9	102.9
NL013C1	Nijmegen	173	20.8	1	19.8	21.9	1	29.0	29.4	108.5	1	107.7	107.8
NL014C1	Apeldoorn	163	18.2							114.6			
NL015C1	Leeuwarden	124	14.0							104.3			
NL016C2	Greater Sittard-Geleen	129	19.3							112.7			
NL018C1	Hilversum	108	18.1							109.2			
NL020C1	Roosendaal	81	20.9							102.3			
NL021C2	Greater Nissewaard	145	22.6							100.2			
NL023C1	Purmerend	82	18.7							105.4			
NL026C1	Alphen aan den Rijn	112	20.1							100.3			
NL028C1	Bergen op Zoom	68	20.4							103.0			
NL030C1	Gouda	75	22.0							100.5			
NL031C1	Hoorn	73	17.8							105.8			
NL032C2	Greater Middelburg	93	16.5							105.3			
NL501C2	Greater Haarlem	270	19.2				1	23.4	26.9	104.2			
NL502C1	Zaanstad	152	20.2	1	21.3	21.7				101.0			
NL503C1	's-Hertogenbosch	156	21.6							104.6			
NL504C1	Amersfoort	152	19.1							108.0			
NL505C1	Maastricht	125	19.6							113.4			
NL507C2	Greater Leiden	257	21.3							103.8			
NL508C1	Haarlemmermeer	167	20.7							100.8			
NL509C1	Zoetermeer	120	23.0							99.5			
NL511C1	Zwolle	122	18.3							110.2			
NL512C2	Greater Ede	156	18.4							110.2			
NL513C1	Deventer	103	18.1							112.5			
NL514C2	Greater Alkmaar	200	15.7							107.0			
NL515C1	Venlo	107	21.6							115.4			

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	
NL516C1	Helmond	93	20.0								110.5			
NL517C1	Hengelo	84	18.3								121.9			
NL519C1	Almelo	79	17.8								117.0			
NL520C1	Lelystad	76	17.9								110.1			
NL521C1	Oss	99	18.8								106.5			
NL522C1	Assen	70	15.4								109.1			
NL524C1	Veenendaal	63	19.2								108.0			
NL528C1	Greater Heemskerk	92	18.1								103.4			
NL529C1	Greater Soest	71	16.5								110.0			
NO001C1	Oslo	613	19.0					8	30.6	29.6	95.3	1	92.2	94.6
NO002C1	Bergen	260	13.3	2	12.3	12.1	3	28.8	27.8		96.1	1	95.3	94.7
NO003C1	Trondheim	175	14.0	1	18.2	14.8	3	24.6	24.5		98.3			
NO004C1	Stavanger	133	10.6	1	9.6	11.7	1	25.8	24.1		91.9			
NO005C1	Kristiansand	84	8.4	1	12.4	8.6	1	23.1	20.7		101.6			
NO006C1	Tromsø	68	7.9				1	31.6	24.5		102.6			
PL001C	M. Warszawa	1 759	24.1	3	22.7	23.4	1	49.7	43.6		111.2	4	108.4	108.9
PL002C	M. Łódź	747	18.6	2	18.2	18.8	1	28.0	32.5		115.2	2	117.9	115.2
PL003C	M. Kraków	782	25.9	1	32.3	24.6	2	49.3	45.1		112.2	1	111.0	112.1
PL004C	M. Wrocław	642	19.7	2	17.0	16.7	1	44.1	37.5		115.3	2	116.0	116.4
PL005C	M. Poznań	601	21.2	3	21.7	20.1					110.4	1	112.2	109.8
PL006C	M. Gdańsk	471	16.1	5	15.6	14.5					99.5	2	92.9	96.8
PL007C	M. Szczecin	433	15.0	1	12.4	13.0	1	19.2	24.2		112.6	1	114.8	113.0
PL008C	M. Bydgoszcz	367	17.3	1	18.9	17.1	1	26.4	27.9		108.7	1	103.4	108.6
PL009C	M. Lublin	359	18.3	1	19.5	19.1					109.3	1	111.2	109.5
PL010C	M. Katowice	314	24.0	1	28.0	24.5	1	54.3	43.4		115.8	1	113.7	116.4
PL011C	M. Białystok	306	14.7	1	12.6	14.4					108.8	1	108.9	108.8
PL012C	M. Kielce	208	18.5	1	21.0	18.6					115.1	1	117.1	115.6
PL013C	M. Toruń	209	14.3	1	10.4	13.8	1	18.1	24.9		109.2	1	103.6	109.3
PL014C	M. Olsztyn	179	12.5	1	12.7	12.7					109.9	1	106.8	110.7
PL015C	M. Rzeszów	192	15.7	1	15.8	17.8	1	33.3	32.3		108.8	1	105.4	108.6
PL016C	M. Opole	137	17.0	1	16.6	18.2					116.0	1	109.1	116.3
PL017C	M. Gorzów Wielkopolski	129	16.1	1	18.2	17.1					112.2	1	106.3	112.0
PL018C	M. Zielona Góra	140	13.3	1	15.2	13.9					120.7	1	113.6	120.0
PL019C	M. Jelenia Góra	88	13.5	1	10.8	10.1					117.2	1	118.9	117.1
PL020C	M. Nowy Sącz	93	19.0	1	22.2	17.9					111.3			
PL021C	M. Suwałki	70	12.4								106.2			
PL022C	M. Konin	84	14.3	1	12.4	16.1					112.4	1	103.4	111.9
PL023C	M. Żory	65	20.3								114.8			
PL024C	M. Częstochowa	244	18.5	1	17.7	18.7	1	39.0	35.7		113.8	1	108.8	113.6
PL025C	M. Radom	229	19.0	1	22.4	19.5					111.8	1	116.6	111.7
PL026C	M. Płock	128	14.4	2	13.3	15.3					113.6	2	113.9	112.4
PL027C	M. Kalisz	110	16.4	1	12.3	14.1					116.0	1	119.1	115.7
PL028C	M. Koszalin	113	12.1	1	12.5	13.4	1	22.2	19.7		110.4	1	118.1	110.2
PL029C	M. Słupsk	99	12.0	1	10.7	10.4					105.8	1	109.1	105.7
PL030C	M. Jastrzębie-Zdrój	98	19.2								113.7			
PL031C	M. Siedlce	80	15.5								108.5			
PL032C	M. Piotrków Trybunalski	78	18.3	1	18.5	17.8					112.7	1	112.3	112.5
PL033C	Lubin	78	15.0								120.3			
PL034C	Piła	75	14.1	1	14.0	14.6					112.6			
PL035C	Inowrocław	77	15.1	1	10.0	12.2					107.4			
PL036C	Ostrowiec Świętokrzyski	78	15.7								113.9			
PL037C	Gniezno	73	15.5								109.8			
PL038C	Stargard	71	13.5								111.1			
PL039C	Ostrów Wielkopolski	77	15.2								117.7			
PL040C	M. Przemyśl	70	14.7	1	14.8	15.4					109.8	1	118.0	109.7
PL041C	M. Zamość	70	15.9	1	15.5	13.4					110.1			

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	
PL042C	M. Chełm	70	15.4								110.0			
PL043C	Pabianice	75	17.1								115.7			
PL044C	Głogów	71	15.4								119.3			
PL045C	Stalowa Wola	67	16.7								113.9			
PL046C	Tomaszów Mazowiecki	69	16.3								115.5			
PL047C	M. Łomża	67	14.4	1	13.0	12.5					110.2			
PL048C	M. Leszno	65	14.3								118.2			
PL049C	Świdnica	63	15.3								114.1			
PL050C	Zgierz	59	15.0	1	15.7	16.1					115.4			
PL051C	Tczew	63	14.7								102.6			
PL052C	Ełk	60	11.2	1	10.0	12.5					108.0	1	108.7	108.5
PL501C	M. Gdynia	265	13.0	3	14.6	13.7					99.6	2	103.0	100.2
PL502C	M. Sosnowiec	261	23.7	1	22.2	24.9					114.4			
PL503C	M. Gliwice	211	21.5	1	20.6	22.0					114.7			
PL504C	M. Zabrze	173	22.0	1	21.9	21.7					114.8	1	114.5	116.0
PL505C	M. Bytom	199	22.7								116.6			
PL506C	M. Bielsko-Biała	185	19.0				1	29.6	33.1		111.8	1	111.4	111.4
PL507C	M. Ruda Śląska	154	21.8								116.0			
PL508C	M. Rybnik	161	18.9	1	20.5	18.1					115.0	1	113.4	115.7
PL509C	M. Tychy	133	22.2	1	21.9	20.2					115.6			
PL511C	M. Wałbrzych	132	13.2	1	13.1	12.9					114.4	1	114.2	114.4
PL512C	M. Elbląg	126	12.6	1	12.1	14.2					106.7	1	112.9	107.0
PL513C	M. Włocławek	119	15.1	1	13.2	11.5	1	24.6	25.5		114.1	1	109.3	113.7
PL514C	M. Tarnów	121	18.3	1	19.5	20.6	1	26.8	29.7		108.5	1	113.7	108.6
PL515C	M. Chorzów	160	25.0								116.3			
PL516C	M. Legnica	106	16.8	1	18.3	15.5					116.1	1	117.5	114.5
PL517C	M. Grudziądz	102	14.0				1	19.9	22.9		104.1			
PT001C1	Lisboa	628	25.9	2	23.6	23.0	3	41.6	35.4		95.4	2	97.5	100.1
PT002C1	Porto	238	28.6								78.4	1	90.6	83.8
PT003C1	Braga	191	17.8								81.9	1	64.0	80.7
PT004C1	Funchal													
PT005C1	Coimbra	151	15.8								91.4	1	89.8	88.5
PT006C1	Setúbal	134	13.8	1	14.1	14.9	1	17.9	21.1		105.1	1	104.5	104.9
PT007C1	Ponta Delgada													
PT008C1	Aveiro	85	14.4	1	9.2	11.1	1	19.5	19.9		91.8	1	69.6	87.0
PT009C1	Faro	68	8.6	1	9.9	10.0					113.1	1	115.1	113.5
PT010C1	Seixal	162	17.5								99.7			
PT011C1	Amadora	168	21.5	2	23.9	23.0					102.5	2	97.7	99.9
PT012C1	Almada	180	19.7	1	22.3	21.4					98.6	1	98.5	92.6
PT013C1	Odivelas	157	21.3				1	25.2	31.2		96.6			
PT014C1	Viseu	103	11.0								103.9			
PT015C1	Valongo	106	21.5	1	26.8	23.2					74.0			
PT016C1	Viana do Castelo	93	10.3								89.6			
PT017C1	Paredes	99	16.4								80.3			
PT018C1	Barreiro	100	17.9	1	15.0	19.1					102.8	1	108.3	103.7
PT019C1	Póvoa de Varzim	84	14.3								81.2			
PT501C1	Sintra	385	16.2	1	12.2	15.8					102.9	1	106.0	101.3
PT502C1	Vila Nova de Gaia	326	22.7								82.2	1	82.1	75.9
PT503C1	Matosinhos	205	24.3				1	47.7	34.6		76.6	1	58.9	77.4
PT504C1	Gondomar	179	22.7								76.3			
PT505C1	Guimarães	190	16.0								83.2			
PT508C1	Vila Franca de Xira	152	18.6	1	18.1	19.7					104.4	1	105.5	104.0
RO001C1	MUNICIPIUL BUCURESTI	1 940	34.9				1	57.4	53.4		96.6			
RO002C1	MUNICIPIUL CLUJ-NAPOCA	331	29.6	1	35.9	28.9	1	60.2	45.2		82.8	1	55.4	82.4
RO003C1	MUNICIPIUL TIMISOARA	326	28.1	1	32.4	25.8	1	49.8	43.5		99.9			
RO004C1	MUNICIPIUL CRAIOVA	272	24.1				1	32.3	35.1		98.1			

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			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB
RO005C1	MUNICIPIUL BRAILA	181	20.8				1	23.7	28.2	100.5			
RO006C1	MUNICIPIUL ORADEA	199	24.6	1	27.8	24.6				101.2			
RO007C1	MUNICIPIUL BACAU	149	23.7							93.1			
RO008C1	MUNICIPIUL ARAD	159	20.2	1	18.1	20.9	1	25.3	28.7	104.6	1	113.0	105.1
RO009C1	MUNICIPIUL SIBIU	148	25.6							95.0	1	102.9	94.9
RO010C1	MUNICIPIUL TIRGU MURES	147	25.2	1	27.2	25.3				94.0	1	85.5	93.9
RO011C1	MUNIC. PIATRA NEAMT	86	21.4							89.5			
RO012C1	MUNICIPIUL CALARASI	73	19.5	1	16.5	17.6	1	26.5	28.0	99.9	1	103.4	99.8
RO013C1	MUNICIPIUL GIURGIU	62	22.8	1	29.3	22.7	1	32.4	31.6	98.5	1	92.9	98.3
RO014C1	MUNICIPIUL ALBA IULIA	64	23.9							94.7			
RO015C1	MUNICIPIUL FOCSANI	81	22.3							97.0			
RO016C1	MUNICIPIUL TIRGU JIU	86	25.8							98.9			
RO017C1	MUNICIPIUL TULCEA	75	21.3							99.4			
RO018C1	MUNICIPIUL TIRGOVISTE	83	23.3							94.5			
RO019C1	MUNICIPIUL SLATINA	72	22.6							100.5			
RO020C1	MUNICIPIUL BIRLAD	56	20.4							95.5			
RO021C1	MUNICIPIUL ROMAN	53	21.7							93.2			
RO022C1	MUNICIPIUL BISTRITA	76	23.4	1	26.3	23.9				92.7			
RO501C1	MUNICIPIUL CONSTANTA	284	22.6							90.8	1	92.0	90.5
RO502C1	MUNICIPIUL IASI	311	24.8	1	30.9	25.7	1	43.0	37.9	93.4			
RO503C1	MUNICIPIUL GALATI	253	22.9	2	19.1	19.3				101.8	2	100.2	102.1
RO504C1	MUNICIPIUL BRASOV	256	29.4	1	33.2	28.2	2	46.0	41.1	88.8	1	80.5	88.1
RO505C1	MUNICIPIUL PLOIESTI	216	25.0	1	24.6	23.7	2	31.9	33.7	86.6	1	73.8	85.7
RO506C1	MUNICIPIUL PITESTI	161	21.4				1	22.1	29.8	100.9	1	118.5	101.1
RO507C1	MUNICIPIUL BAIA MARE	128	19.7	2	15.0	17.2	1	25.0	28.8	94.5	2	97.8	96.6
RO508C1	MUNICIPIUL BUZAU	119	22.7							95.8	1	94.5	95.7
RO509C1	MUNICIPIUL SATU MARE	107	18.4	1	17.6	17.9				99.9	1	91.2	99.2
RO510C1	MUNICIPIUL BOTOSANI	111	25.4	1	31.0	25.3				94.1			
RO511C1	MUNIC. RAMNICU VALCEA	102	24.4	1	18.4	21.1				99.0	1	94.3	98.3
RO512C1	MUNICIPIUL SUCEAVA	99	19.6	1	15.7	21.2				93.8			
RO513C1	M. DROBETA-TURNU SEVER	99	22.5							99.6			
SE001C1	Stockholm	967	11.7	4	10.0	11.9	8	27.5	26.1	103.5	1	103.5	104.7
SE002K1	Greater Göteborg	581	12.3	1	17.0	13.5	2	27.2	25.2	99.8	1	101.2	99.1
SE003C1	Malmö	312	11.7	1	10.3	14.1	3	20.9	19.8	106.4	1	107.4	105.3
SE004C1	Jönköping	130	8.4				1	22.3	18.9	104.6			
SE005C1	Umeå	117	5.1				1	25.8	20.7	97.6			
SE006C1	Uppsala	203	8.1	1	7.5	11.1	1	33.5	25.4	100.8			
SE007C1	Linköping	149	9.0							103.6			
SE008C1	Örebro	139	8.5	1	9.1	10.9	1	11.9	16.6	103.3			
SE009C1	Södertälje	91	8.7				1	24.3	20.6	105.0			
SE501C1	Västerås	141	9.4				1	11.2	16.5	103.8			
SE502C1	Norrköping	133	9.7							102.6			
SE503C1	Helsingborg	134	11.4	1	16.0	13.3	2	21.9	19.4	103.4	1	98.8	104.6
SE504C1	Lund	117	9.5	1	9.2	11.4	1	12.5	15.6	105.2	1	106.1	104.9
SE505C1	Borås	105	8.9				1	25.0	21.0	102.5			
SI001C1	Ljubljana	285	21.3	1	25.0	24.8				114.9	1	115.3	115.2
SI002C1	Maribor	118	18.1				1	24.5	24.0	112.6	1	116.8	111.9
SK001C1	Bratislava	413	18.2	2	15.6	17.4	1	37.2	33.3	117.3	2	124.0	116.3
SK002C1	Košice	250	18.6				1	27.7	30.5	109.4	1	111.0	112.0
SK003C1	Banská Bystrica	85	13.9	1	8.9	12.5	1	29.3	29.8	103.6	1	102.7	104.5
SK004C1	Nitra	81	14.8	1	10.2	10.8	1	30.6	28.2	112.1	1	114.7	111.1
SK005C1	Prešov	96	16.7				1	39.0	32.4	112.1			
SK006C1	Žilina	89	18.8	1	21.4	20.7				105.2	1	107.7	105.0
SK007C1	Trnava	70	14.6				1	33.8	28.3	115.4			
SK008C1	Trenčín	60	15.3				1	26.6	26.4	110.8			
UK002C1	Birmingham	1 082	22.0	1	18.1	20.8	1	32.0	35.4	86.2	1	95.3	84.0

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	NO ₂							O ₃			
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB
UK003C1	Leeds	753	22.7	1	28.3	24.5	1	28.4	33.7	86.6	1	86.5	87.8
UK004C1	Glasgow City	670	21.9	1	24.2	22.0	3	38.4	37.2	86.8	1	87.0	85.1
UK005C1	Bradford	533	21.4				1	41.8	33.6	88.5			
UK006C1	Liverpool	496	20.8							84.0			
UK007C1	City of Edinburgh	485	19.1	1	20.8	19.3	1	50.4	39.5	85.6	1	83.8	85.2
UK008C1	Manchester	512	30.0	1	36.3	30.2				82.3	1	68.0	81.6
UK009C1	Cardiff	357	18.4				1	29.0	35.2	89.5			
UK010C1	Sheffield	557	21.8	2	26.2	23.3	1	38.0	33.3	87.2	1	85.9	85.5
UK011C1	Bristol, City of	457	21.0	1	23.4	21.0	1	39.2	38.3	88.6	1	86.1	88.4
UK012C2	Belfast	351	17.6				1	45.4	37.2	87.2	1	84.1	83.4
UK013C1	Newcastle upon Tyne	288	22.1	1	32.1	22.8	1	38.2	32.6	88.6	1	89.9	87.6
UK014C1	Leicester	383	22.5	1	24.1	21.1	1	36.8	35.3	89.9	1	88.5	90.9
UK016C1	Aberdeen City	226	14.7	1	16.7	15.5	2	35.4	31.2	83.0	1	88.3	73.3
UK017C1	Cambridge	135	17.9				1	27.4	27.5	94.3			
UK018C1	Exeter	121	13.8				1	27.9	27.1	91.0			
UK019C1	Lincoln	99	19.0				1	29.2	28.1	92.3			
UK020C1	Gravesham	109	20.6							91.6			
UK021C1	Stevenage	91	18.1							95.3			
UK022C1	Wrexham	138	15.5				1	16.4	21.1	90.2			
UK023C1	Portsmouth	212	19.1	1	17.5	17.6	1	27.8	28.0	85.5	1	80.0	85.3
UK024C1	Worcester	103	17.7							88.7			
UK025C1	Coventry	317	20.9	1	20.4	20.4	1	30.9	30.6	88.6	1	87.8	90.0
UK026C1	Kingston upon Hull, City of	273	20.4	1	22.5	20.7	1	26.4	28.5	88.0	1	86.6	87.4
UK027C1	Stoke-on-Trent	261	21.5	1	24.0	21.2	1	51.2	36.1	86.3	1	82.9	85.0
UK028C1	Wolverhampton	255	20.4							86.6			
UK029C1	Nottingham	368	23.7	1	27.7	24.4	1	33.1	33.6	86.3	1	83.8	85.9
UK030C1	Wirral	320	17.1	1	16.4	17.9	1	23.3	28.1	88.2	1	91.3	88.1
UK031C1	Bath and N. East Somerset	183	15.0							91.5			
UK032C1	Thurrock	160	21.1	1	23.4	22.5	1	26.2	25.9	90.4			
UK033C1	Guildford	153	20.4							91.2			
UK034C1	Thanet	134	12.7							95.4			
UK035C1	Nuneaton and Bedworth	129	18.8							87.7			
UK038C1	Waveney	118	10.7							95.3			
UK040C1	Tunbridge Wells	127	16.1							95.2			
UK041C1	Ashford	119	13.5							93.7			
UK043C1	East Staffordshire	121	17.6	1	18.3	19.5				87.9			
UK044C1	Darlington	112	15.9							91.6			
UK045C1	Worthing	113	14.0				1	33.1	27.9	89.9			
UK046C1	Mansfield	112	19.6							89.7			
UK047C1	Chesterfield	110	18.1	1	12.4	17.3	1	17.4	24.8	88.2			
UK050C1	Burnley	94	20.0							90.4			
UK051C1	Great Yarmouth	98	9.9							96.3			
UK052C1	Woking	104	23.2							89.8			
UK053C1	Hartlepool	93	15.1	1	12.4	14.9				86.7			
UK054C1	Cannock Chase	108	17.8				1	21.4	27.3	87.5			
UK055C1	Eastbourne	107	12.8	1	11.5	12.3				92.1			
UK056C1	Hastings	94	14.2							94.5			
UK057C1	Hyndburn	82	19.5							88.5			
UK059C1	Redditch	86	17.2							90.0			
UK060C1	Tamworth	82	19.0							88.2			
UK061C1	Harlow	84	18.9							93.3			
UK062C1	Halton	126	20.6				1	33.9	29.8	85.9			
UK101C1	City of London	4	34.0							84.1			
UK102C1	Barking and Dagenham	188	24.4							89.9			
UK103C1	Barnet	380	25.5							87.8			
UK104C1	Bexley	258	23.2	1	22.7	22.3				90.7			

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	NO ₂							O ₃				
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	
UK105C1	Brent	301	30.4								85.7			
UK106C1	Bromley	319	21.3								91.0			
UK107C1	Camden	192	34.4	1	31.5	33.5	1	42.7	46.4		83.3	1	78.0	84.1
UK108C1	Croydon	368	23.1								90.9			
UK109C1	Ealing	322	31.3								85.5			
UK110C1	Enfield	318	24.1								90.5			
UK111C1	Greenwich	237	25.6	1	17.3	21.3					90.5	1	92.1	91.2
UK112C1	Hackney	265	32.3								84.8			
UK113C1	Hammersmith and Fulham	188	34.2								82.7			
UK114C1	Haringey	246	27.8	1	21.9	25.2	1	37.3	40.1		89.3	1	91.2	89.3
UK115C1	Harrow	250	27.3								89.5			
UK116C1	Havering	239	21.2								90.9			
UK117C1	Hillingdon	303	29.8	1	44.7	32.9					86.4	1	77.4	81.6
UK118C1	Hounslow	270	31.8								84.7			
UK119C1	Islington	205	33.6								85.1			
UK120C1	Kensington and Chelsea	151	36.1	1	27.3	32.2					82.7	1	94.1	82.7
UK121C1	Kingston upon Thames	176	26.9								87.0			
UK122C1	Lambeth	324	31.1								86.5			
UK123C1	Lewisham	272	26.4								89.1			
UK124C1	Merton	191	27.5								85.1			
UK125C1	Newham	328	28.9								89.3			
UK126C1	Redbridge	292	24.1								91.0			
UK127C1	Richmond upon Thames	209	29.8								85.8			
UK128C1	Southwark	271	31.5					1	38.8	42.8	86.2			
UK129C1	Sutton	200	23.9								90.3			
UK130C1	Tower Hamlets	258	33.4					1	35.0	44.0	84.1			
UK131C1	Waltham Forest	240	26.6								89.3			
UK132C1	Wandsworth	323	30.9								84.6			
UK133C1	Westminster	228	36.8	1	33.7	34.9	1	62.7	49.7		82.8			
UK501C1	Kirklees	425	21.0								87.4			
UK502C1	North Lanarkshire	350	18.2								90.7			
UK503C1	Wakefield	328	21.3								87.6			
UK504C1	Dudley	314	20.1								87.9			
UK505C1	Wigan	322	20.8	1	19.3	20.6					85.8	1	91.8	86.8
UK506C1	Doncaster	306	20.1					1	30.1	30.0	88.5			
UK507C1	Stockport	292	26.1								84.4			
UK508C1	Sefton	286	15.7								87.7			
UK509C1	Sandwell	305	22.3					1	33.5	34.2	86.6			
UK510C1	Sunderland	274	17.9	1	12.8	15.4	1	17.4	24.3		90.0	1	90.6	93.0
UK511C1	Bolton	283	23.4								84.8			
UK512C1	Walsall	269	20.2	1	16.1	18.7					87.3	1	91.1	87.7
UK513C1	Medway	264	19.9					1	24.4	29.7	91.7			
UK514C1	Rotherham	267	21.4								87.2			
UK515C1	Brighton and Hove	280	15.5	1	15.2	14.3					91.7	1	85.7	88.8
UK516C1	Plymouth	262	14.3	1	18.9	16.7	1	18.8	24.9		91.7	1	90.0	91.0
UK517C1	Swansea	245	13.2					1	24.1	25.9	89.9			
UK518C1	Derby	261	20.8					1	35.0	32.8	87.1			
UK519C1	Barnsley	230	20.0	1	16.6	18.8					87.7	1	90.3	87.6
UK520C1	Southampton	245	23.2	1	27.8	22.6	1	32.5	32.1		85.4	1	81.3	85.7
UK521C1	Oldham	226	25.8					1	30.4	29.7	86.4			
UK522C1	Salford	231	28.2	1	25.4	27.9					82.7			
UK523C1	Tameside	219	26.1								86.4			
UK524C1	Trafford	228	26.7								82.8			
UK525C1	Milton Keynes	253	18.4								94.4			
UK526C1	Rochdale	216	24.0								86.4			
UK527C1	Solihull	218	19.6								85.7			

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	NO ₂							O ₃				
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	
UK528C1	Northampton	218	18.3								92.2	1	100.6	91.4
UK529C1	North Tyneside	198	19.7								91.2			
UK530C1	Gateshead	208	20.3								88.3			
UK531C1	Warrington	204	21.6								85.2			
UK532C1	Luton	217	20.8					1	39.3	34.4	92.3			
UK533C1	York	201	17.7	1	14.8	18.5	1	26.0	26.6		90.6			
UK534C1	Bury	180	23.9					1	27.2	30.7	84.8			
UK535C1	Swindon	213	16.2	1	13.5	16.1					89.4			
UK536C1	Stockton-on-Tees	192	16.2					2	15.1	19.1	87.8			
UK537C1	St. Helens	193	19.6					1	33.4	30.5	85.3			
UK538C1	Basildon	185	19.0								89.2			
UK539C1	Bournemouth	192	14.9	1	11.5	12.3					93.7	1	99.2	92.7
UK540C1	Wycombe	187	21.6								92.6			
UK541C1	Southend-on-Sea	182	18.5	1	17.9	18.8					90.7	1	87.9	89.9
UK542C1	Telford and Wrekin	170	16.3	1	14.9	16.5					89.8			
UK543C1	North East Lincolnshire	163	16.7	1	13.5	17.3					88.2			
UK544C1	Chelmsford	173	17.1								92.8			
UK545C1	Peterborough	205	17.0								93.0			
UK546C1	Colchester	178	14.5								91.1			
UK547C1	South Tyneside	151	18.9								89.8			
UK548C1	Basingstoke and Deane	176	17.7								91.3			
UK549C1	Bedford	176	16.8								94.6			
UK550C1	Dundee City	156	14.8	1	11.0	14.4					92.3			
UK551C1	Falkirk	161	18.0								89.5			
UK552C1	Reading	184	23.7					1	26.7	31.6	88.6			
UK553C1	Blackpool	153	14.8	1	12.2	14.0					93.4	1	95.7	93.6
UK554C1	Maidstone	162	17.1								93.9			
UK555C1	Poole	161	14.3								93.3			
UK556C1	Dacorum	153	20.6								92.9			
UK557C1	Blackburn with Darwen	150	20.8					1	20.2	25.1	88.3			
UK558C1	Newport	153	18.4	1	19.9	18.0					91.1			
UK559C1	Middlesbrough	148	16.8								87.8			
UK560C1	Oxford	160	19.4	1	15.9	15.9	1	42.0	34.6		88.8			
UK561C1	Torbay	132	11.4								93.3			
UK562C1	Preston	150	19.1	1	22.8	20.7					87.9	1	87.0	87.3
UK563C1	St Albans	156	20.6								91.7			
UK564C1	Warwick	138	17.1	1	17.8	18.2	1	16.3	23.8		89.0	1	75.4	88.3
UK565C1	Newcastle-under-Lyme	126	20.1								85.5			
UK566C1	Norwich	162	15.9	1	12.7	14.8					91.4	1	91.0	90.9
UK567C1	Slough	148	29.5								85.1			
UK568C2	Cheshire West and Chester	348	17.9								86.7			
UK569C1	Ipswich	144	16.5								90.7			
UK571C1	Cheltenham	118	18.3								90.8			
UK572C1	Gloucester	132	18.4								88.8			
UK573C1	Bracknell Forest	135	23.6								88.8			
UK575C1	Carlisle	110	14.2					1	26.0	25.1	93.5			
UK576C1	Crawley	113	19.5								88.5			
UK577C1	Watford	112	24.7								92.2			
UK578C1	Gosport	84	18.2								85.1			
UK579C1	Eastleigh	131	20.6								86.3			
UK580C1	Rushmoor	106	22.8								90.6			
UK581C1	Rugby	107	17.1								90.7			
UK582C1	Corby	60	17.3								93.5			
UK583C1	Kettering	96	16.5								93.5			
UK584C1	Inverclyde (Greenock)	81	15.4					1	27.7	24.9	93.2			
UK585C1	Renfrewshire (Paisley)	184	18.4								88.9			

URAU Code	Name of City	POP	NO ₂							O ₃				
			PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	NT	CST	CMT	PWC	NB	CSB	CMB	
UK586C1	Derry & Strabane	148	10.1	1	10.6	11.7					90.1	1	86.5	90.0

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